

MICROM 2025 CONFERENCE

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
**MICROplastics in Organic-rich
Matrices**

ABSTRACT BOOK

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OF GALWAY

MICROM2025 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MICROplastics in Organic-rich Matrices

ABSTRACT BOOK

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Nataša Stojić
Galina Čurčić
Ljiljana Milošević

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CONTACT

contact@micromconference.com

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AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

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Warm Welcome

It is our great pleasure to welcome you to the First International Conference “Microplastics in Organic-Rich Matrices – MICROM 2025,” jointly organized by Educons University (Serbia), the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (Germany), and the University of Galway (Ireland). This conference marks the beginning of what we hope will become a lasting platform for scientific exchange and collaboration in the growing field of microplastic research.

The idea for MICROM emerged from one of the major challenges we faced during our own analyses of microplastics in environmental samples – presence of organic matter that interferes with accurate detection and quantification. Recognizing that this is a widespread issue among researchers working with soils, sediments, and biotic samples, we were motivated to create a space where the scientific community could come together to discuss solutions, share experiences, and explore innovative methods for sample preparation, extraction, and analysis.

In addition to technical discussions on analytical methods, sample processing, and quality assurance, MICROM 2025 will cover a broad spectrum of topics including the interaction of microplastics with organic pollutants, the occurrence and fate of microplastics in terrestrial and aquatic systems, their toxicological impacts and risk assessment, as well as innovative mitigation and remediation strategies. The conference will also address the importance of policy development, education, and public awareness as key components in tackling the growing problem of microplastic pollution.

The conference also provides a valuable opportunity to present results from ongoing research projects, exchange knowledge across disciplines, and foster networking and new collaborations among scientists, institutions, and stakeholders from across Europe and beyond.

We sincerely thank all participants, speakers, and partners who contributed to making this first edition of MICROM possible. We hope that the discussions and connections established here will inspire future research and joint actions aimed at reducing microplastic pollution and protecting our environment.

Prof. Nataša Stojić
Chair of the Conference
MICROM 2025 – Novi Sad, Serbia

Program

Day 1 – Wednesday, November 26, 2025

09:00–10:00 – Registration

10:00–10:30 – Conference Opening

10:30–11:00 – Plenary Lecture 1

Microplastics in the Environment

Speaker: **Dr. Christian Laforsch**, University of Bayreuth, Germany

Moderator: Dr. Fangzhu Wu, Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Helgoland, Germany

11:00–12:00 – Participant Presentations (Session 1)

- **Confocal Raman spectroscopy for nanoplastic detection at microgram to nanogram concentrations in complex media**, *Giulia Biagi, Aref Enayati, Barbara Rothen-Rutishauser, Patricia Taladriz-Blanco, Alke Petri-Fink*
- **Efficiency of Fenton reaction for the clean-up of groundwater and surface water matrices for various microplastic analysis methods**, *Lina Büngener, Guillaume Bucher, Dora Mehn, Douglas Gilliland*
- **Exploring analytical methodologies for monitoring microplastics in media relevant to the urban wastewater treatment Directive (EU) 2024/3019**, *Guillaume Bucher, Lina Büngener, Otmar Geiss, Dora Mehn, Douglas Gilliland*
- **Microplastics in Wastewater Sludge: A Novel Quantification Method developed by Captoplastic S.L.**, *Gonzalo Vega Marcilla, Raquel Parra Sanchez, Amparo Fernández Benito, Belén Carboneras Contreras*
- **What controls the quality of microplastic analysis? Insights from an interlaboratory study using MicroPRefs reference materials**, *Svetlana Pakhomova, Vilde Kloster Snekkevik, Bert van Bavel, Amy Lusher*
- **Methodological approaches for microplastics isolation and analysis from tissues of marine organisms (bivalves, fish)**, *Vlatka Filipović Marijić, Martina Ugrinović, Sara Šariri, Tatjana Mijošek Pavin, Marija Kuštro, Fabio Faraguna, Dajana Kučić Grgić*

12:00–12:15 – Q&A session 1

12:15–12:45 – Networking & Coffee Time

12:45–13:45 – Participant Presentations (Session 1)

- **“Up in the air, deep on the ground” - Quantification & Identification of Microplastics in Marine Sediments and Air by Pyrolysis-GC/MS**, *Michael Soll, Atsushi Watanabe, William Pipkin*
- **Multitechnique analysis of eco-corona formation on airborne polyethylene terephthalate nanoplastics interacting with bee pollen**, *Anna Placci, Marta Fadda, Irene Coralli, Junjie Wang, Andrea Zattoni, Anna Luisa Costa, Raquel Portela, Andrea Mario Giovannozzi, Andrea Mario Rossi, Daniele Fabbri, Dora Melucci, Stefano Giordani, Barbara Roda, Pierluigi Reschiglian, Simona Ortelli, Alessio Sacco, Valentina Marassi*
- **Synthetic Hydrophilic Polymers - An Emerging Class of Polymers in Soil**, *Christian Plicht, Zacharias Steinmetz*
- **Application of coagulation/flocculation process for microplastic and textile fiber removal in different water matrices**, *Sanja Vasiljević, Maja Vujić, Tijana Marjanović Srebro, Jasmina Agbaba, Radivoj Tomić, Aleksandra Tubić*

- **LDIR – automated solution for microplastic determination**, *Bojana Vujačić*
- **Using sediment cores for studying the stratification of textile microfibers in geological records of the deep sea**, *Giuseppe Suaria, Panagiota Lalioti, Andrea Paluselli, Stefano Aliani, Claudio Pellegrini, Stefania Romano, Marzia Rovere*

13:45–14:00 – Q&A session 1

14:00–15:00 – Lunch Break

15:00–15:45 – e-Poster Session

Moderator: Lara Dronjak, American University of Sharjah, Sharjah, UAE

- **Aligned method for microplastic extraction from fresh and decomposed forest litter**, *Collin J. Weber, Ole Heberer, Moritz Bigalke*
- **Analysis of microplastics in different forest soil matrices**, *Ole Heberer, Collin J. Weber*
- **Development of a protocol for extracting nanoplastics from agricultural soils using metal-doped nanoplastics**, *Pia Leban, Quynh Nhu Phan Le, Milica Velimirović, Kristof Tirez, Janja Vidmar*
- **Detection and Isolation of Microplastics from Chicken Feces**, *Anja Klančnik, Živa Zidar, Kristof Kepic, Majda Golob, Manca Kovač Viršek*
- **Fenton oxidation of municipal wastewater for microplastic analysis**, *Daphne Argyropoulou, Andriani Galani, Constantinos Noutsopoulos, Daniel Mamais, Simos Malamis*
- **Isolation and detection of large microplastics from fish intestines**, *Tomislav Kačarević, Sandra Jakšić, Milica Živkov Baloš, Jelena Petrović, Radomir Ratajac*
- **Microplastic background levels in German soils: The influence of site-specific characteristics and land-use practices**, *Sandy Placzek, Karlheinz Weinfurtner, Wiebke Mareile Heinze, Elke Bloem, Zacharias Steinmetz*
- **Microplastic Detection in Blood and Urine: A Comparative Study of Sample Preparation Methods using LDIR**, *Marina Auer, Ajay Khairnar, Thomas C. Meisel*
- **Microplastics in soil: Are smaller particles lost during the extraction process?**, *Diana Nantege, Sarmite Kernchen, Martin G. J. Löder, Christian Laforsch*
- **Mussel Tissue Digestion Protocols: Efficiency and Effects on Microplastics**, *Sevdalina H. Turmanova, Yancho H. Hristov, Dimitrina S. Kiryakova, Alexander N. Dimitrov, Emilia D. Ivanova, Plamena V. Atanasova, Ganka R. Kolchakova, Antonia S. Ilieva, Elena Y. Mollova, N. S. Todorov*
- **Nonlinear optical imaging and Nile Red staining approaches for microplastic detection: Influence of additives and structural modifications**, *Milica Popović, Mira Aničić Urošević, Aleksandar Popović, Milica Čurčić, Mihailo D. Rabasović, Tanja Pajić, Aleksandar Krmpot*
- **Optimization of microplastic analysis methods using the micro-FTIR technique**, *Madalina Calmuc, Valentina Andreea Calmuc, Nina – Nicoleta Lazar, Puiu-Lucian Georgescu, Catalina Iticescu, Mihaela Timofti*
- **Quantification of polyethylene in soils using pyrolysis-gas chromatography mass spectrometry: A comprehensive assessment of matrix interference and plastic weathering effects**, *Quynh Nhu Phan Le, Janja Vidmar, Pia Leban, Dimitrios Savvas, Vasileios Papatropoulos, Milica Velimirović*
- **Unveiling Microplastic Diversity in Wastewater Sludge: Morphology and Color Patterns**, *Dovilė Motiejauskaitė, Karolina Barčauskaitė*

- **Exposure to indoor pollutants – volatile organic compounds, phthalates, bisphenol A - in small-cell vs. non-small-cell advanced lung cancer patients**, *Jana Pavlović, Danica Sazdanić-Velikić, Mirjana Ševo, Jovan Kulić, Maja Milanović, Nataša Milošević, Nataša Milić*
- **Microbial community structure in landfill soils: Case study in Serbia**, *Gordana Racić, Igor Vukelić, Nataša Stojić, Ljiljana Milošević, Galina Ćurčić, Jozefien Demeulenaere, Caroline de Tender*
- **Managing Microplastics for Sustainable Agriculture: Legal and Policy Perspectives from the EU and Serbia**, *Biljana Panin, Ljiljana Milošević, Nataša Stojić, MIRA Pucarević, Dunja Prokić, Galina Ćurčić, Mislav Đidara, Marcela Šperanda*

15:45–16:15 – Plenary Lecture 2

Global Microplastics Monitoring and Harmonization

Speaker: **Dr. Amy Lusher**, NIVA, Oslo, Norway

Moderator: Prof. Dr. Aleksandra Tubić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

16:15–17:15 – Participant Presentations (Session 3)

- **Diversifying Available Micro- and Nanoplastic Reference Particles: Model Studies with Polylactic Acid**, *Jessica Caldwell, Matilda Porro, Athanassia Athanassiou, Despina Fragouli*
- **Evaluation of potential risk of micro and nano plastics in agricultural soils through territorial analysis**, *Ali Hachem, Fabiana Convertino, Evelia Schettini, Giuliano Vox*
- **From Rivers to Sludge: Sorption and Fate of Micropollutants Bound to Microplastics during Anaerobic Digestion**, *Ivan Titov, Michaela Helusová, Jaroslav Semerád, Jana Boháčková, Hynek Beneš, Tomáš Cajthaml*
- **From soil to stream: Experimental evidence of microplastic bioaccumulation in amphibians via trophic transfer**, *Glorija Ćirković, Tanja Trakić, Filip Popović, Rastko Ajtić*
- **Oxidative DNA Damage and Tissue Inflammation Induced by PET and PP Microplastics and Their Additive Dibutyl Phthalate: Comparative In Vivo Assessment**, *Rosari Asty, Shafa Alayda Rachmah, Kezia Aurellia, Noverra Mardhatillah Nizardo, Budiawan*
- **Time-resolved colonization patterns of bacteria and fungi on polystyrene microplastics in floodplain soils**, *Rizwan Khaleel, Julian Wagenhofer, Markus Rolf, Yifan Lu, Hannes Laermanns, Alfons Weig, Frank Nitsche, Tillmann Lüders, Claus Bässler, Christian Laforsch, Martin G.J. Löder, Christina Bogner*

17:15–17:30 – Q&A session 3

19:00–23:00 – Gala Dinner, Sheraton hotel

Day 2 – Thursday, November 27, 2025

09:30–10:00 – Arrival and Gathering of Participants

10:00–10:30 – Plenary Lecture 3

Impact and Risk Assessment of Microplastics and Associated Additives

Speaker: **Prof. Dr. Jacob de Boer**, Faculty of Science, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam Editor-in-Chief Chemosphere
Moderator: Dr. Liam Morrison, University of Galway, Ireland

10:30–11:30 – Participant Presentations (Session 2)

- **A Decade of Research on Biofouled Microplastics: Alterations in the Fate and Transport of Particles**, *Müge Nigdeli, Başak Güven, Nurgül Çelik Balç*
- **Current situation of microplastic pollution in the black sea (Türkiye) whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*)**, *Gonca Alak, Mine Köktürk, Süleyman Özdemir, Aslı Çilingir Yeltekin, Fatma Betül Özgeriş, Serkan Yıldırım, Arzu Uçar, Veysel Parlak, Hünkar Avni Duyar, Emre Çağlak, Muhammed Atamanalp*
- **Detection and Spatial Pattern Analysis of Microplastics in Sewage Sludge– Treated Sandy Soils**, *Alexia Balla, Izabella Babcsányi, Karolina Solymos, György Sipos, Viktória Blanka-Végi*
- **Drinking Water Systems as a Source of Microplastics**, *Agnieszka Szuster-Janiaczyk, Małgorzata Komorowska-Kaufman, Alina Pruss, Beata Mądrecka Witkowska, Mirosław Szybowicz, Tomasz Runka, Ewelina Nowak, Karolina Olszewska*
- **First experimental evidence of fast leaching of small (1.7 µm) microplastics added to soil in field conditions**, *Nick Krekelbergh, Patria Novita Kusuwardan¹, Yin Liu, Steven Sleutel, Bogdan Parakhonsky, Richard Hoogenboom, André Skirtach, Stefaan De Neve*
- **Microplastic and microfibre pollution in unexplored caves**, *Valentina Balestra, Sonia Tassone*

11:30–11:45 – Q&A session 2

11:45–12:15 – Networking & Coffee Time

12:15–13:15 – Participant Presentations (Session 2)

- **Advantages of using Focal Plane Array Infra-red detectors in quantitative and qualitative analysis of Microplastics samples**, *Vladimir Kržaljčić*
- **Nanoplastics in Loch Ness and surrounding rivers and channels**, *Dušan Materić, Mike Peacock, Stuart Gibb*
- **Plastic Pollution in Polar Regions: Comparison of Case Studies from the Southern (Falklands) and Northern (Svalbard) Hemispheres**, *Agnieszka Dąbrowska, Weronika Łada, Dorota Wiktorowicz, Teresa Witkowska*
- **Quantification, characterisation and human health exposure of microplastic from indoor Environment**, *Nisarg Mehta, Barbara Kozielska*
- **Tire wear microplastics in motion: Environmental transport, toxicity, and fate**, *Gabriela Kalčíková, Barbara Klun, Ula Putar*
- **Towards a Framework for Emerging Contaminant Analysis for Marine Stranded Species in UAE**, *Lara Dronjak, Fatin Samara, Dina Tenji, Sofian Kanan, Sandra Knuteson, Fadi Yaghmour*

13:15–13:30 – Q&A session 2

13:30–14:15 – e-Poster Session

Moderator: Galina Ćurčić, Faculty of environmental protection, Educons University, Serbia

- **Artificial Intelligence –Satellite Synergy for Multi-Year Detection of Coastal Plastic Hotspots in Santo Domingo**, Shruti Venkata Chari, Gurusamy Kutralam-Muniasamy, Fermín Pérez-Guevara, Ricardo Cuenca Alvarez
- **Assessment of Microplastics Particles Composition in Raw and Treated Wastewater and River Water**, Małgorzata Komorowska-Kaufman, Katarzyna Jaszczyszyn, Edyta Kiedrzyńska
- **Avoidance behavior of Lumbricus terrestris (Oligochaeta: Lumbricidae) induced by polyethylene microplastics**, Ana Lazić, Milica Baloš, Aleksandra Petrović, Ivana Ivanović, Vojislava Bursić, Dejan Prvulović, Aleksandra Tubić
- **Biodegradable plastic mulch performance and degradation in real field conditions, case Slovenia**, Kristina Ugrinović, Karin Hriberšek, Mojca Bavcon Kralj
- **Degradation Dynamics of Conventional and Biodegradable Mulch Films in Agricultural Soils**, Skaistė Dreskinienė, Karolina Barčauskaitė, Monika Vilkiene
- **Early Plasticrust Formation and Rock-Plastic Interaction Risks in a Caribbean Coastal Zone (Santo Domingo)**, Gurusamy Kutralam-Muniasamy, V.C. Shruti, Fermín Pérez-Guevara, Ricardo Cuenca Alvarez
- **Ecological Footprint of Livestock Farming: Microplastic Contamination in Agricultural Soil and Water**, Suzana Knežević, Milena Milojević, Aleksandra Milošević
- **Harnessing Mushroom Waste for Green Synthesis of ZnO Nanoparticles: A Sustainable Route Toward Soil Microplastic Remediation**, Alok Ranjan Kerketta, Martin Šebesta
- **Identification of microplastic particles in water supply system of Rogoźno (Greater Poland Voivodeship, Poland)**, Agnieszka Szuster-Janiaczyk, Beata Mądrecka-Witkowska, Aleksandra Dajema, Karolina Olszewska
- **Impact of plastic mulching and road proximity on microplastic pollution in agricultural soils: Insights into weathering characteristics, elemental association, and ecological risk**, Jayant Karwadiya, Gopala Krishna Darbha, Sudhakar Srivastava, Alok Ranjan Kerketta, Saurabh Pathak
- **Microplastics assessment in Moroccan Mediterranean Mussels (Mytilus galloprovincialis and Callista chione)**, Mostapha Benomar, Yosra Ajbar, Soumaya Terresti, Chafiq Lahcen
- **Microplastics Contamination in Aquatic Ecosystems: Challenges in Extraction and Ecological Risk Assessment**, Marijana Nikolić, Aleksandra Tubić, Marija Jakovljević, Branko Kordić, Branislav Jović, Vladica Simić
- **Packaging as a Source of Microplastics in the Food Supply Chain: Evidence from Packaged Chicken Meat**, Tina Šaula, Živa Zidar, Sonja Smole Možina, Manca Kovač Viršek, Anja Klančnik
- **Variation in microplastic size ratios in swine and poultry feed mixtures**, Mislav Đidara, Marcela Šperanda, Brigita Popović, Darko Kerovec, Daria Petrović
- **Awareness and knowledge of farmers, winegrowers, and students on microplastics in agricultural soil**, Viktoria Stagl, Claudia Preininger
- **Communicating Microplastics Science through Education**, Katrin Školnik Škrabe, Lea Komerički Kotnik, Anja Bubik
- **InPlasTwin - Increasing expertise in micro- and nanoplastics analysis through twinning action**, Janja Vidmar, Nhu Phan, Milica Velimirović, Katrin Loeschner, Nanna B. Hartmann, André Marcel Bienfait, Dimitrios Savvas, Gordana Racić, Mladen Radišić

- **Microplastics in suspended sediments of the Danube River – preliminary results of the SUNDANSE project research**, Timofti Mihaela, Yevhen Nasiedkin, Ruslan Havryliuk, Madalina Calmuc, Vladyslav Balinsky
- **Methodological Challenges of Microplastic Sampling and Analysis in the Framework of the MicroDrink Project**, Branislav Petrović, Ana Selak, Gábor Bordós, Sebastian Koepfel, Lindinger Helga, Uta Wemhöner, Jadranka Šangulin, Mirna Švec, Ljiljana Vasić, Saša Milanović, Veljko Marinović, Jasmina Lukač Reberski, Ivana Boljat, Marek Polášek, Anja Torkar, Mihael Brenčić, Mohammad Alqadi, Gabriele Chiogna

14:15–15:15 – Lunch Break

15:15–15:45 – Plenary Lecture 4 - online

One tool to test it all: The harmonized analysis of microplastics by siMPLe

Speaker: **Dr. Sebastian Primpke**, Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Germany
Moderators: Dr. Ana Mendez, University of Galway, Ireland and Dr. Ljiljana Milošević, Educons University, Serbia

15:45–16:15 – Participant Presentations (session 4: Project Presentations and Networking)

- **An Innovative Sampling Solution for Microplastics in Small Shallow Rivers**, Anja Bubik, Aljoša Krajnc, Nataša Uranjek
- **An insider's view of Nature journals**, Raghavendra Palankar
- **ECO(RE)ACT-Pioneering ecosystem-based microplastics contamination reduction and climate change resilience in cross-border region**, Biljana Panin
- **Empowering Green Skills through EDU4PlastiCircular: Educational Resources and Awareness Campaigns**, Anca Draghici

16:15–16:30 – Networking & Coffee Time

16:30–17:30 – Participant Presentation (session 4: Project Presentations and Networking)

- **ICPLASTIC - ISO Compatible, Efficient and Reproducible Protocols/Equipment for Micro-Nanoplastic Detection through Machine-Learning**, Aleksandra Tubić
- **INSPIRE - Innovative Solutions for Plastic Free European Rivers**, Annamaria Vujanović
- **Investigation of the Content of Micropolymers in Sediment and Biota from a Marine Ecosystem**, Sevdalina H. Turmanova, Yancho H. Hristov, Dimitrina S. Kiryakova, Alexander N. Dimitrov, N. Todorov, Emilia D. Ivanova, Plamena V. Atanasova, Ganka R. Kolchakova, Antonia S. Ilieva, Elena Y. Mollova
- **Microplastics for Breakfast: Strengthening research collaboration and science to business to policy dialogue in the Western Balkan**, Andreja Palatinus
- **NOMAD: Nano-/Microplastic Mobility and Contaminant Co-Transport in Groundwater – A Multiscale Study with Finnish Perspective**, Muhammad Muniruzzaman, Evgenii Kortunov, Tuomo Soininen, Tenzin Tsering, Jarkko Akkanen, Arto Koistinen

17:30 – Conference Closing with a glass of local wine

Scientific Committee

- Dr. Sebastian Primpke, *Germany*
- Dr. Liam Morrison, *Ireland*
- Prof. Mira Pucarević, *Serbia*
- Prof. Nataša Stojić, *Serbia*
- Dr. Ljiljana Milošević, *Serbia*
- Prof. Agnieszka Dabrowska, *Poland*
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- Prof. Gabriela Kalčíková, *Slovenia*
- Prof. Aleksandra Tubić, *Serbia*
- Prof. Dunja Prokić, *Serbia*
- Dr. Ana Mendes, *Ireland*
- Dr. Fangzhu Wu, *Germany*
- Dr. Lara Dronjak, *UAE*

Organizing Committee

- Prof. Natasa Stojić, *Serbia*
- Dr. Ljiljana Milošević, *Serbia*
- Dr. Miloš Rajković, *Serbia*
- MSc. Suzana Kojić, *Serbia*
- Dr. Ana Mendes, *Ireland*
- Dr. Fangzhu Wu, *Germany*
- MSc. Galina Ćurčić, *Serbia*

SESSION 1: Analytical approaches for microplastics in organic-rich matrices

- Advances in microplastic extraction techniques for soil, compost, and sediments
- Standardisation and validation of collection, extraction, and analysis methods for organic-rich matrices
- Micro FTIR, Raman spectroscopy, and thermal analysis applications
- Emerging analytical technologies and future trends

MODERATOR:

Dr. Fangzhu Wu

Microbial Ecology-Microplastics Research Group Shelf Sea System Ecology Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Helgoland, Germany

Dr Fangzhu Wu did her PhD at the Alfred Wegener Institute in Germany, where she focused on the high-resolution lateral and vertical transport of microplastics in the water column and deep-sea sediments, investigating their distribution from the temperate waters of the southern North Sea to the Arctic Barents Sea. Through this work, she developed strong expertise in field sampling, laboratory analysis, and data interpretation.

Previously, she worked on microplastic pollution in different environmental matrices in an aquacultural bay in China at the Second Institute of Oceanography, MNR, gaining experience in microplastic extraction, identification, and ecotoxicological assessments of commercial fish species.

She is currently a postdoctoral researcher in the GREENLand project, where she applies her expertise to studying microplastics in agricultural soils while contributing to knowledge transfer, education, and international collaboration.

KEYNOTE SPEAKER:
Prof. Christian Laforsch

Full Professor and Head of the Chair: Animal Ecology I, University of Bayreuth, Faculty of Biology, Chemistry, and Earth Sciences

Prof. Dr Christian Laforsch is a Full Professor at the University of Bayreuth, where he leads the Chair of Animal Ecology I within the Faculty of Biology, Chemistry, and Earth Sciences. He earned his Diploma in Biology from LMU Munich in 1999 and completed his PhD in Evolutionary Ecology in 2003. His research focuses on microplastic pollution, ecological interactions, and evolutionary adaptations.

Laforsch has held various academic positions, including Assistant Professor at LMU Munich and Director of the Limnological Field Station Seon. He has played a key role in several major research initiatives, such as the DFG Collaborative Research Centre on Microplastics and the Horizon2020 project LimnoPlast. Recognized for his contributions, he has received multiple awards, including the 2023 Clarivate Highly Cited Researcher distinction.

In addition to his research, Laforsch serves as an editorial board member for the journal *Microplastics and Nanoplastics* and leads the PhD program *Interdisciplinary Microplastic Sciences (InterMicro)*. His work continues to advance the understanding of microplastic pollution and its environmental impacts.

Microplastics in the environment

Prof. Dr. Christian Laforsch

The ubiquitous contamination of the environment with microplastics (MP) and the associated potential risks perpetually attracts a great deal of public, political, economic and scientific attention. However, the problem is very complex, as MP represents a very heterogeneous group of particles with a wide range of chemical and physical properties, which also constantly change due to various environmental impacts and the resulting aging processes. This can lead to altered environmental behavior as well as to different biological effects. However, due to the myriad combinations of properties that MP exhibit in the environment, the study of aging, environmental behavior and effects is a tremendous challenge and requires an interdisciplinary approach that bridges traditional academic disciplinary boundaries. The CRC initiative on microplastics (SFB1357) aims therefore to gain a fundamental understanding of the processes and mechanisms that 1) condition biological effects of MP in limnetic and terrestrial ecosystems as a function of the physical and chemical properties of the particles, 2) influence the migration behavior of MP particles and 3) cause the formation of MP starting from macroscopic plastics, based on model systems for plastics, organisms, and environmental compartments. These findings provide a scientifically sound basis for assessing the environmental risks of MP, as well as for developing environmentally friendly plastics and processes to prevent the emission of MP into the environment. The presentation will highlight the state of the art in this young field of research, identify the key knowledge gaps, present the findings of the CRC, and show how they will contribute to solving this global issue.

Confocal Raman spectroscopy for nanoplastic detection at microgram to nanogram concentrations in complex media

Giulia Biagi¹, Aref Enayati², Barbara Rothen-Rutishauser³, Patricia Taladriz-Blanco^{3,4}, Alke Petri-Fink^{1,3}

¹Department of Chemistry, University of Fribourg, Chemin du Musée 9, 1700 Fribourg, Switzerland

²Institute of Applied Mathematics and Physics, Zurich University of Applied Sciences, Winterthur, Switzerland

³Adolphe Merkle Institute, University of Fribourg, Chemin des Verdiers 4, 1700 Fribourg, Switzerland

⁴International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory (INL), Water Quality Group, Av. Mestre José Veiga s/n, 4715-330 Braga, Portugal

giulia.biagi@unifr.ch

Background & Objectives: Nanoplastics (NPLs) are raising significant concerns within the scientific community due to their ubiquitous presence in environmental and biological systems. However, detecting NPLs remains challenging because of their nanoscale dimensions, low signal intensity, and strong matrix effects. Although advanced techniques such as Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS) have improved sensitivity, they typically require enhancement substrates and extensive sample preparation [1], limiting their applicability in real-world environments.

Methods: In this study, we investigate whether conventional confocal Raman spectroscopy can be optimized to detect NPLs at ngmL⁻¹ concentrations in complex media. We developed an analytical approach based on Raman detection to enhance sensitivity and simplify the detection process. As a first step, we tested our method by using 100 nm polystyrene beads in supplemented cell culture medium as a model system, due to its compositional similarity to physiological fluids, with ultrapure water as a control.

Conclusions: Our system successfully detected polystyrene NPLs down to 1 µgmL⁻¹ in cell culture medium (0.001 µgmL⁻¹ in ultrapure water) without requiring any pre-concentration or purification steps [2]. The results highlight the promising potential of Raman-based detection of NPLs in increasingly complex media and pave the way for future applications in real-world biological settings.

Acknowledgments: The authors would like to thank the Adolphe Merkle Foundation and the University of Fribourg for providing research funding.

[1] Cai, J. et al. (2025) "Quantitative detection of multiscale nanoplastics in biofluids using polyethyleneimine-modified Fe₃O₄ and gold-silver nanostars for SERS signal amplification and stabilization", *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, Volume 13, Issue 4, 117372, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2025.117372>.

[2] Caldwell, J. et al. (2024) "Detection of submicron- and nanoplastics spiked in environmental fresh- and saltwater with Raman spectroscopy", *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, Volume 203, 116468, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2024.116468>.

Nanoplastics, Raman spectroscopy, Complex environments

Development of a protocol for extracting nanoplastics from agricultural soils using metal-doped nanoplastics

Pia Leban^{1,2}, Quynh Nhu Phan Le³, Milica Velimirovic³, Kristof Tirez³, Janja Vidmar^{1,2}

¹Department of Environmental Sciences, Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

²Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School, Ljubljana, Slovenia

³Laboratory for inorganic and organic analysis, Flemish Institute for Technological Research, Mol, Belgium

nhu.phan@vito.be

Background & Objectives: Nanoplastics (NPs) have become emerging pollutants in agricultural soils due to the extensive use of plastics in farming. Their nanoscale size and strong interactions with soil make extraction and quantification challenging. Traditional microplastics extraction methods, like density separation, often ineffectively recover NPs due to their aggregation and adsorption onto soil particles. The lack of standardized NPs extraction protocols and low efficiency further complicate accurate assessment of NPs contamination in soil. The use of metal-doped NPs as tracers offers a promising strategy for method development, enabling sensitive detection and quantitative assessment of extraction recovery via single-particle inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (spICP-MS).

Methods: Here, we developed an extraction protocol for NPs from soil using 198 nm europium-doped polystyrene nanoparticles (PS-Eu NPs). Two g of soils (loamy sand, clay loam and silt clay) were spiked with 200 µg PS-Eu NPs (corresponding to 4.6×10¹⁰ particles). Extraction was performed with 2.5 mM tetrasodium pyrophosphate, and the supernatant obtained after shaking, settling and centrifugation was subjected to organic matter digestion by adding 30% H₂O₂. Aliquots were collected at different stages, diluted and analysed using spICP-MS.

Results: Preliminary results indicate that soil type influenced PS-Eu NPs extraction recoveries. Loamy sand exhibited the highest recoveries (particle number concentration: 73-80%, mass concentration: 63-72%), followed by clay loam (particle number concentration: 56-60%, mass concentration: 52-60%) and silt clay (particle number concentration: 49-50%, mass concentration: 46-49%). spICP-MS analysis indicated that the Eu mass per particle remained constant across samples, suggesting no significant leaching or aggregation of the metal tracer. Therefore, we infer that the extraction procedure likely did not alter particle integrity.

Conclusions: Future work will apply this protocol to various NPs polymer types and sizes, with subsequent identification and quantification performed using pyrolysis-GC-MS. This approach will contribute to the development of a more comprehensive and standardized methodology for assessing NPs contamination in soils

Acknowledgements: This work was funded by the European Union project InPlasTwin, grant agreement No. 101160289.

Metal-doped nanoplastics, Extraction, Agricultural soil, spICP-MS

Efficiency of Fenton reaction for the clean-up of groundwater and surface water matrices for various microplastic analysis methods

Lina Büngener¹, Guillaume Bucher¹, Dora Mehn¹, Douglas Gilliland¹

¹European Commission Joint Research Centre, Nanobiotechnology Laboratory (Technologies for Health Unit), Ispra, Italy

lina.buengener@ec.europa.eu

Background & Objectives: The Fenton reaction has been established as a sample clean-up step for the removal of natural organic matter from environmental samples for microplastic (MP) analysis. The work presented here validates the efficiency of this method for various environmental water sample matrices, in regard to the subsequent applicability of different MP analysis methods.

Methods: In line with current regulatory activities within the EU, samples of groundwater and surface water were tested. 50–500 mL of raw sample were filtered by 20 µm, and the retained particles analyzed for total organic carbon (TOC) content. The same sample volume was filtered and subjected to Fenton reaction, and the final TOC content measured and compared to the raw sample to a) quantify the efficiency of the natural organic matter removal and b) get a mass-based estimate of the maximum total plastic content in the sample, following the assumption that all organic carbon remaining in the sample after Fenton reaction can be attributed to plastic material.

Further, 1 L of sample was filtered and fractionated (>100 µm and 20–100 µm), subjected to Fenton reaction and ZnCl₂ solution density separation, and filtered onto an Anodisc filter. Samples were first analyzed by Raman micro-spectroscopy with automated spectra interpretation, and subsequently stained with Nile Red, imaged under a fluorescence microscope, and particle image analysis conducted (ImageJ). The resulting number-based MP concentrations were compared and, based on the particles' size and polymer type distribution obtained from Raman analysis, a mass-based MP concentration was calculated.

Conclusions: Fenton reaction efficiently reduced the organic matter content for all sample matrix tested. Mineral- rather than organic particles appeared to obstruct Raman analysis in groundwater samples after Fenton reaction. Raman and TOC analysis produced comparable mass-based MP concentration estimates for groundwater samples after Fenton reaction.

Fenton reaction, Micro-spectroscopy, Analytical method comparison, Groundwater, Surface water

Exploring analytical methodologies for monitoring microplastics in media relevant to the urban wastewater treatment Directive (EU) 2024/3019

Guillaume Bucher¹, Lina Büngener¹, Otmar Geiss¹, Dora Mehn¹, Douglas Gilliland¹

¹European Commission, Joint Research Centre, Nanobiotechnology Laboratory (Technologies for Health Unit), Ispra, Italy

guillaume.bucher@ec.europa.eu

Background & Objectives: Within the framework of Directive (EU) 2024/3019 concerning urban wastewater treatment (UWWTD), the European Commission - Joint Research Centre (EC-JRC) is evaluating, developing and testing candidate methodologies for measuring microplastics (MPs) in wastewater treatment plant influent, effluent and sewage sludge. Although MP concentrations in untreated influent and sludge are expected to be significantly higher than in most other environmental matrices, detecting and quantifying MPs in these organic-rich matrices remains very challenging.

Methods: This study investigates the combination of thorough sample treatment – including multiple filtration, digestion and density separation steps – with analytical methods including spectro-microscopic and thermo-analytical techniques, for monitoring microplastics in media relevant to the UWWTD. In parallel, the potential of number-based fluorescence microscopy (FluoMic) and mass-based total organic carbon (TOC) analysis as standalone monitoring techniques or pre-screening techniques in a tiered approach is being investigated.

Conclusions: The key findings of this study will be presented and discussed. These include the absolute necessity of sample treatment to eliminate unwanted organic matter, and how the combination of Fenton oxidation and density separation is efficient for this purpose. Other outcomes include the ability of TOC to detect small quantities of organic carbon originating from polymer-based particles, down to a single 250 µm polystyrene particle; and finally, the comparability of results obtained using various analytical techniques, including µRaman, Py-GC/MS, TOC and FluoMic, when analyzing compost spiked with well-characterized MPs as a proxy for organic-rich wastewater media.

UWWTD, Microplastic, Monitoring, Analytical methodologies, Wastewater and sludge

Microplastics in soil: Are smaller particles lost during the extraction process?

Diana Nantege¹, Sarmite Kernchen¹, Martin G. J. Löder¹, Christian Laforsch¹

¹Animal Ecology I and BayCEER, University of Bayreuth, Bayreuth, Germany

Diana.Nantege@uni-bayreuth.de

Background & Objectives: Soil pollution with microplastics (MPs) presents serious challenges to both environmental and human health, necessitating comprehensive risk assessments and implementation of effective protective measures. A critical first step in this process is the accurate quantification of MPs in soil, as it forms the basis for understanding exposure levels and potential risks. However, the extraction of MPs from soil is a complex, multi-step procedure involving density separation, digestion, and filtration, each of which carries the risk of particle loss or contamination. Therefore, validation of analytical methods, particularly through recovery rate assessments, is essential to ensure reliable and reproducible results.

Methods: Recovery studies typically involve spiking soil samples with known quantities of reference MPs. However, most existing studies focus on relatively large particles (>100 µm), often neglecting the smaller size fractions that are more environmentally prevalent and potentially more hazardous. Smaller MPs pose greater analytical challenges due to their unique physicochemical properties, such as low mass, high surface area, and a strong tendency to adhere to surfaces or pass through filter pores. These factors make them particularly prone to loss during sampling and processing, leading to systematic underestimation of total MP loads. This size-related bias can significantly distort pollution assessments and impede the development of effective remediation strategies. To address this gap, the present study investigated the recovery rates of MPs down to 10 µm, using a slightly modified protocol by Möller et al. (2022). We also examined which steps in the extraction process contributed most to particle loss.

Conclusions: Our findings revealed a significant decline in recovery with decreasing particle size. Major losses occurred during density separation, as well as due to particle lodging in filters, splashing, and adhesion to equipment. These results highlight the critical need for targeted recovery tests for smaller MPs to support accurate analysis and risk evaluation.

[1] Möller, N.J. et al. (2022) 'Tackling the Challenge of Extracting Microplastics from Soils: A Protocol to Purify Soil Samples for Spectroscopic Analysis', *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, Volume 41, Issue 4, p. 844-857. <https://doi.org/10.1002/etc.5024>

Microplastics, Soil, Extraction, Losses, Recovery Rates

Microplastics in Wastewater Sludge: A Novel Quantification Method developed by Captoplastic S.L.

Gonzalo Vega Marcilla¹, Raquel Parra Sanchez¹, Amparo Fernández Benito¹, Belén Carboneras Contreras¹

¹Captoplastic, S.L, Madrid, Spain

belen.carboneras@captoplastic.com

Background & Objectives: Wastewater constitutes one of the primary vectors for microplastic (MP) pollution, positioning wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) as the final barrier preventing the release of these contaminants into the environment. Although WWTPs achieve a significant reduction in MP content (>90%) in water line [1], the lack of dedicated removal technologies results in MPs being retained in sewage sludge. This presents an environmental risk, particularly in agricultural contexts, where sewage sludge is frequently applied as fertilizer.

Currently, no standardized methods exist for quantifying microplastics in organic rich matrices, such as sewage sludge, which complicates comparisons with other common pollutants, typically expressed by mass concentration (mg·L⁻¹). To address this limitation, Captoplastic S.L. has developed an analytical procedure for the quantification of MPs concentration in milligrams per gram of dry sludge (mg·gds⁻¹). This method uses a captor material to interact with MPs and form magnetic aggregates, which can then be separated using an external magnetic field. A subsequent intensified oxidation step is applied to degrade non-plastic organic matter, facilitating accurate MP quantification and allowing its further identification via FTIR.

Methods: The protocol involves drying the sludge at 85 °C to constant weight, followed by a gentle grinding and sieving (<500 µm). Subsequently, 100 mg of dry sludge are suspended in 100 mL of distilled water, mixed with 1 g of collector, and stirred vigorously. After magnetic separation and filtration, the collected aggregates undergo oxidation and final filtration.

Samples from an urban WWTP revealed concentrations of 2.9 mg·gds⁻¹, aligning with the limited available literature [2]. Validation tests using increased 200 and 400 mg, reaching 2.7 and 2.6 mg·gds⁻¹ respectively. Recovery experiments with PE, PES, and PET [1] reported an average recovery rate of 85.2%.

Conclusions: This method enables robust, reproducible, and cost-effective quantification of microplastics WWTP sludge, offering valuable insights into potential environmental discharges.

[1] Miino, M. et al. (2024) 'Microplastics removal in wastewater treatment plants: A review of the different approaches to limit their release in the environment', *Science of the Total Environment*, 930, 172675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.172675>

[2] Hansen, A. (2017) "Microplastic in Danish wastewater: Sources, occurrences and fate" <https://www2.mst.dk/udgiv/publications/2017/03/978-87-93529-44-1.pdf>

Sludge, Quantification, Microplastics, Organic-rich matrices, WWTP

Multitechnique analysis of eco-corona formation on airborne polyethylene terephthalate nanoplastics interacting with bee pollen

Anna Placci¹, Marta Fadda², Irene Coralli³, Junjie Wang¹, Andrea Zattoni^{1,4}, Anna Luisa Costa⁵, Raquel Portela⁶, Andrea Mario Giovannozzi², Andrea Mario Rossi², Daniele Fabbri³, Dora Melucci¹, Stefano Giordani¹, Barbara Roda^{1,4}, Pierluigi Reschiglian^{1,4}, Simona Ortelli⁵, Alessio Sacco², Valentina Marassi^{1,4}

¹Department of Chemistry "G. Ciamician", University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

²Quantum Metrology and Nanotechnology Department, National Institute of Metrological Research, Torino, Italy

³Department of Chemistry "G. Ciamician", Technopole of Rimini, University of Bologna, Rimini, Italy.

⁴ByFlow S.R.L., Via Dell'Arcoveggio 74, 40129 Bologna, Italy

⁵National Research Council of Italy - Institute of Science, Technology and Sustainability for Ceramics, Faenza, Italy

⁶CSIC - Instituto de Catalisis y Petroleoquimica (ICP), Madrid, Spain

a.sacco@inrim.it

Background & Objectives: The ever-growing, pervasive presence of nanoplastics and small microplastics in the environment spurs the necessity for uncomplicated and reliable methods for their detection, but also for the study of their interactions with biological entities and biomolecules. [1] In this study, the formation of eco-coronas on polyethylene terephthalate nanoparticles (NanoPET) in the presence of multifloral bee pollen has been detected and thoroughly investigated.

Methods: In line with current regulatory activities within the EU, samples of groundwater and surface water were tested. 50–500 mL of raw sample were filtered by 20 µm, and the retained particles analyzed for total organic carbon (TOC) content. The same sample volume was filtered and subjected to Fenton reaction, and the final TOC content measured and compared to the raw sample to a) quantify the efficiency of the natural organic matter removal and b) get a mass-based estimate of the maximum total plastic content in the sample, following the assumption that all organic carbon remaining in the sample after Fenton reaction can be attributed to plastic material.

Further, 1 L of sample was filtered and fractionated (>100 µm and 20–100 µm), subjected to Fenton reaction and ZnCl₂ solution density separation, and filtered onto an Anodisc filter. Samples were first analyzed by Raman micro-spectroscopy with automated spectra interpretation, and subsequently stained with Nile Red, imaged under a fluorescence microscope, and particle image analysis conducted (ImageJ). The resulting number-based MP concentrations were compared and, based on the particles' size and polymer type distribution obtained from Raman analysis, a mass-based MP concentration was calculated.

Conclusions: Fenton reaction efficiently reduced the organic matter content for all sample matrix tested. Mineral- rather than organic particles appeared to obstruct Raman analysis in groundwater samples after Fenton reaction. Raman and TOC analysis produced comparable mass-based MP concentration estimates for groundwater samples after Fenton reaction.

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[1] S. Liu, M. et al., Sci. Total Environ., 2022, 836, 155703.

[2] A. Placci et al., RSC Adv., 2025, 15, 30849-30864.

Eco-corona, Pollen, AF4, Raman, DEP, FESEM, Py-GC-MS

Synthetic Hydrophilic Polymers - An Emerging Class of Polymers in Soil

Christian Plicht¹, Zacharias Steinmetz¹

¹RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau, Kaiserslautern, Germany

christian.plicht@rptu.de

Background & Objectives: Current plastic research focuses on particulate and water-insoluble polymers, such as polyethylene or polystyrene. In comparison, synthetic hydrophilic polymers, a class of anthropogenic materials with an annual global production of over 35 Mt, has received little scientific attention. Synthetic hydrophilic polymers are for instance used for the controlled release of agrochemicals as well as for seed coating. Although synthetic hydrophilic polymers are intentionally added in soil, their occurrence, behavior and fate are often unknown.

Methods: The aim of this study was to fill this knowledge gap and, as a first step, to develop a method capable of identifying and quantifying synthetic hydrophilic polymers in different soils. We focused on the most common synthetic hydrophilic polymers, polyacrylic acid (PAA), polyethylene glycol (PEG), polyvinyl alcohol (PVOH) and polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), and agricultural model soils. Extraction of polymers was performed using an alkaline solution (pH = 11) and concentrated sodium pyrophosphate solution (pH = 9). Polymer solutions were measured using pyrolysis gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS). PEG, PVOH and PVP were analyzed simultaneously with multiple peaks for each polymer showing high linearity ($R^2 > 0.992$) between 1 and 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ ($n = 13$). Limits of detection (LOD) were between 3 and 12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and limits of quantification (LOQ) between 48 and 76 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Pyrolysis of PAA and PVOH partly resulted in similar pyrolysis products, challenging the simultaneous quantification of both polymers. 3-Methyl-2-cyclohexenone was the only PAA peak that did not interfere with PVOH peaks and an $R^2 > 0.990$. The LOD and LOQ of 3-Methyl-2-cyclohexenone were 38 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 108 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, respectively. Intra-day repeatability was the best for PEG with a residual standard deviation (RSD) of 5.2 % and PVP with 7.6 %. PVOH and PAA were less accurate at 12.7 % and 16.3 % RSD.

Conclusions: Py-GC/MS is a promising tool to identify and quantify different synthetic hydrophilic polymers. However, further experiments with different methods are needed to understand the behavior of synthetic hydrophilic polymers in soil. To characterize synthetic hydrophilic polymers in soil, size-exclusion chromatography could be used to measure the molecular weight. This could provide information on polymer (bio-)degradation in soil.

Synthetic Hydrophilic Polymers, Py-GC/MS, Agricultural soils

Variation in microplastic size ratios in swine and poultry feed mixtures

Mislav Đidara¹, Marcela Šperanda¹, Brigita Popović¹, Darko Kerovec¹, Daria Petrović¹

¹Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences Osijek, Vladimira Preloga 1, 31000 Osijek, Croatia

mdidara@fazos.hr

Background & Objectives: Microplastics are increasingly recognized as contaminants of concern in animal production systems due to their negative effects on digestive physiology, potential for reabsorption, and long-term consequences for animal health. Their presence in feed constitutes a direct exposure route for livestock and poultry, raising concerns about bioaccumulation and associated health risks. In this study, we analyzed microplastic content in swine ($n=6$) and poultry ($n=6$) feed using a LUMOS II FTIR microscope with Purency software. While the LUMOS II system enables reliable polymer identification, its precision decreases substantially for particles below 20 μm , limiting accurate detection of the smallest microplastics.

Methods: We compared the ratio of small particles (1 pixel $\approx 10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ and up to 3 pixels) to larger particles across feed types using Pearson's Chi-square test of independence, thereby estimating the fraction of microplastics potentially overlooked if small particles were excluded from counts. Feed samples were digested with 10% KOH at 60 °C for 24 h, followed by repeated Fenton oxidation, with both steps accompanied by filtration and rinsing to isolate microplastics.

Results: Our results revealed significant differences in size distributions between swine and poultry feed. Larger particles accounted for 77.3% of the total in swine feed compared to 70.1% in poultry feed. When particles up to 3 pixels were included in the "small" category, larger particle ratios were 52.3% and 45.4%, respectively. Chi-square tests confirmed these differences as statistically significant ($\chi^2(1) = 13.72$, $p < 0.001$ for 1-pixel; $\chi^2(1) = 9.28$, $p = 0.0023$ for ≤ 3 pixels).

Conclusions: These findings demonstrate that excluding the smallest size fraction would systematically bias results, leading to underestimation of microplastic contamination, particularly in poultry feed. The study underscores the importance of methodological refinement for reliable quantification of microplastics and highlights the need to consider particle size distribution when evaluating exposure risks in animal health.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the IPA Croatia-Serbia Project ECO(RE)ACT - Pioneering ecosystem-based microplastics contamination reduction and climate change resilience in cross-border region

Microplastics, Animal feed, Particle size distribution, FTIR microscopy

What controls the quality of microplastic analysis? Insights from an interlaboratory study using MicroPRefs reference materials

Svetlana Pakhomova¹, Vilde Kloster Snekkevik¹, Bert van Bavel¹

¹Norwegian Institute for Water Research, Oslo, Norway

svp@niva.no

Background & Objectives: The analysis of small microplastics (<300 µm) remains a major challenge due to common problems encountered at each step of the analytical process. During sampling, these particles are easily lost or cross-contaminated due to their small size and ubiquity in air and sampling equipment. In the laboratory, extraction and purification from complex environmental matrices such as sediments or biological tissues are challenging because their low mass and density make separation by density flotation ineffective, and their small size increases the risk of incomplete organic matter degradation or co-extraction of interfering substances. Finally, the identification and quantification step is particularly problematic. While techniques such as micro-FTIR and Raman microscopy are effective, their limited spatial resolution makes it difficult to analyse particles close to the diffraction limit, analysis times become prohibitively long for routine counting, and automated software is often unable to reliably distinguish these small, often weathered plastic particles from natural particles, resulting in high uncertainty and potential underestimation or overestimation of environmental concentrations.

Methods: The accuracy of current microplastic detection methods was assessed through an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) conducted in 2024 by the NORMAN network, in collaboration with ISO Technical Group 147/SC2/JWG1 and the PlasticTrace project, with the participation of 32 laboratories. Two types of reference materials (RMs) in the form of pressed soda tablets (Chiron MicroPRefs) were used, each containing three polymers with approximate size ranges between 50–300 µm: Type A (polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyethylene (PE), and polystyrene (PS)) and Type B (polypropylene (PP), polycarbonate (PC), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC)). Laboratories applied either the ISO/NP 16094-2 MP draft standard method or established in-house protocols.

Conclusions: Despite the relatively limited number of sample preparation steps (e.g., filtration only), the results revealed considerable variability in error rates across laboratories, underscoring the importance of identifying potential error sources during filtration and software parameterisation. In this study, particular attention is given to the final analytical stage, focusing on the challenges associated with the use of different software tools for automated MP identification in samples analysed by IR imaging.

ILC, Microplastic reference materials, Microplastic identification

Aligned method for microplastic extraction from fresh and decomposed forest litter

Collin J. Weber¹, Ole Heberer¹, Moritz Bigalke¹

¹Department of Soil Mineralogy and Soil Chemistry, Institute of Applied Geosciences, Technical University Darmstadt, Germany

weber@geo.tu-darmstadt.de

Background & Objectives: Forests and their soils could be a hidden hub for microplastic accumulation within global plastic cycles. Forest soils and especially their organic matrices, build up from fresh or decomposed tree leaf litter, are a particular challenge for microplastic extraction. This contribution aims to present a possible approach for a combined extraction method for organic and mineral soil horizons in forests and discuss further development potential.

Methods: The aligned extraction protocol consists of a full chemical extraction aiming for a later microplastic analysis via chemical imaging by FPA-µFTIR for particles >20 µm. In contrast to a separation by density often applied to mineral soils, a detachment of microplastics from leaf surfaces was preferred before further sample purification. We used 0.1M tetrasodium pyrophosphate (Na₄P₂O₇) solution as a dispersing agent to allow the detachment of microplastics from leaf surfaces including sonification, shaking and washing of leaf litter. Further sample purification of also detached organic matter includes binary-solvent-extraction with ethanol and water, surface degradation of organic matter by sodium-urea-thiourea treatment and controlled Fenton reaction. Blank and recovery tests were performed with incubated leaf litter using cryo-milled PE film and PP fibre microplastic spikes.

Results: Recovery tests showed a variable recovery with 95±11.1% in fresh litter and 60±5.3% to 90±50% in decomposed litter horizons for PE films. For PE fibre spikes the recovery was comparatively low with only 30–40% due to fibre loss during filtration steps with 10 µm stainless-steel filters. During a further method alignment on organic-rich mineral forest matrices, recoveries of 86 ± 12% were found for PE film spikes.

Conclusions: The aligned method allows the particle-based quantification of microplastics in specific sample matrices of forest leaf litter and decomposed litter. Further alignments could increase the recovery of this approach or allow a reduction of its complexity.

Microplastic extraction, Leaf litter, Litter decomposition, Forest soil, Chemical imaging

Analysis of microplastics in different forest soil matrices

Ole Heberer¹, Collin J. Weber¹

¹Department of Soil Mineralogy and Soil Chemistry, Institute of Applied Geosciences, Technical University Darmstadt, Germany

ole.heberer@stud.tu-darmstadt.de

Background & Objectives: To date, there are only few studies considering the microplastic occurrence and storage in forests and their soils. Microplastic accumulation in forest soil might depend on the tree species and on the overall forest structure along with leaf litter decomposition based on soil properties.

The presented research aims to provide further insights into i) the effects of different forest structures on microplastic accumulation and ii) the effects of different soil structures on the vertical distribution of microplastic in forest soils.

Methods: Samples of mineral and organic soil horizons were taken from eight locations across the federal state of Hesse (Germany) which differ in forest and soil characteristics. Microplastic extraction was conducted using an aligned method for forest soil matrices by Weber and Bigalke (2025) [1], including combined methods for organic and mineral soil samples. Organic horizon pretreatment and extraction consist of microplastic detachment and a binary solvent extraction. Mineral horizons undergo a sodium bromide density separation. Sample purification for both matrices is performed by pretreatment with a sodium-urea-thiourea solution. A temperature-controlled Fenton reaction is used for oxidation, followed by further sample purification. Chemical imaging is conducted via FPA- μ FTIR with size detection limit of 22 μ m.

Results: Complete results from 40 samples are expected by the time of the conference. In addition to particle-based microplastic concentrations and particle properties, such as size, shape and polymeric composition, initial statistical analyses on the influence of forest and soil structure will be available.

Conclusions: Forests might play a crucial but not well understood role in the biogeochemical plastic cycle. The results of this study can therefore be used to gain new insights into the global fate of microplastics. Furthermore, conclusions can be drawn on which forest types might be most vulnerable to microplastic pollution.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Federal Agency for Nature Conservation, Environment and Geology of the Hessian federal state, Germany.

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Microplastic Extraction, Leaf litter, Litter decomposition, Forest soil, Chemical imaging

Detection and Isolation of Microplastics from Chicken Feces

Anja Klančnik¹, Živa Zidar¹, Krištof Kepić¹, Majda Golob², Manca Kovač Viršek³

¹ University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Ljubljana, Slovenia

² University of Ljubljana, Veterinary Faculty, Ljubljana, Slovenia

³ National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana, Slovenia

anja.klancnik@bf.uni-lj.si

Background & Objectives: Microplastics (MP), synthetic polymer particles smaller than 5 mm, are widespread in the environment and can enter the food chain through water, soil, and feed, potentially affecting animal and human health [1]. Poultry may be exposed to MP via feed and drinking water, leading to excretion in feces. The objective of this study was to develop and validate a reliable method for isolating and identifying microplastics from chicken feces and to determine their occurrence on Slovenian poultry farms.

Methods: Poultry ceca samples (n = 140) were collected from 14 farms. Microplastics were isolated using chemical digestion with 10% KOH (ratio 1:5, 48 h, 37 °C, 80–100 rpm), followed by vacuum filtration through 60 μ m nylon filters. To minimize contamination, all procedures were performed using glassware rinsed with MilliQ water under laminar flow conditions, and laboratory personnel wore cotton clothing and nitrile gloves. Visual identification of particles was performed under a stereomicroscope, and chemical composition was confirmed using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR).

Results: A total of 57 microplastic particles were isolated from chicken feces. The identified polymers included polypropylene as the most frequent, followed by polyethylene and other types. The particles varied in shape, color, and transparency, indicating multiple potential sources of contamination.

Conclusions: This study confirms the presence of microplastics in chicken feces and provides a validated protocol for their isolation and characterization. The findings suggest that poultry can serve as bioindicators of environmental microplastic contamination, emphasizing the need for further monitoring and mitigation strategies in the food production chain.

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Digestion, Microplastic, Fish, Intestine, ATR-FTIR

Fenton oxidation of municipal wastewater for microplastic analysis

Daphne Argyropoulou¹, Andriani Galani¹, Constantinos Noutsopoulos¹, Daniel Mamais¹, Simos Malamis¹

¹ National Technical University of Athens, School of Civil Engineering, Athens, Greece

d_argyropoulou@mail.ntua.gr

Background & Objectives: Micro-spectroscopic techniques, such as μ Raman, have recently been standardized for analyzing microplastics in clean water samples [1]. However, sample preparation methods for complex matrices have yet to be standardized, and efficient pre-treatment remains crucial for achieving reliable spectral information and shorter analysis times [2], [3]. The present study investigates the removal of organic matter (OM) from municipal wastewater with Fenton's reagent, for subsequent microplastic analysis.

Methods: Influent wastewater (WW_{in}) after pre-treatment was sampled from Psyttaleia Wastewater Treatment Plant, Greece, and suspended solids were collected with stainless-steel sieves of 20 μ m mesh size. The sieves were submerged in 30% H_2O_2 with solid $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ catalyst to digest OM and the digestion efficiency was determined gravimetrically. The chemical doses were optimized by studying the effectiveness of (i) the peroxide to suspended solids ratio, within a range of 0,4–2,4, and (ii) the ferrous catalyst dose between 1,6–3,7. WW_{in} samples prepared with digestion at the optimal conditions, followed by density separation with a $ZnCl_2$ solution and an acidification step, were analyzed with μ Raman spectroscopy to further assess the method.

Results: The results show that 1,2 and 3 ensured 93,6% \pm 1,4% (n=7) mass removal from the WW_{in} stream (**Fig. 1**). Digestion is an exothermic reaction that was usually complete within approximately 20 minutes. Significantly lower mass removal was observed with a 35% H_2O_2 solution. A possible reason may be the presence of stabilizers, which could affect hydroxyl radical formation delaying oxidation in the given 30-minute reaction time, and/ or interact with the catalyst species (**Fig. 1.i**).

Fig. 1. Optimization of Fenton's reagent for municipal WW_{in} . OM removal vs. (i) H_2O_2 dose, (ii) catalyst dose.

Conclusions: Through this study, Fenton is confirmed as a fast and dependable method for OM removal and a simple way to estimate chemical dosing for Fenton oxidation is suggested, depending on the suspended solids concentration of municipal wastewater.

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Microplastic extraction, Fenton, Sample treatment, Wastewater, μ Raman

Isolation and detection of large microplastics from fish intestines

Tomislav Kačarević¹, Sandra Jakšić¹, Milica Živkov Baloš¹, Jelena Petrović¹, Radomir Ratajac¹

¹ Scientific Veterinary Institute "Novi Sad", Novi Sad, Serbia

tomislav.k@niv.ns.ac.rs

Background & Objectives: Microplastic particles in surface waters pose a significant ecological risk to aquatic ecosystems. These particles accumulate in fish through feeding, leading to tissue damage, metabolic disturbances, and reduced reproductive capacity [1]. This study aimed to assess the efficiency of isolating large microplastics from fish intestines and to evaluate the effect of digestion on three common polymer types. Additionally, the method was applied to detect microplastics in fish intestines from the Danube–Tisa–Danube Canal using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy.

Methods: Intestinal samples of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) were used for spike testing and recovery validation. Two northern pike (*Esox lucius*) and seven prussian carp (*Carassius gibelio*) samples from the Canal were analyzed. Samples were digested with 10% KOH for 24 hours at 60 °C, and residues were filtered using glass-fiber filters [2]. Suspected particles were visually selected under a magnifying glass, and their identification was performed by ATR-FTIR spectroscopy using a reference library.

Results: The digestion method effectively decomposed the organic material in trout intestines. In spiked trout samples containing 10 pieces (1–5 mm) of polyethylene, polypropylene, and polyethylene terephthalate, a 100% recovery rate was achieved. Recorded spectra before and after digestion confirmed the stability of polymers. No large microplastic particles were detected in fish intestines from the Canal. Differences in intestinal content were observed between pike and carp; pike contained undigested fish remains, while carp samples showed inorganic residues such as calcium carbonate.

Conclusions: The applied digestion and ATR-FTIR identification method proved effective for analyzing large microplastics (1–5 mm) in fish intestines. Method improvement through density-based separation is recommended due to the high inorganic content in Canal fish samples.

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Digestion, Microplastic, Fish, Intestine, ATR-FTIR

Microplastic background levels in German soils: The influence of site-specific characteristics and land-use practices

Sandy Placzek¹, Karlheinz Weinfurtner², Wiebke Mareile Heinze³, Elke Bloem⁴, Zacharias Steinmetz¹

¹ RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau, Germany

² Fraunhofer-Institut für Molekularbiologie und angewandte Ökologie, Germany

³ Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden

⁴ Julius Kühn-Institut, Germany

s.placzek@rptu.de

Background & Objectives: Microplastics (< 5 mm; MPs) are anthropogenic pollutants that have been detected in all environmental compartments, including soil. Important sources of MPs to soils are tire abrasion, agriculture, horticulture, atmospheric deposition, and littering. However, knowledge of MP background levels in agricultural soils remains incomplete, which makes environmental assessments and the development of mitigation strategies difficult.

Methods: Our study aims at assessing the background levels of MPs in German soils and to elucidate the influence of site-specific characteristics and land-use practices on their spatial distribution. To this end, soil was sampled from 400 cropland and 200 pasture soils across Germany. The samples were characterized for soil texture, organic carbon content, and pH level. Polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polystyrene are the most produced plastics, and therefore their contents were quantified using solvent-based pyrolysis GC/MS. Additional method validation of the organic solvent extraction of PE, PP and PS was deemed necessary as the samples contained varying amounts of organic matter (0.7–39.0%). Recovery experiments were conducted on three soil textures: a clay soil (2.4% soil organic matter, SOM), a sandy loam (1.7% SOM), and a sandy silt (12.5% SOM). Recoveries varied with respect to polymer and soil texture. Higher polymer spikes (25 µg/g) yielded better recovery rates (12.5 – 88.0 %) than lower concentrations (5 µg/g, 0 – 48.9 %). The highest recovery rate was 88% for PS with quartz sand. Among the polymers tested, PE showed the highest recovery efficiency, whereas PP exhibited the lowest.

Conclusions: Recovery experiments with different soil textures are crucial in microplastic research to ensure accurate quantification, as varying soil properties can significantly affect the reliability of the extraction process. The monitoring efforts in this project will help to develop a geoinformatics-based assessment framework for classifying microplastic pollution in the German agricultural landscape and to derive recommendations for mitigating microplastic inputs.

Pyrolysis-GC/MS, Germany, Polyethylene, Polypropylene, Polystyrene

Mussel Tissue Digestion Protocols: Efficiency and Effects on Microplastics

Sevdalina H. Turmanova¹, Yancho H. Hristov¹, Dimitrina S. Kiryakova¹, Alexander N. Dimitrov², Emilia D. Ivanova², Plamena V. Atanasova¹, Ganka R. Kolchakova¹, Antonia S. Ilieva¹, Elena Y. Mollova², N. S. Todorov²

¹Faculty of Technical Sciences, Burgas State University „Prof. Dr. Assen Zlatarov“, Burgas, Bulgaria

²Faculty of Natural Sciences, Burgas State University „Prof. Dr. Assen Zlatarov“, Burgas, Bulgaria

gkolchakova@gmail.com

Background & Objectives: Microplastics (MPs) are emerging pollutants in marine ecosystems [1], and filter-feeding mussels are widely used as bioindicators [2]. A key step in MP analysis is tissue removal without altering plastics [3]. The aim of this study was to compare the efficiency of enzymatic, acidic, and alkaline digestion of lyophilized and frozen mussel tissues, and to evaluate their effects on selected polymers representing microplastics.

Methods: *M. galloprovincialis* samples, prepared in lyophilized and frozen forms, were subjected to enzymatic (Creon®25000 in Tris-HCl buffer, 37.8°C), acidic (HNO₃ + H₂O₂, 55°C), and alkaline (KOH + H₂O₂, 60°C) treatments. Digestion efficiency was determined gravimetrically and verified microscopically. High-density polyethylene (HDPE), polyamide (PA), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) were treated without biological matrix, and changes assessed by microscopy and ATR-FTIR spectroscopy, with similarity quantified by hit quality index (HQI).

Results: All methods achieved high digestion efficiency (>96%). Acidic digestion was the fastest and most effective (mean 99.49%) for mussel tissue removal, but induced measurable alterations in PA (HQI ~93.7%) and PVC (~95–96%). HDPE remained stable across all treatments (HQI >99.2%). PET showed high resistance (HQI >98%), with minor spectral shifts under acid exposure. Enzymatic and alkaline treatments preserved both morphology and ATR-FTIR spectra of all polymers (HQI close to 100%) under the tested conditions, with alkaline treatment providing a good balance between efficiency and structural stability.

Conclusions: These findings underline the importance of selecting digestion protocols according to polymer type and research goals, ensuring both effective removal of biological matrices and preservation of polymer integrity. Overall, the results support the use of *M. galloprovincialis* as a bioindicator for future assessments of microplastic pollution in the Black Sea.

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Microplastics, Black Sea, Burgas Bay, Mussels, Digestion Protocols

Microplastic Detection in Blood and Urine: A Comparative Study of Sample Preparation Methods using LDIR

Marina Auer¹, Ajay Khairnar¹, Thomas C. Meisel¹

¹ Montanuniversität - Technical University of Leoben, Chair of General and Analytical Chemistry, Leoben, Austria

thomas.meisel@unileoben.ac.at

Background & Objectives: Microplastics have recently been reported in human biological samples, raising concerns about potential health risks, although conclusive evidence is still lacking. The detection of particles in complex fluids such as blood and urine requires workflows that combine effective removal of biological material with strict contamination control. This study develops and evaluates preparation protocols for microplastic analysis in these matrices using Laser Direct Infrared spectroscopy (LDIR, Agilent 8700).

Methods: The approach builds on an initial review of ethical and legal aspects of handling biological samples, followed by contamination-controlled sampling, transport, and storage procedures. For blood, oxidative (H₂O₂) and alkaline (KOH) digestion were compared. Oxidative treatment produced foaming and persistent residues that obstructed analysis, whereas alkaline digestion under controlled conditions provided more reproducible filtrates suitable for spectroscopic identification. For urine, direct filtration as well as alkaline and oxidative digestion were investigated. All approaches were impeded by crystalline precipitates, most likely calcium phosphate, which masked particles on the filters and prevented reliable detection.

The samples and blanks were processed on gold-coated PET track-etched membranes. Blank experiments consistently revealed background particles from reagents and handling, highlighting the necessity of systematic blank correction. Across workflows, LDIR enabled simultaneous determination of polymer type, particle size, and particle number.

Conclusions: The findings demonstrate that alkaline digestion represents a workable pathway for blood, while urine remains analytically challenging under the tested conditions. By systematically testing multiple approaches, the study highlights critical obstacles such as foaming, crystalline precipitates and background contamination, providing a clear basis for optimisation. This framework not only supports harmonisation of workflows in human biomonitoring of microplastics but also guides future validation steps, including the use of spiking experiments and reference materials.

Sample preparation, Blood, Spectroscopy

Nonlinear optical imaging and Nile Red staining approaches for microplastic detection: Influence of additives and structural modifications

Milica Popović¹, Mira Aničić Urošević², Aleksandar Popović², Milica Čurčić¹, Mihailo D. Rabasović¹, Tanja Pajić³, Aleksandar Krmpot¹

¹Institute of Physics Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia

³University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology, Belgrade, Serbia

pmilica@ipb.ac.rs

Background & Objectives: Microplastics (MPs) are emerging environmental pollutants, for which standardized detection methods remain lacking due to their diverse shapes, chemical compositions, and the presence of various additives [1]. Although Nile Red (NR) staining is proposed as a rapid fluorescence-based detection approach [2], its reliability may be affected by particle properties. In this study, we applied nonlinear optical imaging and NR staining to investigate the optical characteristics of reference polymers and consumer-derived MPs, aiming to assess the influence of particle size, additives, and structural modifications to polymers' fluorescence and the reliability of NR-based detection.

Methods: Three types of reference polymers – high-density polyethylene (HDPE), polystyrene (PS), and polypropylene (PP) – were examined using nonlinear laser scanning microscopy modalities: two-photon excitation fluorescence (TPEF) and third harmonic generation (THG). Fluorescence spectra were recorded upon excitation at three different wavelengths: 730 nm, 800 nm and 1040 nm. Subsequently, reference polymers were stained with NR and re-analyzed. The same procedure was applied to MPs (<50 µm) obtained by grinding plastic packaging.

Results: Reference polymers exhibited negligible autofluorescence at all excitation wavelengths, whereas NR stained polymers induced strong fluorescence responses. In contrast, almost all MPs emitted measurable autofluorescence: HDPE and PP fluoresced upon the shorter excitation wavelengths (730 and 800 nm), with a weak signal upon excitation at 1040 nm, while PS displayed weak fluorescence only upon excitation at 730 nm. Unlike reference polymers, NR stained MPs did not substantially enhance the fluorescence signal. All studied MP samples exhibited strong THG signals.

Conclusions: While NR staining effectively induced fluorescence of pure polymers, its performance applied to commercial MPs is limited, highlighting the need for further investigation of how particle size, additives and structural changes of the plastic packaging affect dye binding. The consistently strong THG signals suggest the potential of this label-free modality for MP detection in environmental samples.

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Microplastics, Nonlinear optical imaging, Third harmonic generation, Two-photon excitation fluorescence, Nile Red

Optimization of microplastic analysis methods using the micro-FTIR technique

Madalina Calmuc¹, Valentina Andreea Calmuc¹, Nina – Nicoleta Lazar¹, Mihaela Timofti^{1,2}, Puiu-Lucian Georgescu^{1,2}, Catalina Iticescu^{1,2}

¹Rexdan Research Infrastructure, “Dunarea de Jos” University Galati, 800008 Galati, Romania

² Department of Chemistry, Physics and Environment, “Dunarea de Jos” University Galati, 800008 Galati, Romania

madalina.calmuc@ugal.ro

Background & Objectives: Microplastics (MPs) are emerging pollutants, ubiquitous in the environment, for which standardized methods of analysis have not yet been established [1]. Micro-FTIR is a non-destructive technique applied in the analysis of MPs extracted from various matrices [2]. The advantage of using this type of method is that it allows for the morphological characterization of MPs (e.g., shape, size).

Methods: The main objective of this study is to optimize the parameters of microplastics analysis methods using the Spotlight 400 FT-IR Imaging System, PerkinElmer, which is part of the REXDAN Research Infrastructure at “Dunarea de Jos” University of Galati, Romania. Thus, both microplastic particles from certified reference materials for polyethylene and polypropylene polymers and MPs samples taken from the Danube River were analyzed. Various filters, including polycarbonate gold-coated, aluminum oxide, silver, and polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) membranes, were tested on the surface of which MPs were scanned using a microscope.

Conclusions: Based on the tests performed, advantages and disadvantages were identified for each filter analysed, with the polycarbonate gold-coated and aluminum oxide filters being the most suitable in terms of accuracy results, and the PVDF filter in terms of cost-effectiveness.

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Microplastics, micro-FTIR, Filter, Optimization

Quantification of polyethylene in soils using pyrolysis–gas chromatography mass spectrometry: A comprehensive assessment of matrix interference and plastic weathering effects

Quynh Nhu Phan Le¹, Janja Vidmar², Pia Leban², Dimitrios Savvas³, Vasileios Papatotiropoulos³, Milica Velimirovic¹

¹Laboratory for inorganic and organic analysis, Flemish Institute for Technological Research, Mol, Belgium

²Department of Environmental Sciences, Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

³Department of Crop Science, Agricultural University of Athens, Athens, Greece

nhu.phan@vito.be

Background & Objectives: Quantification of polyethylene (PE) by pyrolysis-gas chromatography mass spectrometry (py-GC/MS) in complex matrices such as soil is hindered by poorly understood matrix interferences. Moreover, existing methods are validated mainly on large, pristine particles, overlooking the environmental relevant smaller, weathered plastics.

Methods: Here, we present a comprehensive assessment of PE quantification in soils, addressing the impacts of matrix interferences and polymer characteristics, especially weathering. Pristine and weathered mulch film PE (28-63 µm) were cryomilled, spiked into soil, extracted by freeze-thaw assisted density separation, Fenton digestion, filtration, and analyzed with Py-GC/MS. To evaluate the influence of polymer characteristics on quantification, calibration curves were prepared using pristine and aged mulch PE and commercial PE standards. Matrix effects were systematically assessed by monitoring 16 oligomers (C10-C25 alkenes) for sensitivity, diagnostic ion ratio stability, and relative oligomer ratios using a standard addition approach, to identify markers least influenced by soil interference.

Results: Preliminary results indicated significant oligomer-specific variation, determined by both plastic characteristic and matrix level. Pristine and weathered mulch PE showed clear differences in oligomer patterns and peak ratios in pyrograms. Method recoveries, calculated as the average of 16 oligomers and corrected against unspiked soils, were 36.6 ± 21.9% for pristine mulch PE and 10.5 ± 3.0% for weathered one, likely reflecting both their susceptibility to extraction losses and an approximate 20% reduction in instrumental sensitivity for weathered PE compared to pristine one. Application of the method to soils from strawberry fields with mulch film application revealed preliminary PE concentrations ranging from 0.5 to 19.5 µg/g, with higher values in organic-rich soils, likely reflecting false positives from residual organic matter after extraction.

Conclusions: Using PE as a case study, this work highlights the complexity of soil polymer quantification by py-GC/MS and underscores the need to address matrix interferences and polymer characteristics, particularly weathering, to improve analytical reliability.

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Microplastics, Polyethylene, Mulching films, Agricultural soil, Py-GC/MS

Unveiling Microplastic Diversity in Wastewater Sludge: Morphology and Color Patterns

Dovilė Motiejauskaitė¹, Karolina Barčauskaitė¹

¹Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry, Institute of Agriculture, Lithuania

dovile.motiejauskaite@lammc.lt

Background & Objectives: Microplastic (MP) contamination in wastewater systems has become a critical environmental concern due to its persistence and potential ecological impacts. Plastic particles in wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) are mostly originating from sources such as personal care products, synthetic textiles and industrial effluents. WWTPs act as both sinks and potential pathways for these particles, retaining a significant portion in sludge while also allowing a fraction to be released into receiving water bodies[1]. Sewage sludge, as a by-product of wastewater treatment, is a complex matrix rich in organic matter and other substances, making the isolation and characterization challenging[2].

Methods: This study aimed to extract and characterize microplastics from sludge collected from WWTPs employing distinct treatment technologies, focusing on particle size, shape, color and number of particles. By comparing the morphological features of microplastics between facilities, the work provides insights into how treatment processes influence MP retention and transformation.

Sewage sludge samples were collected from a wastewater treatment plant in Kaunas, Lithuania (large-scale WWTP) and Šilalė, Lithuania (small-scale WWTP). Fenton's reagent was applied to remove organic matter and saturated NaBr solution and distilled water were used to separate inorganic particles from MP. Extracted particles were characterized by size, shape, and color using a stereomicroscope (NIKON Z100, Japan) employing ImageJ program.

Results: The study showed that in the sewage sludge of small-scale wastewater treatment plant about 24.3 % fewer microplastic particles compared to the large-scale WWTP was found. Our findings support previous works that smaller particles are found more frequently than finer ones. Particles with a size ranging from 30 μm to 1 mm occupy about 80 % of all identified particles. The most predominant color were transparent and the shape – fragment and fiber.

Conclusions: The results highlight how treatment processes influence the composition and physical properties of microplastics retained in sludge, offering insights into potential environmental release and can help to simulate strategies for improved microplastic management. More information will be presented during the conference.

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Microplastics, Polyethylene, Mulching films, Agricultural soil, Py-GC/MS

“Up in the air, deep on the ground” - Quantification & Identification of Microplastics in Marine Sediments and Air by Pyrolysis-GC/MS

Michael Soll¹, Atsushi Watanabe², William Pipkin³

¹Frontier Laboratories Europe, 45359 Essen, Germany

²Frontier Laboratories Ltd., 963-8862 Koriyama, Japan

³Graduate School of Environmental Studies, Tohoku University, Sendai, Japan

Background & Objectives: Environmental pollution by plastics has become one of the most serious environmental issues. Microplastics may affect marine life by accumulating in the food chain and have a possible impact on human health. Therefore, analysis of microplastics in the environment is of interest. In this study, a vertical furnace pyrolyzer coupled to GC/MS (Py-GC/MS) was applied to microplastics analysis, since it provides high-sensitivity analysis and quantitative data even when the sample is a mixture of multiple polymers.

Methods: The analytical workflow and instrumental setup are described. A dedicated software using a new search algorithm[1] and mass spectral libraries were applied to identify and quantify micro plastics. Software features and step-by-step workflow are demonstrated. The libraries contain 11 and 12 abundant plastic types. For easy weighing of µg scale of polymers and to consider polymer-polymer side reactions, a Micro Plastic Calibration Standard Mixture [2] was used. A dedicated micro plastic GC column setup, containing a Precolumn and analytical separation column is improving chromatographic resolution. A newly developed multifunctional sampler (MFS) for splitless pyrolysis [3] without secondary reactions increased S/N ratio, thus improving limit of quantification of trace level micro/nano plastics. In the first study, offshore and coastal sediment samples have been analysed. After data analysis using the micro plastic search software, various plastic types could be detected and quantified. In the second study, we investigated the analysis of indoor airborne microplastics by Py-GC/MS [4]. Indoor air was passively sampled using quartz fibre filters. Sample preparation consisted only of cryo-milling the quartz filters used for sampling to ensure homogeneity.

Conclusions: The results demonstrate that MFS enabled Splitless Py-GC/MS can be used to identify and quantify microplastics at the nanogram level, allowing researchers to rapidly ascertain the magnitude of the microplastic threat in environmental air.

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Pyrolysis-GC/MS, Marine sediments, Air borne particles, Splitless pyrolysis

SESSION 2: Sources, fate, and transport of microplastics in the environment

- Contributions of agricultural practices (plastic mulches, foils) to microplastic pollution
- Microplastics in wastewater sludge and compost: pathways to soil and be on (underground water, streams, and rivers)
- Environmental factors influencing microplastic degradation and transformation
- Modeling microplastic transport in organic-rich systems
- Interactions between microplastics, organic matter, and pollutants
- Analysis of microplastic particles in aquatic environments
- Microplastic research in the atmosphere

MODERATOR:

Prof. Aleksandra Tubić

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Serbia

Prof. Dr Aleksandra Tubić, full professor at the University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences. The focus of her scientific research is behaviour of microplastics in the environment. She has been intensively working on the investigation of the plastic waste and microplastic pollution impact and its interactions with organic pollutants across diverse environmental mediums.

Currently, she is the leader of Serbian team in two projects under the HORIZON EUROPE program and holds the position of Vice Chair of the COST action PRIORITY.

Beyond her academic endeavours, she is actively involved in the work of the International Water Association (IWA Groundwater Management Group). Her scholarly contributions extend to over 200 publications, including 70 papers featured in SCIE journals (h-index 20).

Furthermore, she is deeply committed to fostering knowledge exchange between academia, industry, and policy makers in the realm of environmental protection.

KEYNOTE SPEAKER:
Dr. Amy Lusher

*Senior Research Scientist (Forsker 1)
at Norwegian Institute for Water
Research*

Dr. Amy Lusher is a marine biologist who has focused her career on the topic microplastics and litter pollution. She has authored and co-authored over 60 peer-reviewed publications, with several seminal publications on the assessment of microplastics. For the last five years, she has been recognised as a Highly Cited Researcher in the field of Environment and Ecology and Cross Field – by Web of Science. In addition, she has co-authored numerous book chapters, conference proceedings and research reports, and contributed towards several international technical reports.

Amy's research currently focuses on the necessity of best practice methods to understand distribution, interactions, and potential effects of microplastics in the environment. She is actively engaged in method development and optimisation, she works with different environmental matrices including sediments, water column, and biota. Dr Lusher contributes to international working groups on marine litter including those associated to OSPAR, AMAP and ICES. Formally she was associated to GESAMP (Group of Experts on the Scientific Aspects of Marine Environmental Protection) Group 40: Microplastics in the Marine Environment (2015-2019), where she focuses on microplastic distribution and the ecological consequences of exposure of biota to microplastics.

Global microplastics monitoring and harmonisation

Dr. Amy Lusher

Microplastics and other plastic litter pose a critical and escalating threat to global freshwater and marine ecosystems. While substantial progress has been made in developing regionally recognized monitoring approaches, these efforts remain insufficiently aligned with global initiatives. Existing frameworks - such as the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Regional Sea Conventions - have historically overlooked freshwater systems, resulting in data gaps, inconsistent methodologies, and weak cross-regional harmonization. To address this, it is essential to assess the full source-to-sea continuum, enabling a more integrated and focused understanding of plastic pollution dynamics. Research has concentrated on validating monitoring approaches and comparing methods to support policy goals. However, regulatory bodies often demand answers that current methods cannot yet provide. Such dialogue can be challenging, as researchers prioritize technical rigor and precision, while policymakers seek actionable insights but may struggle to define clear priorities. Bridging these differing approaches requires collaboration to ensure scientific capabilities align with policy needs. Although some methods are suitable for international monitoring, limitations persist regarding target plastic types and sizes, sampling strategies, analytical capacity, and data harmonization. Balancing scientific advancement with the urgency of policy action remains a central challenge. This presentation will focus on harmonized, scalable monitoring strategies that bridge freshwater and marine systems - supporting evidence-based policy and global environmental protection. It will highlight international efforts to assess Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) for microplastic monitoring methods and how these assessments inform choices. Attention will be given to interdisciplinary activities and their roles in harmonizing monitoring, including the Integrated Marine Debris Observing System (IMDOS) and the AMAP LMEG. These examples illustrate how global harmonization is not only feasible but essential for building robust, policy-relevant data infrastructures to guide mitigation strategies across diverse environmental contexts.

Application of coagulation/flocculation process for microplastic and textile fiber removal in different water matrices

Sanja Vasiljević¹, Maja Vujić¹, Tijana Marjanović Srebro¹, Jasmina Agbaba¹, Radivoj Tomić¹, Aleksandra Tubić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, biochemistry and environmental protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

sanjav@dh.uns.ac.rs

Background & Objectives: Microplastics enter the environment mainly through human activities such as poor waste management, discharge of untreated wastewater, tire wear, washing of synthetic textiles, and the use of personal care products containing microbeads. Industrial sources, including plastic pellets, further increase their presence in water, soil, and air [1]. Among them, textile microfibers have gained attention as a specific subgroup, since the textile industry produces over 42 million tons of synthetic fibers annually, a large fraction of which ends up in wastewater [2].

Coagulation–flocculation has emerged as an effective physicochemical method for microplastic removal, especially where conventional treatment processes are insufficient [3]. The application of aluminum- and iron-based salts can enhance particle aggregation and improve removal efficiency.

Methods: This study investigated the impact of coagulation conditions on the removal of microplastics (polyethylene – PE, polyvinyl chloride – PVC) and textile microfibers (synthetic and mixed synthetic/cotton) from different water matrices: Danube River water, municipal wastewater effluent, washing machine effluent, and a synthetic matrix. Ferric (III) chloride (FeCl_3) and polyaluminum chloride (PACl) were applied as coagulants at doses of 20–220 mg/L and 10–50 mg/L, respectively.

Results: Results showed that PVC was the most successfully removed across all matrices, particularly with FeCl_3 (up to 100% in washing machine effluent), while PE exhibited the lowest removal potential, especially in more complex matrices (wastewater), where its efficiency with PACl was only 16–31%. Both types of textile fibers were effectively removed (up to 99%) with FeCl_3 , except in municipal wastewater effluent (~70%). PACl was more effective in simpler matrices, such as the synthetic one, and at lower doses. In contrast, FeCl_3 consistently achieved better results in more complex matrices, particularly those rich in organic matter.

Conclusions: Overall, the study provides insights into the behavior of microplastics and textile fibers under realistic treatment conditions and highlights the potential of optimized coagulation–flocculation for improving wastewater treatment.

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (Grants No. 451-03-137/2025-03/ 200125 & 451-03-136/2025-03/ 200125).

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Microplastics, Textile fibers, Coagulation and flocculation, Water treatments

A Decade of Research on Biofouled Microplastics: Alterations in the Fate and Transport of Particles

Müge Nigdeli¹, Başak Güven¹, Nurgül Çelik Balcı²

¹Institute of Environmental Sciences, Bogazici University, Bebek, 34342, Istanbul, Türkiye

²Department Geological Engineering, Faculty of Mines, Istanbul Technical University, Maslak, 34469, Istanbul, Türkiye

muge.ozdemir@bogazici.edu.tr

Background & Objectives: Mechanisms governing the fate and transport of microplastic particles in natural aquatic environments remain poorly understood. The behavior of microplastics, particularly under biofilm formation, has emerged as a new and critical research area. Biofilm development can substantially modify their intrinsic properties including density, polymer type, size and shape; thereby altering their transport and distribution dynamics within water bodies. In this review, effect of biofilm formation on the fate and transport processes of various microplastic particles was addressed.

Methods: A total of 137 relevant papers published between 2015 and 2025 were identified from the Web of Science (WOS) database, using the keywords microplastic and biofouling. WOS categories were selected as 'Environmental Sciences', 'Marine Freshwater Biology', 'Water Resources', 'Oceanography', 'Microbiology', 'Ecology' and 'Limnology' are selected as WOS categories.

Results: According to result of the review, fate of biofouled microplastics in the aquatic environment has been examined separately under the following headings: 'microplastic abundance', 'sorption', 'aging' and 'ingestion'.

Conclusions: It can be concluded that abundance of biofilm-formed microplastics had been predominantly examined under the subjects of plastic density, weight, microplastic size and spectroscopy spectra. The aging of biofilm-coated microplastics has been classified into three primary categories: thermal oxidative, solar and chemical degradation. Ingestion processes were mainly investigated in relation to specific aquatic organisms, revealing that microplastic uptake through ingestion tends to increase with biofilm formation due to the enhanced toxicity associated with biofouling. Moreover, biofilm development amplifies the vector role of microplastics for emerging contaminants by altering their sorption and desorption capacities.

Fig 1. (a) Research methodology including the selected categories of WOS Core Collection database. (b) Distribution of publications addressing biofouling on microplastics according to the WOS database (retrieved on June 12th, 2025)

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Boğaziçi University Research Fund Grant Number 20200.

Microplastic, Biofouling, Biofilm Formation, Fate and Transport

Current Situation of Microplastic Pollution in the Black Sea (TÜRKİYE) Whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*)

Gonca ALAK¹, Mine KÖKTÜRK², Süleyman ÖZDEMİR³, Aslı Çilingir YELTEKİN⁴, Fatma Betül ÖZGERİŞ⁵, Serkan YILDIRIM⁶, Arzu UÇAR⁷, Veysel PARLAK⁸, Hünkar Avni DUYAR⁹, Emre ÇAĞLAK¹⁰, Muhammed ATAMANALP⁶

¹Department of Seafood Processing, Faculty of Fisheries, Atatürk University, Erzurum, Türkiye.

²Department of Organic Agriculture Management, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Iğdır University, Iğdir, Türkiye.

³Department of Fisheries, Faculty of Fisheries, Sinop University, Sinop, Türkiye.

⁴Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Yüzüncü Yıl, Van, Türkiye.

⁵Department of Nutrition and Dietetics, Faculty of Health Sciences, Atatürk University, Erzurum, Türkiye.

⁶Department of Pathology, Faculty of Veterinary, Ataturk University, Erzurum, Türkiye, Veterinary Faculty, Department of Pathology, Kyrgyzstan-Türkiye Manas University, Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan.

⁷Department of Aquaculture, Faculty of Fisheries, Ataturk University, Erzurum, Türkiye.

⁸Department of Basic Sciences, Faculty of Fisheries, Ataturk University, Erzurum, Türkiye.

⁹Department of Seafood Processing Technology, Faculty of Fisheries, Sinop University, Sinop, Türkiye.

¹⁰Department of Seafood Processing Technology, F. of Fisheries, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, Rize, Türkiye

mataman@atauni.edu.tr

Background & Objectives: It was aimed to obtain information about the current status of microplastic pollution, which constitutes an agenda in aquatic environments, in *Merlangius merlangus* tissues.

Methods: Whiting (*Merlangius merlangus*) were sampled seasonally from 3 stations (9 stations in total) in the Eastern, Central and Western regions of the Black Sea within the borders of Türkiye. The targeted tissues of *Merlangius merlangus* were homogenized with buffer solution (KH₂PO₄) and the experimental procedure was performed [1].

Results: As a result of the analysis on the presence and abundance of microplastic (MP) in 4 different tissues (muscle, liver, gill and digestive system) of fish samples; In the eastern black sea region, 0.15±0.51 (MP/g) in muscle tissue, 0.07±0.027 (MP/g) in liver, 0.59±0.69 (MP/g) in gill tissue and 0.52±0.80 (MP/g) in digestive tract; In the Central Black Sea region, 0.17±0.37 (MP/g) in muscle tissue, 0.20±0.41 (MP/g) in liver, 0.73±0.80 (MP/g) in gill tissue and 0.53±0.83 in digestive tract; In the Western Black Sea region, microplastic presence was determined as 0.04±0.10 (MP/g) in muscle tissue, 0.06±0.24 (MP/g) in liver, 0.39±0.70 (MP/g) in gill tissue and 0.78±0.94 (MP/g) in digestive system.

Conclusions: In terms of environmental and consumer health, it is important to monitor especially economical fish species.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by TÜBİTAK 1001 research project with the code of 123Y106

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Pollution, Microplastic, *Merlangius merlangus*

Degradation of microplastics in Douala Bay, Cameroon

Bella Bella Jean Marie¹, Ngamo Kouayep William Martial¹, Eba Edibi Daniel²

¹University of Douala, Faculty of Sciences, Douala, Cameroon

²University of Ebolowa, Department of Geosciences and Environment, Ebolowa, Cameroon

bellajm@yahoo.com

Background & Objectives: Douala Bay, located in the Littoral region of Cameroon, is facing increasing pollution from plastic waste, threatening its unique mangrove ecosystem. This problem is exacerbated by heavy rainfall and the intense port and industrial activity that characterises the region. This article aims to analyse the environmental factors that influence the degradation of microplastics in the sediments and surface waters of Douala Bay, in order to understand the mechanisms of their transformation and their impact on local wildlife.

Methods: Our methodology combined a review of the literature on plastic pollution in tropical environments [1], with a series of laboratory analyses on samples taken from several strategic points in the bay. We studied the effect of intense sunlight (photodegradation), high temperatures, and humidity on the fragmentation of plastics into microplastics [2]. In addition, we assessed the role of microbial biofilms, particularly the 'plastisphere' in estuaries, in the degradation and alteration of the physicochemical properties of microplastics.

Results: The results of this study indicate that the combination of strong solar radiation and high temperatures accelerates the physical fragmentation of plastics. At the same time, we observed significant microbial colonisation of plastic particles, which alters their density and behaviour in the water column, potentially making them more easily ingestible by marine organisms. These transformations have direct implications for the food chain and the toxicity of microplastics, as they can release additives and adsorb pollutants [3].

Conclusions: In conclusion, the degradation of microplastics in Douala Bay is a complex process influenced by environmental factors specific to humid tropical climates. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for developing pollution management strategies tailored to this region and for protecting its fragile ecosystem.

Acknowledgments: The research was funded by the City Council of Douala, to whom we extend our gratitude.

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Douala, Cameroon, Microplastics, Pollutants, Environmental

Detection and Spatial Pattern Analysis of Microplastics in Sewage Sludge– Treated Sandy Soils

Alexia Balla¹, Izabella Babcsányi¹, Karolina Solymos¹, György Sipos¹, Viktória Blanka-Végi¹

¹University of Szeged Department of Physical and Environmental Geography, Szeged, Hungary

balla.alexia@szte.hu

Background & Objectives: An increasing proportion of sewage sludge, generated as a by-product of wastewater treatment is used in agriculture as organic fertilizer, partly substituting the use of synthetic fertilizers. This practice, however, may have side effects such as the release of micro- and nanoplastics into arable soils. According to European studies, microplastic concentrations in agricultural soils range between 700 and 4,000 particles/kg; however, no data are currently available for Hungary. Our study aims to analyse the spatial and vertical distribution of microplastics on agricultural lands, which received sewage sludge treatment for the first time in April 2025.

Methods: The two analysed sample sites (18 and 46 ha) are located in the sandy area of the Danube-Tisa Interfluvium. Both fields received sewage sludge treatment at a dosage of 13 t/ha of raw sludge. At the 46-ha plot, samples were collected at 11 points at depths of 0–20 cm and 20–40 cm. Two soil profiles were sampled in 5 cm intervals, and one control sample was taken. On the 18-ha plot, sown with sunflowers, samples were collected along two transects from the topsoil, and four additional boreholes were drilled down to 100/120 cm. For microplastic analysis, soil samples are subjected to density separation after air drying, followed by hydrogen-peroxide treatment. Afterwards, fluorescent staining is applied to enable optical microscopic detection and counting. Selected samples are also undergone micro-FTIR microscopic analysis for polymer identification.

Results: Our results showed that the microplastic concentrations ranged from 1000 to 5000 particles/kg. The spatial distribution of microplastics showed that the concentrations were lower on the edges of the plots, while the highest values were measured in the central parts. The vertical distribution of microplastics reflects the effect of human interventions, as the concentrations were 2-3 times higher in the top 20 cm layer compared to the layer underneath (20-40 cm).

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the PLAGROSYS 2024-1.2.3-HU-RIZONT-2024-00010 project financed from the NRD Fund, Hungary

Agricultural soil, Sewage sludge, Spatial distribution

Drinking Water Systems as a Source of Microplastics

Agnieszka Szuster-Janiaczyk¹, Małgorzata Komorowska-Kaufman¹, Alina Pruss¹, Beata Mądrecka-Witkowska¹, Mirosław Szybowicz², Tomasz Runka², Ewelina Nowak², Karolina Olszewska²

¹ Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Energy, Poznan, Poland

² Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Materials Science and Technical Physics, Poznan, Poland

agnieszka.szuster-janiaczyk@put.poznan.pl

Background & Objectives: Plastic pipes are widely used in water distribution systems, yet their potential to release microplastics into drinking water remains insufficiently understood. This study aimed to develop and validate a procedure for sampling, filtering, and preparing water samples to assess the occurrence of microplastics in pressurized supply systems.

Methods: A year-long pilot-scale experiment was conducted under operating pressures of 4.5–5.0 bar, using both model water and tap water. The installation consisted of two independent 100 m modules, one made of PVC and the other of PE, with stainless steel measurement panels to avoid contamination. Hydraulic conditions included static, circulation, and flow regimes. Released particles were identified with Raman spectroscopy, as recommended by the EU Directive on drinking water quality. In parallel, 50 key physicochemical parameters were analyzed according to Standard Methods of Water and Wastewater Examination.

Results: Microplastic particles were detected in all tested samples. The highest concentrations were observed during the initial operation days, likely reflecting system adaptation to flow-through conditions. Particle abundance did not correlate with size, which was predominantly within the 2–6 µm range. Larger particles (>25 µm) appeared only sporadically.

Conclusions: Compared with literature reports, the detected microplastics were significantly smaller than the particles typically found in water supply networks (25–100 µm). This difference may be attributed to advanced degradation processes of the pipe materials as well as the application of Raman spectroscopy, which provides higher sensitivity for detecting smaller particles. These findings highlight the importance of advanced analytical methods in assessing microplastic contamination in drinking water systems.

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Plastic release, Drinking water, Water pipes, Raman spectroscopy

First experimental evidence of fast leaching of small (1.7 µm) microplastics added to soil in field conditions

Nick Krekelbergh¹, Patria Novita Kusuwardani¹, Yin Liu¹, Steven Sleutel¹, Bogdan Parakhonsky², Richard Hoogenboom³, André Skirtach², Stefaan De Neve¹

¹Ghent University, Department of Environment, Research Group Soil Fertility & Nutrient Management, Ghent, Belgium

²Ghent University, Department of Biotechnology, Research Group NanoBioTechnology, Ghent, Belgium

³Ghent University, Department of Organic and Macromolecular Chemistry, Supramolecular Chemistry Group, Ghent Belgium

nick.krekelbergh@ugent.be

Background & Objectives: Research on microplastics (MPs) in soils is much complicated due to the lack of dedicated (extraction) methodologies and the strong matrix interferences for MP detection, and there is almost no research on the dynamics of the smallest MPs in soil (< 20 µm). In our research we first compared the possible detection of the smallest MP fraction (1–2 µm) by µ-Raman spectroscopy and fluorescence microscopy in matrices of highly varying complexity. Subsequently, we have demonstrated that it is possible to use fluorescent MPs to measure the rate of leaching process of small MPs in soils under field conditions.

Methods: In a first experiment, fluorescent polystyrene (PS) microparticles (1.71 ± 0.03 µm) were added at concentrations of 0.1–0.001% to different matrices: pure quartz sand, soils of varying texture (sandy loam, silt loam, clay loam) with removed soil organic matter (SOM) and with native SOM intact. After mixing and compaction, both Raman spectra and fluorescence microscopy images were collected. Characteristic PS Raman peaks (main fingerprint peak at 1001 cm⁻¹) were detected in quartz sand (all concentrations), and in sandy loam and silt loam soils without SOM (only at some concentrations), but not in any of the other cases. In contrast, fluorescence microscopy consistently visualized MPs in all matrices across all concentrations.

In a second experiment, fluorescent PS MPs were introduced into a sandy loam soil under field conditions at a concentration of 70 mg kg⁻¹, applied to small surface plots (circles of ~0.2 m diameter) to a depth of 3 cm. Soil samples were collected at regular intervals across different depths. Using fluorescence microscopy, the rapid downward movement of MPs could be tracked, showing that MPs reached a depth of 30 cm after 41 days and 100 cm after 211 days, indicating high migration rates of small MPs driven by rainfall infiltration.

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Microplastics, soil, Leaching, Fluorescence microscopy, Raman spectroscopy

Microplastic and microfibre pollution in unexplored caves

Valentina Balestra^{1,2}, Sonia Tassone³

¹ Department of Environment, Land and Infrastructure Engineering, Politecnico di Torino, Italy

² Biologia Sotterranea Piemonte – Gruppo di Ricerca, Italy

³ Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences, University of Turin, Italy

valentina.balestra@hotmail.com

Background & Objectives: Microplastic and microfibre contamination has emerged as a pressing global issue, however, karst systems remain largely overlooked. Due to their properties, these microparticles of anthropogenic origin are highly mobile and environmentally persistent, allowing them to reach even the most remote ecosystems. Subterranean environments - the so-called “dark continent” - represent one of the least explored frontiers of terrestrial science, with vast areas still inaccessible. In such hypogean systems, the distribution of pollutants is tightly regulated by the interplay between surface–subsurface connectivity, aquifer hydrodynamics, geological context, and local environmental factors. In this study, the first evidence of microplastic and microfibre pollution in unexplored caves was presented, revealing how human activity could indirectly impact even the uncontaminated environments of the dark continent.

Methods: Working together with speleologists, sediment samples from unexplored caves of the Abruzzo Region, Italy, were collected and investigated. Examined microparticles were counted and characterized by composition, size, shape, fluorescence, and color, via microscopy and spectroscopy.

Conclusions: Our findings show that microplastic concentrations were generally low or absent, whereas natural and regenerated microfibres were more frequent, with fibres representing the dominant morphological category. Most particles were transparent and exhibited fluorescence under UV light. Likely sources of contamination in the study area include atmospheric deposition, local anthropogenic activities, road networks, and waste dispersal. These results provide clear evidence that anthropogenic microparticles are present even in remote karstic caves, posing potential risks to subterranean biota and groundwater resources. Given the intrinsic connectivity of karst systems, there is an urgent need for systematic monitoring and protection. We also emphasize the key role of speleologists in contributing to data collection during explorations, as such rarely studied habitats can provide critical insights into pollutant pathways, ecosystem vulnerability, and conservation priorities. Future long-term research will be essential to elucidate sources, transport mechanisms, and ecological impacts of these contaminants.

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Microplastics, Microfibres, Pollution, Caves, Karst

Microplastic Contamination in Organic-Rich Agricultural Soils: Sources, Impacts, and Mitigation Approaches

Shah Irfan Ali¹

¹PhD Student & Independent Researcher, Chief Editor – Daily Rehai Karachi, Karachi, Pakistan

dailyrehai@gmail.com

Background & Objectives: The ubiquitous presence of microplastics (MPs) in organic-rich agricultural soil matrices constitutes a growing global concern, fundamentally impacting soil fertility, microbial community dynamics, and potential food chain transfer. Agri-systems heavily reliant on high-organic amendments (compost, manure, biosolids) are uniquely vulnerable due to the strong affinity between polymer residues and organic matter components. This research aims to systematically identify the major sources and environmental transport pathways responsible for MP influx into these systems and to quantify their immediate impacts on soil physical structure and overall ecosystem health.

Methods: A hybrid methodological approach was employed, combining a comprehensive systematic literature review with a field-based analytical campaign focusing on compost-treated farmlands. Soil samples were subjected to rigorous density separation protocols, followed by confirmation and polymer characterisation using Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. Analytical results detailing MP abundance and polymer types were subsequently benchmarked against global contamination datasets to assess input-specific and regional variability in MP loading.

Results: Preliminary findings confirm that MPs, predominantly polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) fragments, enter agricultural soils via three primary vectors: organic fertilizers (compost/manure), irrigation water supplies, and the in-situ fragmentation of plastic mulch. Crucially, the presence of these polymers was correlated with measurable disruptions in soil aggregate stability, a significant reduction in microbial biomass, and observable hindrances in the bioavailability of essential macro- and micronutrients.

Conclusions: The pervasive introduction of MPs into organic-rich matrices fundamentally threatens the long-term resilience and sustainability of global agricultural systems. Effective mitigation requires a multi-pronged strategy, including the immediate adoption of stricter regulatory standards for organic amendment quality, the accelerated deployment of certified biodegradable mulching alternatives, and integrated waste-stream management. This study strongly advocates for the harmonization of international protocols for MP detection and validated risk assessment frameworks within agricultural environments

Microplastics, Agricultural Soils, Organic Matter, Soil Health, Mitigation Strategies

Nanoplastics in Loch Ness and surrounding rivers and channels

Dušan Materić¹, Mike Peacock², Stuart Gibb³

¹ Department of Environmental Analytical Chemistry, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research – UFZ, Germany

² Department of Geography & Planning, University of Liverpool, UK

³ Environmental Research Institute, The University of the Highlands and Islands – North, West and Hebrides, UK

dusan.materic@ufz.de

Background & Objectives: Nanoplastics (NPs) are an emerging class of pollutants that remain challenging to accurately quantify in environmental matrices. Increasing evidence suggests their potential for long-range atmospheric and aquatic transport, contributing to their global distribution[1,2]. Understanding NP occurrence in remote environments is therefore essential for identifying sources, transport pathways, and baseline background levels.

Methods: In this study, we analyzed water samples from Loch Ness and surrounding rivers and channels in the Scottish Highlands to assess the presence and composition of nanoplastics using Thermal Desorption–Proton Transfer Reaction Mass Spectrometry (TD-PTR-MS)[3]. This represents one of the first reports of nanoplastics in UK inland waters.

Results: The dominant polymer types detected were polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polyethylene (PE), and tire-wear particles (TWP). Nanoplastics were present even at depths exceeding 100 m in Loch Ness. Subsurface NP concentrations in lakes were influenced by the proximity of local sources, while among the rivers, the Ness River showed the highest levels near urban areas, with some tributaries exhibiting no detectable NPs.

Conclusions: The combined evidence points to both long-range and local inputs: background levels of PET across multiple samples indicate remote or airborne sources, while elevated concentrations near populated or industrial areas highlight localized emissions.

Spatial patterns suggest a mix of local and long-range inputs. Elevated NP concentrations near populated and industrial areas point to local emissions, while consistent background levels of PET across remote sites indicate atmospheric or diffuse sources. These findings demonstrate nanoplastics to be pervasive even in isolated freshwater systems, and underline the need for integrated monitoring approaches to better understand their transport and fate.

Fig. 1. Nanoplastics concentration and polymer type found in subsurface water of Loch Ness

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Nanoplastics, Loch Ness, TD-PTR-MS, Microplastics

Plastic Pollution in Polar Regions: Comparison of Case Studies from the Southern (Falklands) and Northern (Svalbard) Hemispheres

Agnieszka Dąbrowska¹, Weronika Łada², Dorota Wiktorowicz³, Teresa Witkowska²

¹University of Warsaw, Faculty of Chemistry, Laboratory of Spectroscopy of Nanomaterials, Pasteura 1 st., 02-093 Warsaw, Poland

²University Centre of Environmental Studies and Sustainable Development, Żwirki i Wigury 93 st., 02-089 Warsaw, Poland

³University of Warsaw, Faculty of Biology, Biological and Chemical Research Centre, Institute of Evolutionary Biology, Żwirki i Wigury 101 st., 02-089 Warsaw, Poland

adabrowska@chem.uw.edu.pl

Background & Objectives: Marine microplastics (MPs), including the remote and sensitive polar regions, are ubiquitous within the environment. Due to their low accessibility, the data about the MPs pollution is still limited. Despite many common features, the situation in both hemispheres is entirely different. Namely, Svalbard is under much higher anthropogenic pressure, and its capital beaches (Longyearbyen) are highly contaminated. For this reason, the proper monitoring strategy will be related to the issue of proper samples' selection. Thus, we propose the local sources (LS) idea to monitor those parts comprehensively.

Methods: From LS plastics (mainly from PE), a total of 36 strains representing 20 fungal taxa were isolated. The most frequently isolated taxa were: *Mucor* (5 strains), *Trichoderma* (5 strains), *Phoma* (4 strains), *Cadophora luteo-olivacea* (3 strains), and *Linnemannia gamsii* species complex sensu Vandepol & Bonito (3 strains). Five taxa were recorded from Svalbard for the first time. LS in Longyearbyen consisted of PE (64%), PP (27%), and PS (9%), whereas all plastic composition was identified as PE (36%), PVC (19%), PP (16%), PET (8%), PS (5%), PA (2%), with the contribution of cellulose (3%) and other materials (11%). On the other hand, the Falklands are relatively little contaminated, and plastic might be holistically tackled with its dynamic environmental changes. Plastic fragments were collected in five sites within the Falklands: Saunders Island and East Falkland. One additional point chosen at West Falkland did not contain visible plastic particles. All samples were spectrally identified and characterised (by Raman spectroscopy, FTIR and ATR-FTIR methods). We confirmed that the ghost nets and littering by tourists were dominant local sources. Clear indications of the plastic tide from the fisheries are also underlined.

Conclusions: This research provides sampling strategies, spectral identification, and ageing modelling with preliminary conclusions about the sentinel species for bio interactions and the insight into the underestimated role of fungi. Finally, for the zones in which ghost netting is one of the main factors contributing to the problem (Falklands), the mitigation strategy based on the upcycling of lost or abandoned nets to blends or recycled products was discussed. Tackling an essential issue of plastic pollution in this relatively little-contaminated zone may help model the fate, transport, and behaviour of secondary microplastics present in the Antarctic.

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Quantification, characterisation and human health exposure of microplastic from indoor Environment

Nisarg Mehta¹, Barbara Kozielska¹

¹Department of Air Protection, Faculty of Energy and Environmental Engineering, Silesian University of Technology, 22B Konarskiego St., 44-100 Gliwice, Poland

Nisarg.dipakkumar.mehta@polsl.pl

Background & Objectives: Indoor microplastics (MPs) are emerging contaminants with potential human health risks [1]. MPs are synthetic particles <5 mm, are increasingly found in indoor environments, where humans spend ~ 90% of their time. Hospitals, with their unique microenvironments and use of synthetic materials, are particularly vulnerable yet understudied in this context. This study presents the first comprehensive assessment of MPs in hospital indoor settled dust in India, focusing on quantification, morphological and chemical characterization, spatial distribution, and human exposure.

Methods: Dust samples were collected from various zones (e.g., OPD, ICU, corridors) in two hospitals (public and private) in Rajkot, India. Samples underwent organic digestion and density separation, followed by optical microscopy and FTIR spectroscopy. Statistical analyses included Kruskal-Wallis tests and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Human exposure was assessed using Estimated Daily Intake (EDI) models.

Results: The study found high levels of microplastics (MPs) in hospital dust, averaging 65–80 MPs/g. Fibers were the most common shape (52–69%), with red and blue colors linked to synthetic textiles and medical items. PET and PE were the dominant polymers. Most particles measured 200–500 µm, though smaller, potentially more harmful MPs were likely underestimated. Infants faced the highest exposure, up to 0.82 MPs/kg/day in high-traffic zones. While overall distribution appeared uniform, zones like ICUs had lower levels, indicating that hospital activities and materials influence MP presence. Indian hospitals are significant hotspots for indoor MP pollution, with exposure risks influenced by institutional practices.

Conclusions: This baseline study urges targeted mitigation strategies—reducing synthetic textiles, improving air filtration, and minimizing single-use plastics. Future research should standardize methodologies, address sub-50 µm MPs and nanoplastics, and employ advanced techniques like Raman spectroscopy and pyrolysis-GC-MS to better understand exposure dynamics.

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Microplastic, Indoor, Settled dust, Hospital, FTIR, Human Health

Towards a Framework for Emerging Contaminant Analysis for Marine Stranded Species in UAE

Lara Dronjak¹, Fatin Samara¹, Dina Tenji², Sofian Kanan¹, Sandra Knuteson¹, Fadi Yaghmour³

¹ Department of Biology, Chemistry and Environmental Sciences, American University of Sharjah, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates

² University of Novi Sad – Faculty of Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, 21000, Novi Sad, Serbia

³ Hefaiyah Mountain Conservation Centre (Scientific Research Department), Environment and Protected Areas Authority, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates

ldronjak@aus.edu

Background & Objectives: Marine ecosystems are increasingly threatened by emerging contaminants such as microplastics (MPs), per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), pharmaceuticals, personal care products, and other pollutants [1]. These compounds pose serious risks to marine organisms, particularly stranded species that serve as bioindicators of ecosystem health [2]. This study establishes a comprehensive framework for assessing emerging contaminants in marine stranded species along the UAE coastline, integrating standardized sampling, extraction, and analytical methodologies to improve comparability across species and pollutants.

Methods: As part of this framework, we conducted the first large-scale investigation of MPs contamination in stranded seabirds and sea snakes from the Arabian Gulf and Gulf of Oman coasts. Twenty seabird specimens—Common Black-headed Gulls (*Chroicocephalus ridibundus*, n=14) and Socotra Cormorants (*Phalacrocorax nigrogularis*, n=6)—and sixty-three sea snakes from six species were analyzed.

Results: MPs were detected in 100% of seabird samples and 95.24% of sea snake specimens, confirming widespread exposure. Fibers were the dominant morphology, accounting for 71.6% in seabirds and 96.92% in sea snakes. FTIR-ATR spectroscopy confirmed the synthetic origin of the particles, identifying polypropylene (PP) as the dominant polymer in seabirds (72.2%) and nylon (PA) in sea snakes (82.35%).

Conclusions: The predominance of synthetic fibers suggests that textile microfibers are the main source of MPs, released during washing and incompletely removed by wastewater treatment plants. Once discharged, these fibers accumulate in coastal ecosystems and are ingested by marine organisms across multiple trophic levels. This study highlights the pervasive nature of MPs pollution and its ecological implications for marine predators. The proposed framework establishes a foundation for systematic contaminant assessment and cross-species comparisons, emphasizing the need for integrated monitoring and mitigation strategies to address emerging contaminants in UAE marine ecosystems.

Fig. 1. Microplastics found in seabirds and sea snakes

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Microplastics, Marine stranded species, Emerging contaminants

Tire wear microplastics in motion: Environmental transport, toxicity, and fate

Gabriela Kalčíková¹, Barbara Klun¹, Ula Putar¹

¹Faculty of Chemistry and Chemical Technology, University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia

gabriela.kalcikova@fkkt.uni-lj.si

Background & Objectives: Tyre wear microplastics (TWMPs) are generated through friction between vehicle tyres and road surfaces and represent a significant fraction of microplastic pollution. Despite their abundance, the environmental implications of TWMPs remain poorly understood. In our research, we investigated their transport, fate, and effects on aquatic organisms.

Methods: For transport, we examined their distribution in a laboratory constructed wetland with and without macrophytes. We then focused on their effects on the duckweed *Lemna minor* and, finally, on their biodegradation in the environment.

Results: Our findings demonstrated that TWMPs accumulate predominantly in sediments but can also remain suspended in the water column or float on the water surface. Their spatial distribution was influenced by the presence and type of aquatic vegetation, which affects particle retention and movement [1]. The ecotoxicological assessment using *Lemna minor* showed that TWMPs primarily affect root growth. Microscopic analysis revealed that the particles adhere to root surfaces, leading to the observed effects [2]. To further evaluate their environmental persistence, we tested biodegradability over 12 weeks under controlled conditions. The results showed minimal degradation, indicating long-term stability of TWMPs in the aquatic environment. In addition, we observed extensive leaching of metals and organic compounds, raising concerns that they may act as secondary sources of pollution [3].

Conclusions: The persistence and release of pollutants from TWMPs highlight the need for further research on their long-term ecological risks and possible mitigation strategies.

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Using sediment cores for studying the stratification of textile microfibers in geological records of the deep sea

Giuseppe Suaria¹, Panagiota Lalioti^{1,2}, Andrea Paluselli², Stefano Aliani², Claudio Pellegrini³, Stefania Romano³, Marzia Rovere³

¹ISMAR-CNR (National Research Council – Institute of Marine Sciences), Lerici (SP), Italy

²Department of Marine Biology, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium.

³ISMAR-CNR (National Research Council – Institute of Marine Sciences), Bologna, Italy

giuseppe.suaria@cnr.it

Background & Objectives: The deep sea, once considered pristine, is now recognized as a significant sink for anthropogenic debris, particularly microfibers from textiles. This study investigates the vertical distribution and composition of microfibers in deep-sea sedimentary records, aiming to evaluate their potential as stratigraphic markers of human activity.

Methods: A high-resolution sediment core, spanning over a century of deposition, was retrieved from a depth of 368 meters using an oceanic box corer and a stainless-steel liner. Fibers were extracted using ZnCl₂ density separation, quantified, and then chemically identified using μ FTIR. Fiber abundance was normalized to dry sediment weight and assigned to deposition years based on a sedimentation rate of 0.24 cm/year. In total, over 1200 fibers were identified.

Results: Results showed a clear stratification, with fiber abundance increasing significantly toward the surface layers. A strong positive correlation (Spearman's $\rho = 0.93$, $p < 0.001$) was observed between microfiber concentration and estimated deposition year. Blank comparisons using Wilcoxon tests confirmed that environmental samples contained significantly more fibers than laboratory controls ($p < 0.01$), validating sample integrity. Cellulose-based materials (man-made cellulosic, animal, and natural fibers) were the most abundant, accounting for 83.7% of the total. Synthetic fibers, comprising 12.7% of the total and including PET, PE, and PP, were found exclusively in layers deposited after the 1960s, a period consistent with the rise of global plastic production.

Conclusions: The findings confirm that microfibers serve as effective chronological markers of anthropogenic pollution and can indicate potential ecological stress in deep-sea environments. The deep sea is not only a long-term sink for human-made debris but also a valuable archive for reconstructing the history of human impact. These results underscore the need for further research to understand the long-term ecological effects of microfibers on benthic ecosystems.

Textile microfibers, Deep-sea sediments

Artificial Intelligence –Satellite Synergy for Multi-Year Detection of Coastal Plastic Hotspots in Santo Domingo

V.C. Shruti¹, Gurusamy Kutralam-Muniasamy², Fermín Pérez-Guevara¹, Ricardo Cuenca Alvarez²

¹Department of Biotechnology and Bioengineering, Centro de Investigación y de Estudios Avanzados del Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Av Instituto Politécnico Nacional 2508, San Pedro Zacatenco, Gustavo A. Madero, 07360, Ciudad de México, México

²CIITEC - IPN. Centro de Investigación e Innovación Tecnológica. Cda. de Cecati s/n, Santa Catarina, Azcapotzalco, 02250 Ciudad de México, CDMX

shruti.venkata@cinvestav.mx

Background & Objectives: Coastal plastic hotspots are ecological crises, choking marine life, harming fisheries, and exposing communities to toxic microplastics. Traditional monitoring methods—expensive and infrequent—fail to keep up. The 2018 plastic deluge at the Ozama River mouth in Santo Domingo was a wake-up call: without real-time, large-scale detection, mitigation efforts are blindfolded. But what if satellites could track this threat like a storm system? This study introduces a machine learning-powered system that analyzes 5 years of high-resolution satellite imagery (2020–2025) to pinpoint plastic hotspots, predict accumulation patterns, and enable proactive government action to address the root cause, not just the aftermath.

Methods: Sentinel-2 Level-2A surface reflectance images from 2020 to 2025 were processed to derive spectral indices including Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, Normalized Difference Water Index, Floating Debris Index, and Plastic Index. A Random Forest classifier was trained with labeled samples representing eight classes such as water, plastics, wood, seaweed, pumice, sea snot, sea foam and land. Coastal plastic hotspots were identified through classification and spatial analysis focused on shoreline areas.

Results: The classifier achieved an overall accuracy of 95% across 2020–2025, with strong per-class accuracy for plastics (producer's accuracy: 95%, user's accuracy: > 95%). Persistent hotspots of plastic debris were consistently detected near the Ozama River mouth, within 1 km of the coastline, especially in urban and industrially influenced zones. These findings highlight the Ozama River's role as a primary source and accumulation point for marine plastics in the area.

Conclusions: This study confirms the effectiveness of combining remote sensing with machine learning for multi-year coastal plastic monitoring. The repeated detection of plastic hotspots near the Ozama River mouth underscores the importance of targeted management in this critical pollution source area. Satellite-based approaches offer valuable, timely information to support plastic pollution mitigation in vulnerable coastal environments.

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Marine plastic pollution, Remote sensing, Machine learning classification, Santo Domingo coastline

Assessment of Microplastics Particles Composition in Raw and Treated Wastewater and River Water

Małgorzata Komorowska-Kaufman¹, Katarzyna Jaszczyszyn^{1,2}, Edyta Kiedrzyńska^{2,3}

¹ Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Energy, Poznan, Poland,

² European Regional Centre for Ecohydrology of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Lodz, Poland

³ University of Lodz, Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, UNESCO Chair on Ecohydrology and Applied Ecology, Poland

malgorzata.komorowska-kaufman@put.poznan.pl

Background & Objectives: The presence of microplastics (MPs) in the environment in recent decades has become a significant issue, especially because their toxic impact on living organisms has been documented. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are considered as one of the main point sources of this pollution, thus increasing MPs removal during wastewater treatment is crucial. This research aimed to determine the quantity and quality of MPs found in typical urban wastewater at various treatment stages and in the receiver (river).

Methods: Wastewater samples were collected at the inlet, after mechanical treatment, and after biological treatment at the urban WWTP (PE 45,000) situated in central Poland. River water samples were collected in the river stream, approximately 21 km downstream from the treated wastewater discharge, in the center of a large city. Following appropriate sample preparation, analysis using micro-FTIR spectroscopy (Thermo Scientific Nicolet iN10) was performed.

Results: Raw wastewater contained the higher amount of particles of varying shapes, chemical composition, and colors. The quantity of particles diminished in the treated wastewater and the particle morphology also changed, with gray fibers predominating. MPs particle removal efficiency within the tested particle size range (>20 µm) was very high (98-99%). A greater variety of particles was found in the river water compared to the wastewater treatment plant effluent.

Conclusions: Properly operated WWTPs can effectively eliminate substantial amounts of microplastics. The mechanism of this removal is varied, partially it is based on MPs degradation and fragmentation, which may increase the number of particles not detected by the selected analytical approach, specifically those under 20 µm. Although WWTPs are known and controllable source of microplastics, it is also important to identify and reduce uncontrolled sources of this contamination.

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Microplastics, FTIR spectroscopy, Wastewater, River water

Avoidance behavior of *Lumbricus terrestris* (*Oligochaeta: Lumbricidae*) induced by polyethylene microplastics

Ana Lazić¹, Milica Baloš², Aleksandra Petrović¹, Ivana Ivanović¹, Vojislava Bursić¹, Dejan Prvulović¹, Aleksandra Tubić³

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Environmental and Plant Protection, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

²Agrounik d.o.o., Zemun, Republic of Serbia

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

aleksandra.petrovic@polj.edu.rs

Background & Objectives: The widespread presence of microplastics in terrestrial ecosystems, especially agricultural soils, has raised growing concerns regarding their potential ecological effects, not only on plants and soil-dwelling invertebrates such as earthworms, but also human health. *Lumbricus terrestris* (*Oligochaeta: Lumbricidae*), a well-recognized bioindicator model in soil ecotoxicological researches, contributes significantly to soil aeration and nutrient cycling, making it suitable for assessing microplastic-related impacts. The aim of this study was to investigate how polyethylene microplastic particles affect the avoidance behavior of adult *L. terrestris*.

Methods: A four-compartment soil avoidance assay was conducted; following the SRPS EN ISO 17512-1 standard, with avoidance responses quantified using the avoidance coefficient.

Results: The results showed the greatest avoidance response (53.17%) at a concentration of 0.75% microplastic mixed into 200 g of soil, which also corresponded with the highest observed mortality rate (10%). Applied analysis of variance confirmed a statistically significant behavioral response between control and treated plots ($p=0.000000$, for $p < 0.01$), although no significant differences were detected among the tested concentrations (0.25%, 0.5%, and 0.75% w/w; $p=0.931227$ for $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: These findings suggest that microplastics in soil can elicit strong avoidance behavior and elevate mortality in *L. terrestris*, potentially impairing soil functionality. Furthermore, the obtained results emphasize the ecological relevance of standardized tests as an early warning indicator of soil contamination. The observed effects underline the potential threat microplastics pose to soil biodiversity and ecosystem stability, reinforcing the need for further research into their long-term environmental consequences as well as for human health.

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Microplastics, Lumbricus terrestris, Earthworm bioindicators, Avoidance behavior, Soil

Degradation Dynamics of Conventional and Biodegradable Mulch Films in Agricultural Soils

Skaistė Dreskinienė¹, Karolina Barčauskaitė¹, Monika Vilkienė¹

¹ Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry, Institute of Agriculture, Lithuania

skaiste.dreskiniene@lammc.lt

Background & Objectives: Plastic mulch films are widely used in agriculture, but their persistence in soils leads to concerns over environmental pollution. Conventional polymers such as polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) degrade very slowly, whereas biodegradable films are promoted as more sustainable alternatives. However, their actual degradation under field conditions remains insufficiently understood. This study aimed to evaluate the degradation dynamics of PP, PE, and biodegradable films over one year under different soil environments and burial depths, focusing on chemical changes and microplastic formation. **Background & Objectives:** Briefly introduce the problem and research goals.

Methods: A field experiment was conducted in two distinct locations differing in soil characteristics. Samples of PP, PE, and biodegradable mulch films were buried at two depths (10 cm and 30 cm) and retrieved after 6 and 12 months. Attenuated Total Reflectance–Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) was applied to assess chemical changes in polymer structure. Film surface integrity and evidence of microplastic fragmentation were examined to evaluate degradation progress.

Results: The results showed that degradation strongly depended on polymer type, burial depth, and environmental conditions. Biodegradable films exhibited clear structural changes and surface damage, particularly at 10 cm depth, while PP and PE showed only minor chemical modifications and limited microplastic formation.

Conclusions: The findings confirm that conventional polymers (PP and PE) persist with minimal degradation over one year, contributing to microplastic generation, while biodegradable films degrade more extensively under field conditions. These results highlight the importance of long-term field testing to assess the environmental sustainability of agricultural plastic films and their role in soil microplastic pollution.

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Polypropylene, Polyethylene, Field degradation

Biodegradable plastic mulch performance and degradation in real field conditions, case Slovenia

Kristina Ugrinovič¹, Karin Hriberšek², Mojca Bavcon Kralj²

¹Agricultural Institute of Slovenia, Hacquetova ulica 17, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

²University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Health Sciences, Zdravstvena pot 5, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

kristina.ugrinovic@kis.si

Background & Objectives: Biodegradable (BD) plastic mulch films (MF) are designed to be tilled into the agricultural soil after the crop harvest, and native microorganisms are expected to break down and use the mulch polymers [1]. They are aimed to avoid waste generation and reduce time and cost in collecting and managing plastic fragments [2] associated with the conventional, low density polyethylene-based (LDPE) MF. Only few studies report of complete biodegradation of BD plastic MF. Therefore, it is very likely that most of the undegraded material is fragmented into micro and nano plastics (MNPs) [3]. Besides, the tilling of BD MF into the soil, to facilitate biodegradation, is an open door to potential environmental impacts [2]. With our studies we aim to assess the degradation/accumulation dynamics of BD MF in soil at continuous use under the real field conditions and their impact on crops and soil in a long term.

Methods: Long term field trial in vegetable rotation with 4 commercially available BD MF (2 made from thermoplastic starch (TPS) and 2 from combination of polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) and polylactic acid (PLA) along with standard LDPE film and uncovered control are set at two agroclimatic regions of Slovenia on two soil types since 2022. Beside MF and crops performance the influence of films on soil properties and on the formation of (BD) microplastics is monitored through soil sampling and further plastic extraction.

Results: The BD MF are (in most cases) slightly less effective at weed suppressing than LDPE film. The early development of plants is the fastest on the LDPE. First attempt to determine the plastic MF fragments in soil samples proved challenging, anyhow highest mass of plastic fragments was determined in the group of films composed of TPS, followed by PBAT/PLA, and finally LDPE.

Conclusions: Studying of the formation of (BD) plastic fragments and their degradation in real field conditions on a long term is crucial for evaluating their impact on the environment as well as on agricultural production. Several challenges still need to be addressed.

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Agricultural film, Microplastics, Soil, TPS, PLA, PBAT

Early Plasticrust Formation and Rock–Plastic Interaction Risks in a Caribbean Coastal Zone (Santo Domingo)

Gurusamy Kutralam-Muniasamy¹, V.C. Shruti², Fermín Pérez-Guevara², Ricardo Cuenca Alvarez¹

¹CIITEC - IPN. Centro de Investigación e Innovación Tecnológica. Cda. de Cecati s/n, Santa Catarina, Azcapotzalco, 02250 Ciudad de México, México

²Department of Biotechnology and Bioengineering, Centro de Investigación y de Estudios Avanzados del Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Av Instituto Politécnico Nacional 2508, San Pedro Zacatenco, Gustavo A. Madero, 07360, Ciudad de México, México

mgurusamy@cinvestav.mx

Background & Objectives: Plastic–geological interactions represent an emerging frontier in marine pollution research. While reports of plasticrusts and related formations highlight the capacity of plastics to adhere to rocky substrates, systematic methods to quantify the extent and dynamics of such interactions remain lacking. No study to date has established standardized indices for assessing the morphology and risk potential of plastic–rock composites. This study addresses that gap by documenting and characterizing plastic–rock interactions along the Santo Domingo coastline, Dominican Republic, where no prior evidence exists.

Methods: High-resolution photographs of rock–plastic interactions were processed using four novel indices developed in this study. The Plastic Interaction Index (PII) quantified coverage of plastics on rock surfaces, the Surface Exposure Risk Index (SERI) measured the elevation and roughness of plastic fragments relative to the substrate, and the Morphoplastic Risk Density (MPRD) captured the density of contact points. These were synthesized into a composite Hazard Score. Morphometric features (area, perimeter, compactness, circularity) were extracted, and dynamic interaction zones were mapped through density and clustering analysis.

Results: Quantitative analysis confirmed plastic fragments were tightly embedded in calcareous rock pores, forming persistent plasticrusts. Strong morphometric correlation ($r = 0.97$) indicated microtopographical control, with preferential entrapment on irregular surfaces. Indices (PII, SERI, MPRD) revealed heterogeneous adhesion and clustering in erosion-prone zones. Integration produced a hazard map identifying risk hotspots amplified by wave action, providing a predictive framework for classifying plastic–rock interaction strength and environmental risk.

Conclusions: This work provides the first quantitative evidence of plastic–rock composites in the Caribbean. By introducing a standardized index framework, it establishes a foundation for future monitoring of plastic–substrate interactions, advancing understanding of how coastal geology mediates plastic persistence and ecological risk.

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Plastic–rock interactions, Hazard risk indices, Geological interfaces, Environmental plastics, Microplastic clustering, Interaction zones

Ecological Footprint of Livestock Farming: Microplastic Contamination in Agricultural Soil and Water

Suzana Knežević¹, Milena Milojević¹, Aleksandra Milošević²

¹Academy of Applied Studies Šabac, Unit for Agricultural and Business Studies and Tourism, Šabac, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Faculty of Law, Belgrade, Serbia

s.knezevic@akademijasabac.edu.rs

Background & Objectives: Microplastic pollution has emerged as a significant environmental concern, increasingly recognized in agricultural soils and waters. Livestock farming has been identified as a potential source of microplastics, primarily through the application of manure containing synthetic residues. Additionally, certain veterinary pharmaceuticals used on farms have been found to contain microplastic particles, contributing to environmental load. This review explores the extent to which livestock-related activities contribute to microplastic contamination and their impact on the ecological footprint of agroecosystems.

Methods: A systematic review of peer-reviewed literature published between 2015 and 2025 was conducted. The selection criteria focused on studies reporting microplastic presence in animal manure, agricultural soils, and drainage water. Emphasis was placed on identifying pathways of microplastic movement and accumulation resulting from livestock farming practices.

Results: Studies indicate that continuous application of pig manure leads to significantly elevated levels of microplastics in soils—rising from baseline concentrations of ~16 particles/kg to over 40 particles/kg in treated fields [1]. In specific agricultural zones, concentrations in raw manure have reached up to 88,000 particles/kg [2]. Evidence suggests horizontal transport from treated soils to adjacent fields, and vertical migration into drainage systems, confirming their mobility beyond initial application zones [3].

Conclusions: Livestock farming contributes notably to the introduction and spread of microplastics in agroecosystems, exacerbating environmental degradation through soil and water contamination. The presence of microplastics in veterinary drugs represents an additional, often overlooked pathway. Effective management of manure, pharmaceuticals, and plastic waste in agriculture is essential to mitigate ecological impact and promote sustainability.

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Microplastics, Livestock farming, Agricultural soil, Water pollution, Ecological footprint

Harnessing Mushroom Waste for Green Synthesis of ZnO Nanoparticles: A Sustainable Route Toward Soil Microplastic Remediation

Alok Ranjan Kerketta¹, Martin Šebesta¹

¹Comenius University Bratislava, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Institute of Laboratory Research on Geomaterials, Mlynská dolina, Ilkovičova 6, 842 15 Bratislava, Slovak republic

kerketal@uniba.sk

Background & Objectives: The escalating presence of microplastics in terrestrial environments poses severe threats to soil health, ecological balance, and food security. Green synthesis of metal oxide nanomaterials utilizing plant-based, microbial, or biogenic processes offers a sustainable strategy to address these emerging pollutants while minimizing the environmental footprint of nanomaterial production. Recent evidence demonstrates the efficacy of green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles in microplastic degradation. Vas et al. [1] (2024) reported that ZnO nanoparticles synthesized using Piper longum leaf extract achieved maximum microplastic degradation at 100 µg/mL concentration under UV irradiation. Similarly, Tofa et al. [2] (2019) demonstrated 30% increase in carbonyl index of low-density polyethylene microplastics using ZnO nanorods under visible light, indicating effective photocatalytic breakdown. However, limited research has explored sustainable nanomaterial-based remediation strategies that can effectively address microplastic pollution while maintaining soil ecological integrity.

Methods: In this study, zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were synthesized via a green route using NaOH as the reducing agent and spent substrate extracts from Pleurotus mushrooms as the stabilizing and capping agents. The formation of ZnO nanoparticles was confirmed by UV-visible spectroscopy, which exhibited a characteristic absorption peak at approximately 370 nm within the 200–800 nm spectral range. The successful formation of ZnO nanoparticles was confirmed by UV-visible spectroscopy, which revealed a distinctive absorption peak at around 370 nm in the 200–800 nm range. We will further characterize these nanoparticles using SEM and TEM to elucidate their morphology and size distribution.

Conclusions: Future work will focus on testing their photocatalytic potential for degrading microplastics and investigating how they influence the uptake of toxic elements by plants. This approach valorizes mushroom cultivation waste, providing a cost-effective and widely available feedstock for environmentally benign nanoparticle production without yet assessing their efficacy in microplastic degradation.

Acknowledgments: The article was supported by the Scientific Grant Agency of the Ministry of Education, Research, Development and Youth of the Slovak Republic and the Slovak Academy of Sciences under contract No. VEGA 1/0331/23: 'Innovative approaches to the methodological study of the properties of inorganic nanoparticles during their biosynthesis and transformation and other aspects of behaviour in the soil-plant model system using LA-ICP-MS, Mössbauer spectroscopy and other spectrometric methods

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Green synthesis, Zinc oxide nanoparticles, Sustainable nanomaterials, Microplastic remediation, Photocatalysis, Environmental nanotechnology

Identification of microplastic particles in water supply system of Rogoźno (Greater Poland Voivodeship, Poland)

Agnieszka Szuster-Janiaczyk¹, Beata Mądrecka-Witkowska¹, Aleksandra Dajema¹, Karolina Olszewska², Tomasz Runka²

¹Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Energy, Poznan, Poland

²Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Materials Science and Technical Physics, Poznan, Poland

beata.madrecka@put.poznan.pl

Background & Objectives: Synthetic polymers are widely used in the production of pipes for water supply systems (WSS). Polyvinyl chloride and polyethylene are common materials in Polish WSS. These substances can be potentially released to drinking water as a result of degradation, leaching, aging etc. The aim of this research was to investigate the presence of microplastic in WSS in the urban-rural commune of Rogoźno (Greater Poland Voivodeship, Poland).

Methods: The water supply network is approximately 387.3 km long and consists primarily of PVC pipes. Water samples were collected at the water treatment plant (raw water, after 1st and 2nd stage of filtration, and after disinfection) and at five points in the water supply network. For each water sample, a volume of 5 liters was filtered through 0.45µm nylon filters. Microplastic were identified with the use of Raman spectrometer.

Results: Microplastic were detected at all sampling points. The exception was the raw water, which was difficult to analyze due to the significant suspended solids content. The number of detected particles was very low (max. 3 particles per 5-liter sample). Their size was in the range of 4-256µm. Amorphous carbon, cellulose, iron oxide and other types of particles were also observed.

Conclusions: The detection of microplastic confirms the possibility of its migration from the studied WSS. As the knowledge about the influence of microplastic on human health is still insufficient, extensive monitoring of microplastic in drinking water should be performed. In order to conduct valuable scientific research, there is a significant need to develop a detailed analysis methodology.

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Drinking water, Microplastic, Water supply system, Raman spectroscopy

Microplastics assessments in Moroccan Mediterranean Mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Callista chione*)

Mostapha Benomar¹, Yosra Ajbar², Soumaya Terresti², Chafiq Lahcen³

¹Regional centre of National Institute of Fisheries Research, Tangier, Morocco

² Faculty of Science and Technology, Abdelmalek Essaâdi University, Tangier, Morocco.

³Regional centre of National Institute of Fisheries Research, Nador, Morocco

benomar@inrh.ma

Background & Objectives: The Moroccan Mediterranean Sea holds considerable economical potential across multiple sectors, including tourism, fishing, and marine transportation. Nevertheless, other external factors adversely impact this marine, including pollution from plastic debris, including microplastics.

Methods: Bivalve mollusks were collected from the Moroccan Mediterranean in 2025 to evaluate this contamination. In this sense, seven sampling locations were developed to encompass the whole coastline: Kabila, M'diq, Oued Laou, Cala Iris, Torres, Ras El Ma, and Saida. The species collected from the western Mediterranean were varnish shells (*Callista chione*), whereas the species from the eastern Mediterranean were mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*). The factors examined for these microplastics include size, color, form, and others.

Results: The abundance of microplastics per individual varies across the studied sites: Kabila (9.43 items/individual), M'diq (4.92 items/individual), Oued Laou (13.3 items/individual), Rass El Ma (17.83 items/individual), Saidia (4.08 items/individual), and Torres (14.2 items/individual). The microplastics identified exhibit colors including transparent, blue, brown, red, black, and green, with a predominance of transparent plastics. The predominant forms are fibers and fragments, with diameters of the studied microplastics ranging from 250 µm to 1 µm.

Microplastics, Moroccan Mediterranean sea, Mussels, Assessment

Impact of plastic mulching and road proximity on microplastic pollution in agricultural soils: Insights into weathering characteristics, elemental association, and ecological risk

Jayant Karwadiya¹, Alok Ranjan Kerketta¹, Saurabh Pathak², Sudhakar Srivastava², Gopala Krishna Darbha¹

¹Environmental Nanoscience Laboratory, Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Kolkata, Mohanpur, West Bengal, India, 741246

²Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India, 221005

jayantkarwadiya@mail.com

Background & Objectives: Plastics have become an inseparable part of modern farming and is being used in mulches, greenhouses, and other practices that boost crop productivity. Yet, this convenience comes with a hidden cost leading to accumulation of residual plastics in agricultural soils. While studies on this issue are emerging, we still know little about how everyday farming choices, like using mulch or farming near busy roads, shape the distribution of macroplastics (MaPs) and microplastics (MPs) in soils, especially in regions such as India. Hence, we assessed plastic contamination across 22 sites in six districts of Bihar, which revealed mean MaP concentrations of 7.5 ± 3.6 particles kg^{-1} soil (d.w.) and MP abundance ranging from 150 to 1460 particles kg^{-1} soil.

Methods: MP concentrations were highest in mulched fields near roads (803 ± 371 particles kg^{-1}), followed by distant mulched sites (657 ± 143 particles kg^{-1}). Elevated levels were observed even in unmulched near-road fields (494 ± 327 particles kg^{-1}), while the unmulched, distant fields (335 ± 76 particles kg^{-1}) had the least contamination, indicating a combined influence of agricultural practices and road proximity. ATR-FTIR and μ -Raman analysis revealed four types of MPs (PP > PE > PET > PS), with PE and PP accounting for over 95 % of the total. Weathering assessment via carbonyl index (CI) showed significantly higher values in MPs than MaPs, and field-extracted mulch films exhibited reduced contact angles relative to pristine films, indicating increased surface oxidation and hydrophilicity [2]. Furthermore, multiple heavy metals were found to be associated with the environmental MPs. Based on the MultiMP framework, all field types were classified as high-risk for MPs related impacts.

Conclusions: This study highlights the need for sustainable plastic use in agriculture and calls for targeted policy measures to prevent long-term soil contamination and ecological harm.

Fig 1. Graphical abstract

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Microplastics, Soils, Mulching, Weathering, Heavy metals, Carbonyl index

Microplastics Contamination in Aquatic Ecosystems: Challenges in Extraction and Ecological Risk Assessment

Marijana Nikolić¹, Aleksandra Tubić², Marija Jakovljević¹, Branko Kordić², Branislav Jović², Vladica Simić¹

¹University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Science, Department of Biology and Ecology, Kragujevac, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Science, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

marijana.nikolic@pmf.kg.ac.rs

Background & Objectives: Microplastics (MPs) contamination is a growing environmental concern, originating from diverse sources such as municipal solid waste landfills, plastic packaging, road runoff, and agricultural activities. Once in the environment, plastic degrades into micro- and nanoplastics, which interact with organic matter and pollutants, complicating their extraction and analysis. Understanding these interactions is crucial for assessing the ecological risks of MPs and their role as pollutant vectors. Riverine MPs pollution has been extensively studied for over a decade, with research focused on quantification and characterization. As particle size decreases, MPs become more bioavailable, increasing the risk of uptake by lower trophic levels. MPs act as carriers for pollutants from the aqueous phase and release chemical additives upon ingestion, raising concerns about their potential toxicity.

Methods: A major challenge in MPs research is the extraction of particles from complex organic matrices. The choice of methods must balance efficiency with minimal damage to MPs structure. Visual sorting remains a key step before chemical digestion. Sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) has proven effective in processing benthopelagic fish samples, specifically the common bleak (*Alburnus alburnus*), preserving the integrity of MP particles while successfully digesting organic matter.

Conclusions: Despite the ubiquity of MPs in aquatic environments—detected across species and throughout the water column—methodological inconsistencies hinder large-scale comparative analyses. To improve reliability, a standardized methodology adapted to different biological materials is necessary for accurate risk assessment and environmental monitoring. This research aims to enhance our understanding of MPs-pollutant interactions and develop robust analytical approaches to evaluate their ecological impact better.

Fig. 1. Filaments found in the stomach content of fish (a) visually identifying; (b) after chemical digestion with NaClO

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Microplastics, Freshwater, Fish, Methodological inconsistencies

Packaging as a Source of Microplastics in the Food Supply Chain: Evidence from Packaged Chicken Meat

Tina Šaula¹, Živa Zidar¹, Sonja Smole Možina¹, Manca Kovač Viršek², Anja Klančnik¹

¹University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical Faculty, Ljubljana, Slovenia

²National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana, Slovenia

tina.saula@bf.uni-lj.si

Background & Objectives: Microplastics (MPs) are increasingly recognised as emerging food safety hazard due to their ubiquitous presence in the environment and their ability to adsorb or transport chemical and biological contaminants. Within food production systems, MPs can originate from various sources, including packaging, potentially accumulating on the food surface. MPs in food represent a possible route of consumer exposure. This study aims to assess the occurrence of MPs on the surface of packaged chicken meat from various producers and packaging types.

Methods: Analyses were performed under sterile and dust-controlled conditions. A 50 g portion was excised from the outer 10 mm of each meat sample surface. Samples were digested in KOH and the resulting suspensions were filtered through filters with the pore size of 10 µm. Suspected MPs were isolated using precision tweezers and examined under a stereomicroscope to determine their size, shape, and colour. Polymer composition was confirmed using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy.

Results: Microplastics were detected in 9 out of 10 analysed meat samples, ranging from 1 to 6 particles per sample. The predominant morphotypes were fibres and films sized between 0.2 and 2.2 mm, most frequently transparent or green, resembling the packaging material. FTIR analysis confirmed polymer correspondence with the packaging in several cases, whereas others differed, indicating possible additional contamination routes during meat processing or handling.

Conclusions: The findings confirm that packaged chicken meat can act as a vector for human exposure to MPs, originating from packaging and other environmental sources. These results emphasize the significance of MPs as potential physical and chemical hazards, and underscore the need for further research into their occurrence, sources, and implications for food safety throughout the supply chain.

Acknowledgments: This research was supported by the Slovenian Research and Innovation Agency (ARIS) under the project MR-58148, J4-4548 and P4-0116.

Microplastics, Chicken meat, Food packaging, Consumer exposure, Food safety

SESSION 3: Impact and risk assessment of microplastics and associated additives

- Toxicological studies on microplastics and chemical additives (e.g., phthalates, PBDEs)
- Effects on soil health, microbial communities, and crop growth
- Human exposure through food chains and potential health impacts
- Risk assessment frameworks for organic-rich environments
- Policy implications and regulatory measures for reducing microplastic impacts

MODERATOR:

Dr. Liam Morrison

Earth and Life Sciences, School of Natural Sciences and Ryan Institute, University of Galway, Ireland

Dr Liam Morrison is a lecturer in Earth and Ocean Sciences at the School of Natural Sciences and the Ryan Institute at University of Galway, Ireland. Dr Morrison is the Course Director and Academic Coordinator for the MSc in Marine and Freshwater Resources: Management (1MFR1) at the University of Galway and Academic) and is Deputy Director of the Ryan Institute's Centre for One Health (COH).

Research interests include: presence, speciation and bioavailability of toxic and essential trace elements and organic contaminants in marine, freshwater and terrestrial ecosystems; obtaining data to support policy on environmental protection; characterisation and removal of engineered nanomaterials (ENMs) in water and biological systems; development and application of analytical and chemical methods for studying the presence of microplastics in biotic and abiotic systems; nutrient dynamics and eco-physiology of opportunistic macroalgal blooms (including invasive species) in estuaries and coastal bays in order to understand the mechanisms behind macroalgal blooms in order to develop management tools to control their size; application of remote sensing techniques in the spatial and temporal determination of macroalgal blooms; nature based solution and marine ecological restoration; marine radioactivity; and sustainable development of marine resources in the context of global change.

KEYNOTE SPEAKER:

Prof. Jacob de Boer

Emeritus professor, Editor-in-Chief Chemosphere, Faculty of Science, Environmental Health & Toxicology, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

Prof. Dr Jacob de Boer is emeritus Professor of Environmental Chemistry and Toxicology at the Faculty of Science, Vrije University Amsterdam, The Netherlands. He obtained a PhD in analytical chemistry at the Vrije Universiteit in 1995. Prof. De Boer has worked for 50 years on the environmental contamination and analysis of persistent, bioaccumulating and toxic substances such as polychlorinated biphenyls, flame retardants, perfluorinated compounds, and other contaminants. He started his career in 1974 at the Netherlands Institute for Fisheries Research. In 2005 he was appointed as endowed professor at the Wageningen University, the Netherlands, after which in 2006 he moved as full professor to the Vrije University in Amsterdam. From 2012-2015 he was director of the Institute for Environmental Studies (IVM) at that same university, and from 2015-2022 head of the Department of Environment and Health.

In 1998 he won the Excellent Scientist Award of the Wageningen University. He co-authored one of the most cited papers in *Chemosphere* (2010, 88, 1119–1153), with more than 2000 citations. In 2015 he was honoured as one of the highly cited scientists in his field (Top 1%) according to Thomson & Reuter.

He was advisor for the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP), and a member of the European Scientific Advisory Panel of the CEFIC Long Range Initiative. In 2013 he was appointed by the Chinese government for five years as National Expert for China under the 1000-talents plan. He has (co)coordinated a large number of European research projects, and many research projects for other international organisations and industries. He advised the Belgian government on public health in relation with a large PFAS pollution in Flanders. He organised numerous international interlaboratory studies on contaminants. He is regularly consulted by lawyers for advice in lawsuits on PFAS or other contaminants. In 2023 he was appointed by the Dutch Minister for the Environment as expert for monitoring the health related to the steel industry in the Amsterdam harbour. He is a regular reviewer of scientific projects and programmes in various countries. He is a regular guest in TV and radio programs in the Netherlands and abroad.

He has published more than 250 peer reviewed articles, among which one paper in *Nature* and one in *Science*, two books and 22 book chapters. His H-index is 65. He is editor-in-chief of *Chemosphere* and member of the editorial board of the *Handbook of Environmental Chemistry*.

Discharge of microplastics from sewers to oceans showing the huge dimensions of plastic pollution in India

C. Rathore^{a,b}, M. Saha^{a,b}, J. de Boer^c, A. Desai^{a,b}, P. Gupta^{a,b}, A. Naik^a, H. Y. Subha^{a,d}

^a CSIR-National Institute of Oceanography, Dona Paula, Goa 403 004, India

^b Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad 201002, India

^c Vrije University, De Boelelaan 1085, 1081 HV Amsterdam, the Netherlands

^d Department of Marine Chemistry, Kerala University of Fisheries and Ocean Studies, Kochi 682506, India

Owing to their pervasive dispersion in the environment and their potential ramifications on both marine life and human health, microplastics (MPs) are of increasing concern. However, there is still a lack of research on the release of MPs from different land-based pathways like creeks, drainage outfalls, and conduits into coastal water systems in India. This study represents comprehensive research into the attribution of MPs in the estuarine system, specifically those emanating from wastewater sources in Panjim City, Goa, India. Urban wastewater collected from different locations in and around Panjim City exhibited values ranging from 79 ± 21 to 338 ± 7 MPs/L, with a prevalence of fibrous and black MP particles. The size range of the MPs at all sampling sites was 100–300 μm . Analysis by $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ revealed 35 distinct polymeric compositions in wastewater, with a dominance of polyacrylamide (PAM), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), and polyamide (PA). Additionally, primary and secondary MPs were studied to unravel the contributions from land-based sources. This included the quantification of MPs in ten samples from personal care products (PCPs) and twenty samples from washing machine effluents (WMEs). MPs in PCPs ranged from 1.8 to 1554 MPs/g. Microfibres and fragments were predominant in WMEs (3986 to 4898 MPs/L). This study suggests a strong relation between polymers found in wastewater effluent and those present in PCPs and WMEs.

Diversifying Available Micro- and Nanoplastic Reference Particles: Model Studies with Polylactic Acid

Jessica Caldwell¹, Matilda Porro^{1,2}, Athanassia Athanassiou¹, Despina Fragouli¹

¹Smart Materials, Italian Institute of Technology (IIT), Via Morego 30, 16163 Genoa, Italy

²Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences (DISAT), University of Milano-Bicocca, Piazza della Scienza 1, 20126 Milan, Italy

jessica.caldwell@iit.it

Background & Objectives: A rapidly expanding body of literature exists which highlights the potential hazards of plastic-based products after they have entered the natural environment. A chief concern is the formation of smaller fragments of these bulk plastic products, known as microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs), which are documented to be more bioavailable than their larger macroplastic counterparts. To assess whether these MPs and NPs pose a threat to the flora and fauna present in contaminated environments, our research group has developed multiple methods for the creation of reference particle systems, with a specific focus on creating test models for biopolymer-based plastic materials that are potential candidates for replacing conventional petroleum-based plastic products.

Methods: Polylactic acid (PLA) pellets from NatureWorks (4043D) were purchased and utilized to create NPs via either sequential milling (a two-step, top-down methodology) or solubilized in a solvent for nanoprecipitation with a confined impinging jet mixer. Milling is used for creation of a broader range of particle sizes (from several hundreds of micron to a few hundred nanometers), while nanoprecipitation is employed to create spherical nanoparticles and is conducted with or without the presence of fluorescent labels or inorganic tracers (i.e., gold nanoparticles).

Conclusions: PLA particles with sizes from the micro- to nano- range were successfully created from the same starting plastic pellets. The particles could be tuned through selection of the optimum processing protocol. Particle shapes, presence or absence of labels, and the final particle size dispersions obtained were all demonstrated to be modifiable. Thus, the final reference particle system can be adapted to suit the subsequent experimental work, with the possibility to incorporate labels within the particles potentially facilitating their tracking in complex sample matrices.

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Biopolymers, Model particles, Fluorescence, Inorganic tracers

Evaluation of potential risk of micro and nano plastics in agricultural soils through territorial analysis

Ali Hachem¹, Fabiana Convertino¹, Evelia Schettini¹, Giuliano Vox¹

¹ Department of Soil, Plant and Food Sciences, University of Bari, via Amendola 165/a, 70126 Bari, Italy

fabiana.convertino@uniba.it

Background & Objectives: The widespread use of plastic products in agriculture has improved productivity but has also resulted in the accumulation of agricultural plastic waste (APW) due to its mismanagement and continuous degradation, posing significant environmental concern. A particularly urgent issue is the potential release of micro- and nano-plastics (MNPs) from agricultural plastics into soils, resulting in impacts that are still understudied. This study presents a spatially integrated approach to assess the potential risk of soil contamination by MNPs due to plastic use in agriculture across European regions.

Methods: Data on APW generation per plastic application and crop type were estimated using plastic waste indices. Along with the estimations, an additional step was also performed by combining them with relative risk indices that reflect the likelihood of MNPs release from plastic applications. The outcome was a semi-quantitative Agricultural Plastic Pollution Risk Index (APPRI) that shows the most vulnerable regions, and it was properly visualized through a geographic information system.

Results: Results reveal that regions in southern Europe, particularly Andalusia (Spain), Puglia and Sicily (Italy), show the highest risk levels while most regions in Northern Europe were with a minimal risk compared to those in the South.

Conclusions: The APPRI approach enables a comparative evaluation of plastic pollution risk by MNPs based on both quantity and hazard potential of APW. This approach offers a practical baseline to support targeted monitoring and mitigation strategies. It also emphasizes the need for harmonized metrics and region-specific interventions to reduce MNP input into agricultural soils and aligns with broader sustainability goals related to soil health and circular economy principles. It is a step further that allows for a better assessment and understanding of the extent of MNPs pollution of agricultural soils.

Agricultural plastic, Plastic pollution, Microplastics, Waste mapping, Risk assessment

From Rivers to Sludge: Sorption and Fate of Micropollutants Bound to Microplastics during Anaerobic Digestion

Ivan Titov^{1,2}, Michaela Helusová^{1,2}, Jaroslav Semerád¹, Jana Boháčková^{1,2}, Hynek Beneš³, Tomáš Cajtham^{1,2}

¹ Institute of Microbiology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Vídeňská 1083, 142 20 Prague, Czech Republic

² Institute for Environmental Studies, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Benátská 2, 128 01 Prague, Czech Republic

³ Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Heyrovského náměstí 2, 162 06 Prague, Czech Republic

titovi@natur.cuni.cz

Background & Objectives: Microplastics are emerging vectors for organic micropollutants in aquatic and sludge environments. While their sorption behaviour in natural waters has been increasingly studied, little is known about how these pollutants behave once microplastics enter wastewater treatment systems, particularly during anaerobic digestion. This study bridges these two environmental compartments by investigating both the sorption of micropollutants onto microplastics under environmentally relevant river conditions in the vicinity of a wastewater treatment plant effluent and their fate during anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge.

Methods: Microplastics of various polymer types (LDPE, PET, PVC) were placed in a Central European river and characterized for adsorbed micropollutants using chromatographic and spectroscopic techniques. Parallel laboratory experiments simulate anaerobic digestion of sewage sludge containing known concentrations of microplastics and representative organic pollutants, including pharmaceuticals, pesticides, and endocrine disruptors. The distribution of pollutants between sludge and microplastic surfaces before and after digestion is being evaluated.

Results: Results from the river study showed significant adsorption of selected micropollutants onto aged microplastics, with sorption efficiency influenced by polymer type and surface oxidation. Building upon these findings, ongoing anaerobic digestion experiments aim to evaluate how the presence of microplastics affects the degradation and redistribution of these pollutants in sewage sludge. It is hypothesized that compounds sorbed to microplastics may display different degradation behaviour compared to those bound to organic matter, potentially influencing the persistence and mobility of micropollutants during sludge stabilization.

Conclusions: By linking field and laboratory studies, this research provides a novel view on the environmental fate of microplastics-associated pollutants across aquatic and engineered systems. Understanding these interactions is essential for assessing the risk of pollutant recycling through sludge reuse and for developing mitigation strategies within the circular economy framework.

Microplastics, Micropollutants, Sorption, Anaerobic digestion, Sewage sludge

From soil to stream: Experimental evidence of microplastic bioaccumulation in amphibians via trophic transfer

Glorija Ćirković¹, Tanja Trakić¹, Filip Popović¹, Rastko Ajtić¹

¹University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Science, Department of Biology and Ecology, Radoja Domanovića 12, 34000 Kragujevac, Serbia

glorija.cirkovic@pmf.kg.ac.rs

Background & Objectives: Microplastic pollution represents an increasing risk to freshwater ecosystems [1,2]; however, its trophic transfer and impacts on amphibians are still inadequately studied. This research examines the consumption and possible effects of microplastics on 20 individuals of *Pelophylax kl. esculentus* (Linnaeus, 1758) that were fed with *Eisenia fetida* (Savigny, 1826) previously exposed to microplastic particles.

Methods: Earthworms were exposed to environmentally relevant concentrations of microplastics and subsequently provided as prey to frogs over a defined period. Post-exposure analyses involved dissection and microscopic examination to identify microplastic presence in gastrointestinal tracts, alongside the evaluation of potential sublethal effects, including weight changes, behavioral alterations, and gut morphology.

Conclusions: The findings validated the transfer of microplastics within the food chain, illustrating trophic uptake from contaminated prey to amphibian predators. This study emphasizes the ability of microplastics to traverse trophic levels and underscores concerns regarding their accumulation and biological impacts on amphibians. The findings enhance the understanding of the impact of plastic pollutants on freshwater food webs and underscore the necessity of monitoring microplastic pathways at terrestrial-aquatic interfaces.

Acknowledgments: This work was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia No. 451-03-137/2025-03/200122.

[1] E Souza-Ferreira, M. L. C. et al. (2025) 'First record of microplastic contamination in adult endemic amazonian anuran species', *Scientific Reports*, Issue 15(1). doi: 10.1038/s41598-025-86434-9,

[2] Hu, L. et al. (2018) 'Microplastics in small waterbodies and tadpoles from Yangtze River Delta, China', *Environmental Science & Technology*, Issue 52, p. 8885-8893. doi: 10.1021/acs.est.8b02279

Pelophylax kl. esculentus, Eisenia fetida, Microplastics, Food chains

Oxidative DNA Damage and Tissue Inflammation Induced by PET and PP Microplastics and Their Additive Dibutyl Phthalate: Comparative In Vivo Assessment

Rosari Asty¹, Shafa Alayda Rachmah¹, Kezia Aurellia¹, Noverra Mardhatillah Nizardo¹, Budiawan¹

¹Universitas Indonesia, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Depok, Indonesia

rosari.asty51@ui.ac.id

Background & Objectives: Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polypropylene (PP) are widely used polymers that can degrade into microplastics (MPs) capable of carrying additive compounds such as dibutyl phthalate (DBP). These substances may induce oxidative stress and DNA damage in biological systems. This study aimed to compare the toxicological effects of PET and PP MPs and their additive DBP on oxidative DNA damage and tissue inflammation.

Methods: Male *Rattus norvegicus* were orally exposed for 28 days to PET or PP MPs (5 mg/day), DBP (50 mg/kg BW/day), and their combination. Serum 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) levels were measured by ELISA, and histopathological changes in liver, kidney, intestine, and stomach were analyzed by hematoxylin-eosin staining.

Results: Single exposure to PET and PP MPs significantly increased 8-OHdG concentrations (PET: 35.02 ng/mL vs. control: 11.96 ng/mL), accompanied by moderate to hepatic periportal and intestinal inflammation. The combination with DBP resulted in lower oxidative damage and inflammation, suggesting antagonistic interactions due to π - π adsorption of DBP onto polymer surfaces, reducing bioavailability [1].

Conclusions: PET and PP MPs exert stronger oxidative and inflammatory toxicity than DBP, while co-exposure attenuates these effects through physicochemical interactions. These findings emphasize the need for integrated risk assessments considering both polymeric matrices and their additives in evaluating human health risks from chronic microplastic exposure.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia through the PMDSU scholarship, Grant No. 571/UN2.RST/HKP05.00/2025.

[1] Z. Li et al., "Acute and chronic combined effect of polystyrene microplastics and dibutyl phthalate on the marine copepod *Tigriopus japonicus*," *Chemosphere*, vol. 261, p. 127711, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.127711.

Microplastics, PET, PP, Dibutyl phthalate, Oxidative DNA damage, Risk assessment

Time-resolved colonization patterns of bacteria and fungi on polystyrene microplastics in floodplain soils

Rizwan Khaleel¹, Julian Wagenhofer², Markus Rolf¹, Yifan Lu¹, Hannes Laermanns¹, Alfons Weig³, Frank Nitsche², Tillmann Lüders⁴, Claus Bässler⁵, Christian Laforsch⁶, Martin G.J. Löder⁶, Christina Bogner¹

¹Ecosystem Research, Institute of Geography, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, University of Cologne, Zùlpicher Straße 45, 50674 Cologne, Germany

²General Ecology, Institute of Zoology, University of Cologne, 50674 Cologne, Germany

³Keylab Genomanalytik & Bioinformatik, BayCEER, University of Bayreuth, 95440 Bayreuth, Germany

⁴Ecological Microbiology, BayCEER, University of Bayreuth, 95440 Bayreuth, Germany

⁵Fungal Ecology and BayCEER, University of Bayreuth, 95440 Bayreuth, Germany

⁶Animal Ecology I, BayCEER, University of Bayreuth, 95440 Bayreuth, Germany

khaleel.rizwan@uni-koeln.de, christina.bogner@uni-koeln.de

Background & Objectives: Microplastic (MP) contamination in terrestrial ecosystems is an emerging issue, but our understanding of how soil microbes interact with MPs remains limited. While many studies have examined how MPs affect soil organisms, less attention has been given to how soil biota, particularly microbial biofilms, influence MPs in soils.

Methods: This study investigates time-resolved colonization patterns of bacterial and fungal communities on polystyrene (PS) MPs incubated in floodplain soil under both controlled laboratory and natural conditions over 4, 8, and 16 weeks. Using scanning electron microscopy and biofilm assays, we observed progressive biofilm formation on MPs.

Results: We found higher biomass on MPs under laboratory conditions compared to natural incubation. With metabarcoding (16S rRNA for bacteria and ITS1 for fungi) techniques on MP biofilm, we identified bacterial communities that showed distinct temporal and environmental variation, with Acidobacteriota and Proteobacteria dominating and shifting depending on incubation conditions. In contrast, fungal communities, primarily Ascomycota and Basidiomycota, remained more stable in composition across both conditions over time. Genera with known PS degradation potential, such as *Pseudomonas*, *Bacillus*, and *Penicillium*, were also detected, suggesting microbial involvement in potential MP breakdown.

Conclusions: Our findings highlight that natural conditions promote more dynamic microbial succession, emphasizing the importance of in situ studies to better reflect environmental realities. This work provides foundational insights into MP – microbe interactions in soils, particularly focusing on bacterial and fungal communities. The study also underscores the need to explore a wider range of polymer types and sizes under long-term natural incubation to better characterize microbial colonization patterns and assess the biodegradation potential of soil microbial communities.

Microplastics, Biofilm, Floodplain Soil, Bacteria, Fungi

Exposure to indoor pollutants – volatile organic compounds, phthalates, bisphenol A - in small-cell vs. non-small-cell advanced lung cancer patients

Jana Pavlović¹, Danica Szdanić-Velikić^{2,3}, Mirjana Ševo^{2,4}, Jovan Kulić¹, Maja Milanović², Nataša Milošević², Nataša Milić²

¹University of East Sarajevo, Faculty of Medicine Foča, Foča, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

³Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Clinic for Pulmonary Oncology, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

⁴IMC Banja Luka-Center of Radiotherapy, Part of Affidea Group, Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

jana.stojanovic@ues.rs.ba

Background & Objectives: As lung cancer became the fifth leading cause of cancer-related death among non-smokers, scientific focus shifted to other risk factors, including environmental pollution [1]. This study assessed potential exposure to indoor pollutants: volatile organic compounds (VOCs), phthalates, and bisphenol A (BPA), in newly diagnosed advanced lung cancer patients and compared these exposures between small-cell (SCLC) and non-small-cell (NSCLC) lung cancer types.

Methods: In this study, 205 newly diagnosed patients with IIB/IV stage of either SCLC or NSCLC (111 men vs. 94 women) from Vojvodina, Serbia, were surveyed for selected environmental factors through questionnaire.

Results: Among respondents, 44.9% reported using air fresheners in homes, cars, and offices, 42.9% used deodorants ≥ 3 x/week, while 19.5% applied perfumes daily. Scented laundry detergents, fabric softeners, and household cleaning products were commonly used by 96.1%, 94.6%, and 95.6% of participants, respectively. No significant differences were found between SCLC and NSCLC patients regarding the use of scented products as possible sources of VOC and phthalates. Only 7.3% used organic, fragrance-free alternatives. Men with NSCLC were more frequently exposed to scented cleaning products than women ($p=0.049$), whereas women with NSCLC favored organic, fragrance-free products more often ($p=0.007$). Deodorant use was higher among women across both cancer types ($p\leq 0.006$). Consumption of instant soups and canned foods as probable source of BPA was similar between groups, although men with SCLC used canned foods more than women ($p=0.010$). Most respondents reported never using plastic containers for heating food which was observed as BPA and phthalates source of exposure.

Conclusions: The use of fragranced products was predominantly associated with gender rather than with the cancer type. Our findings also indicate that men more frequently consume canned foods, which are potential sources of endocrine disruptors and warrant further investigation as probable risk factors for lung cancer.

Acknowledgements: This research was funded by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AP Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia, Grant No. 003076431 2024 09418 003 000 000 001.

[1]LoPiccolo, J. et al. (2024). Lung Cancer in Patients Who Have Never Smoked—An Emerging Disease. *Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology*, Issue 21, p. 121-146. doi: 10.1038/s41571-023-00844-0.

Microplastics, Biofilm, Floodplain Soil, Bacteria, Fungi

Microbial community structure in landfill soils: Case study in Serbia

Gordana Racić¹, Igor Vukelić², Nataša Stojić³, Ljiljana Milošević³, Galina Ćurčić³, Jozefien Demeulenaere⁴, Caroline de Tender⁴

¹Research and Development Institute Tamiš d.o.o., Novoseljski put 33, 26000 Pančevo, Serbia

² Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Maksima Gorkog 30, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

³Faculty of Environmental Protection, Educons University, 21208 Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

⁴Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

racic@institut-tamis.rs

Background & Objectives: Microorganisms are vital for soil health and demonstrate an adaptive capacity to environmental change, with their role in plastic biodegradation increasingly recognized. Main purpose of this case study was to analyse bacterial and fungal communities in soils where high numbers of microplastics are expected.

Methods: Soil samples were collected from three land use types: active landfill, remediated landfill, and agricultural soil. From each field, we took 3 replicates and isolated all DNA from soil samples of the top soil layer (0 - 10 cm). Microbial community profiling was performed using Illumina amplicon sequencing, making use of a Novaseq (2x300 bp, paired-end), targeting the V3-V4 fragment of the 16S rRNA gene (bacteria), and ITS2 rDNA region (fungi).

Results: Sequencing analysis showed shifts in microbial community structure across the tested soil types. In the agricultural soil (control), the bacterial community was dominated by *Pseudomonadota* (>50%) and *Actinomycetota* (20–25%). The active landfill exhibited a significant reduction in both species, with a strong increase in *Bacteroidota*. This change in community structure was proven by a PERMANOVA analysis ($p<0,001$) showing a statistical difference in microbial community in between the two land types. In the remediated landfill the relative abundance of *Pseudomonadota* was higher than in the active landfill but still lower than in the control. This indicates that the long-term effects of landfill continue to prevent a full return of microbial communities to the structure observed in the agricultural soil, served as control. However, we do acknowledge that the effects could also be soil dependent and should be evaluated further with information regarding nutrient status, organic matter content, microplastic content and soil texture.

Conclusions: These findings highlight the lasting impact of land use and remediation efforts on soil microbial communities, aligning with existing results on environmental stress and community composition.

Acknowledgements: This abstract is based upon work from COST Action MiCropBiomes, CA22158, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology), European Union Horizon Europe Project GREENLand - Twinning Microplastic-free Environment under Grant Agreement 101079267 and the ERC funded project MiCoS, grant number 101075944

Microbiome, Microplastic, Bioremediation, Sequencing, PERMANOVA

Managing Microplastics for Sustainable Agriculture: Legal and Policy Perspectives from the EU and Serbia

Biljana Panin¹, Ljiljana Milošević¹, Nataša Stojić¹, Mira Pucarević⁴, Dunja Prokić¹, Galina Čurčić¹, Mislav Đidara², Marcela Šperanda²

¹Educons University, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

²Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences Osijek

biljana.panin@educons.edu.rs

Background & Objectives: Management of microplastics in agriculture is not an isolated environmental issue but a key area for achieving multiple goals of the 2030 Agenda – from resource protection and the attainment of sustainable agriculture to ensuring food safety and preserving ecosystems.

Methods: This paper examines existing legislation, regulatory frameworks, and policy measures addressing plastic management, with a particular focus on microplastic, within the framework of sustainable agriculture, focusing on the European Union (EU) and the Republic of Serbia. Special attention is given to sectoral approaches targeting microplastic reduction in water, soil, air, and food systems, as well as relevant directives on waste, packaging, and environmental quality standards.

Conclusions: The research concludes that achieving sustainable agriculture in both the EU and Serbia requires the development of a coherent and comprehensive regulatory framework that explicitly governs microplastic generation, use, and mitigation.

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by the Interreg IPA Croatia-Serbia HR-RS00018 – ECO(RE)ACT project

[1] Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions; The European Green Deal COM/2019/640 final <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52019DC0640>

[2] Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), consolidated text of 17 December 2022, as amended by Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/2055 of 25 September 2023 amending Annex XVII as regards synthetic polymer microparticles, Official Journal of the European Union L 238, 27.9.2023

Microplastics, Agriculture, Policy, European Union, Serbia

Methodological approaches for microplastics isolation and analysis from tissues of marine organisms (bivalves, fish)

Vlatka Filipović Marijić¹, Martina Ugrinović¹, Sara Šariri¹, Tatjana Mijošek Pavin¹, Marija Kuštro¹, Fabio Faraguna², Dajana Kučić Grgić²

¹Ruđer Bošković Institute, Division for Marine and Environmental Research, Zagreb, Croatia

²University of Zagreb, Faculty of chemical engineering and technology, Zagreb, Croatia

vf Filip@irb.hr

Background & Objectives: Plastic is widely recognized as an emerging pollutant in the aquatic environment. Large amounts of microplastics (MPs), of primary or secondary origin, enter and persist in marine and freshwater ecosystems worldwide and, due to their small size, may be ingested by aquatic organisms [1]. Data on the presence of MPs in different tissues of bivalves and fish are still rare, and the methodologies for MPs isolation and analyses are not defined.

Methods: Few different methodologies for digestion of intestine and gonads of fishes and digestive gland and mantle of bivalves were applied (combination of acids, hydroxides, peroxide) at different temperatures in the ultrasonic bath or dryer, followed by vacuum filtration over polyester and polycarbonate filters coated with gold of a pore size of 0.8 μm. Isolated MPs were analyzed by optical and IR microscopy and the data were compared.

Conclusions: Generally, MP particles were rare in tissues, depending on tissue type, with higher occurrence in fish intestine and mussel digestive gland, confirming dietary uptake routes from the environment. The most common shapes were fibers of different colors, while MP types included polystyrene, polyethylene, polypropylene, polyamide, poly(ethylene-co-acrylic acid), poly(ethylene-co-vinyl acetate). Methodological approach should avoid high temperatures and strong acids to preserve MPs, but also needs to minimize the presence of other organic and inorganic compounds. Proper isolation protocols and analyses of MP occurrence (like IR microscopy) may provide valuable data to develop strategies for the protection of aquatic ecosystems, but also human health.

Fig.1. Isolated MPs from tissues of fish and mussels on IR microscope (AIM-9000, Shimadzu)

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by the Croatian Science Foundation under the project number HRZZ-IP-2024-05-8918 (PlastOrgAnoTox)

[1] Vivekanand, A.C. et al. (2021) 'Microplastics in aquatic environment: Challenges and perspectives', *Chemosphere*, 282, 131151. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.131151>

SESSION 4: Project networking session

- Connecting research teams, institutions, and innovators working on microplastics
- Short project presentations from EU, national, and local initiatives
- Opportunities for collaboration, joint publications, and future partnerships
- Showcasing interdisciplinary approaches and project success stories
- Featured projects will be included in the MICROM2025 Book of Abstracts

MODERATOR: Dr. Ana Mendes

Earth and Life Sciences, School of Natural Sciences and Ryan Institute, University of Galway, Ireland

Dr Ana Rita M. Mendes is a marine biologist specialised in biodiversity, ecology, and genetics. She earned her PhD at the University of Galway, Ireland, where she developed analytical methods to detect and track microplastics in the marine environment. Before her doctoral studies, she gained experience in geological and environmental analysis while working for several years in a petrology laboratory.

Currently, she is a postdoctoral researcher in the GREENLand project, which focuses on developing digital tools and training researchers to investigate microplastics in soil, water, and microorganisms while promoting collaboration between institutions and industry for a plastic-free future. She has contributed to multiple national and international research projects focused on marine pollution assessment. Her research aims to contribute to a better understanding of marine pollution and its impact on ecosystem health.

MODERATOR: Dr. Ljiljana Milošević

*EDUCONS University,
Faculty of Environmental Protection*

Dr Ljiljana Milošević is an environmental scientist specializing in environmental protection management, currently serving as Assistant Professor and Vice Dean for Corporate Relations at Educons University's Faculty of Environmental protection. She holds a Ph.D. in Environmental Science and a Master's degree in Environmental Engineering. With more than ten years of academic and research experience at the Faculty of Environmental Protection, her work focuses on air quality monitoring, waste management, climate neutrality, and the development of evidence-based environmental policies.

Throughout her career, she has contributed to numerous national and international projects aimed at mitigating environmental impacts. Her research addresses critical issues such as microplastic contamination in the environment, carbon emissions, waste management and climate change. The outcomes of these projects have been instrumental in identifying and evaluating sustainable, innovative solutions that advance environmental protection, support academic and industrial sectors in developing strategies for sustainable environmental management, and strengthen cross-sector collaboration and capacity-building in environmental management.

KEYNOTE SPEAKER:
Dr. Sebastian Primpke

*Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz
Centre for Polar and Marine
Research, Helgoland, Germany*

Dr Sebastian Primpke is an expert in analytical and physical chemistry and holds a doctorate and a diploma degree in chemistry.

His doctoral studies focused on polymer science before he moved into his current position in the Microbial Ecology – Microplastics Research Group of the Shelf Sea System Ecology department. Here, he focused on the analysis of microplastics in various environmental compartments for microplastics ranging from aqueous samples (including melted ice and snow) over solid matrices to biota.

In this scope, he developed analytical methods using FTIR and Raman spectroscopy with the aim of an automated analysis of the results. He is part of different ISO and DIN working groups aiming on the standardization of microplastics sampling and analysis.

One tool to test it all: The harmonized analysis of microplastics by siMPle

Sebastian Primpke¹, Alvis Vianello², Gunnar Gerds¹, Jes Vollertsen²

¹ Alfred-Wegener-Institut, Biologische Anstalt Helgoland, Kurpromenade 201, 27498 Helgoland, Germany

² Aalborg University, Department of the Built Environment, Thomas Manns Vej 23, 9220, Aalborg Øst, Denmark

While in the past decade the number of studies on microplastics (MPs) rapidly increased the meta-analysis of the generated data is hampered by a missing harmonization of the reported results. This hampers the broad scale assessment of the overall risk of these particles. To achieve comparable results to foster policy advice and decision making, the generation of harmonized data is of high importance. In the case of MP analysis, different spectroscopical methods like Fourier-Transform Infrared (FTIR) imaging are used. While it allows a bias-free chemical mapping of the sample, a comparable and harmonized spectral data determination is challenging due to the different manufacturers and commercial software tools available. This generates a broad diversity in the reported data for derived material types and particle sizes. To overcome these limitations, we developed the freeware software tool siMPle (www.simple-plastics.eu). It has been applied in a wide variety of studies covering samples from air, biota, waters, sediments and soils. Here, it handled large datasets from various manufacturers by two automated analysis pipelines. We present a selection different application scenarios of the software ranging from data analysis harmonization in large scientific towards its application in citizen science projects. This will be combined with a short outlook on lessons learned using a harmonized analytical tool over a broad series of projects and study areas. Finally, due to the increasing number of data analysis tools based on machine learning or artificial intelligence, we will provide a preview on future developments. These aim to allow the analysis of large datasets containing several million spectra with relative ease using custom-made analysis tools while using the siMPle graphical interface and data reporting tools. At the same time, comparing results to previous studies or projects like is possible allowing the harmonization of MP data analysis for spectroscopic data for future research.

An Innovative Sampling Solution for Microplastics in Small Shallow Rivers

Anja Bubik¹, Aljoša Krajnc¹, Nataša Uranjek^{1,2}

¹ Faculty of Environmental Protection, Trg mladosti 7, 3320 Velenje, Slovenia

² Velenje Public Utility Company, Koroška cesta 37b, 3320 Velenje, Slovenia

anja.bubik@fvo.si

Background & Objectives: Microplastic pollution in aquatic environments poses a growing threat to ecosystems. Although marine environments have received the most scientific attention, rivers play a crucial role, as up to 70% of plastic pollution in oceans originates from inland waterways. Small and shallow rivers remain underrepresented in research and likely underestimated in their contribution to microplastic pollution. Sampling microplastics in these environments is particularly challenging. Researchers are therefore seeking diverse and adaptable solutions to overcome these barriers.

Methods: Within the Interreg Europe project PLASTIX, we initiated a study to develop a sampling method for microplastics in small and shallow rivers. The Savinja-Salek region in Slovenia, with its two main rivers Paka and Savinja, was selected as the study area, where traditional net-based or vessel-dependent methods are not applicable. We conducted a literature review of 37 studies to evaluate existing sampling techniques, including manta nets, plankton nets, pump-based systems, and manual collection. Based on the key features of each method, we designed a novel sampling device tailored to regional conditions.

Results: The developed prototype is a portable, pump-driven system equipped with a 150-micron stainless steel filter and an ultrasonic flowmeter for precise volume measurement. Its telescopic arm enables sampling in shallow rivers without the need for bridges or vessels. In both rivers, the device filtered 1 m³ of water in 10 minutes, yielding 2 liters of concentrated sample. Small amounts of microplastics, predominantly microfibers, were found in all samples, which was expected given the environmental pressures in the region.

Conclusions: This innovative approach offers a scalable, regionally adapted solution for microplastic sampling in shallow inland waters. While further validation is needed to improve sampling efficiency and eliminate contamination risks, the first version of the device has proven to be a promising tool for seasonal monitoring and long-term pollution assessment.

Acknowledgements: The study was co-funded by the European Union through the Interreg Europe project PLASTIX – Plastics Revolution for European Regions (ID 01C0084).

Microplastics, River sampling, PLASTIX project, Inland water pollution

An insider's view of Nature journals

Raghavendra Palankar¹

¹Senior Editor - Nature Nanotechnology, Springer Nature, Heidelberger Platz 3, 14197 Berlin

raghavendra.palankar@nature.com

Background & Objectives: Raghavendra Palankar is a senior editor of the journal Nature Nanotechnology. He has a PhD in Biochemical Engineering with multidisciplinary training in basic, applied and translational research.

Within the editorial team of Nature Nanotechnology, he handles a broad cross-section of topics covering single-molecule /particle sensing techniques, nanoscale analytics, DNA/RNA nanotechnology, nano/micro-robotics, bioelectronics, and synthetic biology, spanning all areas from nano- to macroscales. Besides this, he handles topics related to micro- and nanoplastics research more broadly, as this is one of the areas the journal he is particularly interested in.

The talk will cover:

- Scope of Nature Nanotechnology and the content we publish
- Editorial process and editorial criteria
- Micro- and nanoplastics in Nature Nanotechnology
- Relationship with other Nature journals within the portfolio.

Scientific publishing in Microplastics and nanoplastics research

Advantages of using Focal Plane Array Infra-red detectors in quantitative and qualitative analysis of Microplastics samples

Vladimir Kržalić¹

¹Donau Lab d.o.o. Beograd

vladimir@donaulab.rs

Background & Objectives: Microplastics, defined as plastic particles smaller than 5 mm, have become major environmental contaminants in ecosystems. Their chemical diversity and small particle size present significant challenges for qualitative and quantitative determination. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy has emerged as a powerful technique for microplastic characterization due to its ability to provide molecular-level information. Recent advances in infrared detector technology, particularly the development of focal plane array (FPA) detectors, have greatly improved the spatial resolution and acquisition speed of FTIR imaging. It enables fast, automated collection of large spectral datasets, allowing detailed mapping and classification of microplastic particles in complex environmental matrices. The Bruker LUMOS II FPA infrared microscope has become a leading tool for microplastics analysis due to its high spatial resolution, rapid data acquisition, and fully automated sample workflow.

Methods: Environmental and reference samples containing microplastics were analysed using a Bruker LUMOS II FTIR microscope equipped with a 32x32 pixel FPA detector. Measurements were performed in both reflection and transmission modes. Spectra were acquired in the mid-infrared range with a spatial resolution of 5 µm per pixel. Automated acquisition and analysis were carried out using Bruker's OPUS and Microplastics Finder software, enabling particle detection, spectral identification, and polymer classification through database comparison.

Results: This approach enables rapid identification and mapping of microplastic particles with high spatial resolution. Thousands of spectra were collected in a single measurement, greatly reducing analysis time compared to conventional point-by-point FTIR methods. Automated workflows improved reproducibility and minimized operator influence.

Conclusions: FPA-based FTIR microscopy provides a powerful, efficient, and reproducible method for microplastics determination. Its combination of high spatial resolution, rapid data acquisition, and automated analysis enhances throughput and accuracy, demonstrating strong potential for standardized use in environmental and research laboratories.

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by Bruker Optics GmbH & Co. KG, Ettlingen, Germany.

Fig. 1. Functionality of FPA FT-IR detector

ECO(RE)ACT - Pioneering ecosystem-based microplastics contamination reduction and climate change resilience in cross-border region

Biljana Panin¹

¹Educons University, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

biljana.panin@educons.edu.rs

Background & Objectives: The project's overall objective is to establish a comprehensive system for addressing plastic and microplastics issues in ecosystems, contributing to climate change adaptation. Its primary focus is to tackle the issue of microplastics contamination in ecosystems from agriculture within the cross-border region of Croatia and Serbia. The project will encompass a well-developed Strategy, Control points for monitoring microplastics contamination, and "Centre for Microplastics". The goal is to achieve sustainable practices, reduced contamination levels, heightened awareness among stakeholders, and implement policies for effective adaptation to climate change.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Project number:	HR-RS00018 – ECO(RE)ACT
Project name:	Pioneering ecosystem-based microplastics contamination reduction and climate change resilience in cross-border region
Project acronym:	ECO(RE)ACT
Call:	Interreg IPA Croatia-Serbia 2021-2027 1st Call for Proposals
Project starting date:	15. 6. 2024.
Project duration:	30 MONTHS
Participants:	Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences Osijek - Lead partner Educons University in Sremska Kamenica - Partner Institute for Nature Conservation of Vojvodina Province - Partner
Website page:	https://mikroplastika.fazos.hr/

Microplastics, Climate change resilience, Cross-border region

Empowering Green Skills through EDU4PlastiCircular: Educational Resources and Awareness Campaigns

Anca DRĂGHICI¹, Florica MANEA¹, Cristiana RUS¹, Anastasia ROȘCA¹, Aniela POP¹

¹Politehnica University of Timisoara, Romania

anca.draghici@upt.ro, aniela.popa@upt.ro

Background & Objectives: EDU4PlastiCircular promotes sustainable micro/nanoplastic use through targeted educational campaigns and a multilingual training program. Its newsletters highlight achievements in building green skills, raising awareness, and supporting policy alignment across Europe. By offering accessible resources and practical insights, the project empowers educators and learners to contribute to the Circular Economy. Central to its outreach is the digital library, which serves as dynamic platforms for disseminating multilingual resources (including presentations, readings, worksheets, and terminology guides) aligned with the project's e-learning modules. These materials cover key topics such as the role of plastics in daily life, typologies and manufacturing technologies, and relevant standards and legislation within the Circular Economy. The newsletters have spotlighted impactful campaigns aimed at fostering behavioral change and encouraging harmonization of policies across Europe. By integrating educational content with practical insights, EDU4PlastiCircular empowers educators, students, and stakeholders to contribute meaningfully to a climate-neutral future.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Project number:	2023-1-RO01-KA220-HED-000166242
Project name:	Education for Plastic in a Circular and Climate Neutral Economy - Preventing Waste Ending Up into the Environment
Project acronym:	EDU4PlastiCircular
Call:	Erasmus+
Topic:	Plastic Circularity
Type of action:	Erasmus+ KA220-HED - Cooperation partnerships in higher education
Project starting date:	1 November 2023
Project duration:	36 MONTHS
Participants:	Politehnica University of Timisoara, Romania – Coordinator; Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania – Partner; Universitat Politecnica de Valencia, Spain – Partner; Universita degli studi dell'Insubria, Italy – Partner; Faculty of environmental protection Velenje, Slovenia – Partner; DERMOL Ltd, Slovenia – Partner
Website page:	https://microplastics.today/

Micro/nanoplastics, Education, E-learning, Digital library, Awareness campaigns, Circular economy

ICPLASTIC - ISO Compatible, Efficient and Reproducible Protocols/Equipment for Micro-Nanoplastic Detection through Machine Learning

Aleksandra Tubić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Science, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

aleksandra.tubic@dh.uns.ac.rs

Background & Objectives: ICPLASTIC is an ambitious research network with a transformative goal of developing efficient and reproducible protocols and equipment for micro and nanoplastic sampling, sample preparation and analysis to both support the application of ISO standards and water quality legislation and close knowledge gaps in risk analysis and occurrence.

The main aim of the Action is to develop a suitable formulation of efficient/reproducible protocols and equipment for micro- and nanoplastic sampling, sample preparation and analysis to support the application of ISO standards and all water quality legislation, and close knowledge gaps in risk analysis through their enablement of improved toxicological/environmental studies.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Project number:	CA23131
Project name:	ISO COMPATIBLE, EFFICIENT AND REPRODUCIBLE PROTOCOLS/EQUIPMENT FOR MICRO-NANOPLASTIC DETECTION THROUGH MACHINE-LEARNING
Project acronym:	ICPLASTIC
Call:	OC-2023-1
Project starting date:	18 September 2024
Project duration:	48 MONTHS
Participants:	ASTON UNIVERSITY - Primary proposer 75 Secondary proposers
Website page:	https://www.icplastic.eu

Microplastics, ISO standard, Machine learning, Environmental, Drinking and bottled water, Analytical techniques

INSPIRE – Innovative Solutions for Plastic Free European Rivers

Annamaria Vujanović¹

¹University of Maribor, Slovenia

annamaria.vujanovic@um.si

Background & Objectives: The INSPIRE project brings together 20 innovative technologies and strategic actions to detect, collect and prevent the extent of aquatic litter. The project aims to provide holistic solutions by testing technologies and actions in six use cases while involving 26 partners from the academia, industry, and communication sectors. INSPIRE strives to establish a modular master plan for scaling up technologies and actions, offering ‘fit for all’ solutions applicable and replicable in rivers across Europe, contributing to the drastic reduction of litter, macroplastics and microplastics in our rivers.

Among these advanced solutions are technologies for the retention and elimination of microplastics and nanoplastics from urban wastewater systems. The currently operational pilot system, set up at the Domžale–Kamnik Wastewater Treatment Plant in Slovenia and coordinated by the University of Maribor, showcases a pilot-scale integration of these technologies under real operational conditions.

At this demo site, INSPIRE has implemented the following technologies: EcoPlex (Waste & Water), the Super-TW-Net (DELVEC), the CLERA filtration technology, and the photocatalytic nanocoating device (KTH) as a cascade systems designed to achieve staged removal and final degradation of plastic particles. The partners are supported by Infordata with integrated digital sensors as well as VITO and VLIZ in performing sample analysis and MINDS in coordinating WP2 on technology implementation.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Project number:	101112879
Project name:	Innovative Solutions for Plastic Free European Rivers
Project acronym:	INSPIRE
Call:	HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01
Topic:	HORIZON-MISS-2022-OCEAN-01-04 - Prevent and eliminate litter, plastics and microplastics: Innovative solutions for waste-free European rivers
Type of action:	HORIZON-IA - HORIZON Innovation Actions
Service:	REA/C/03
Project starting date:	30 MAY 2023
Project duration:	48 MONTHS

Participants:	VLIZ, BELGIUM – Coordinator VITO, BELGIUM – Partner UNIVERSITY OF MARIBOR, SLOVENIA – Partner CLERAONE, SLOVENIA – Partner MOLD SRL, ITALY – Partner FISHLOW INNOVATIONS, NETHERLANDS – Partner CIIMAR, PORTUGAL – Partner 123ZERO, SLOVENIA – Partner HOSCHULEN FRESENIUS, GERMANY – Partner WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, NETHERLANDS – Partner BIO-MI, CROATIA – Partner MINDS, GREECE – Partner KTH, SWEDEN – Partner DELVEC, GREECE – Partner CNR, ITALY – Partner EXIT FOUNDATION, SERBIA – Partner UNIVERSITY OF CADIZ, SPAIN – Partner ALCHEMIA-NOVA, AUSTRIA – Partner ARCHA SRL, ITALY – Partner INFORDATA SISTEMI SRL, ITALY – Partner CIRCE BIOTECHNOLOGIE, AUSTRIA – Partner RIVER CLEANUP, BELGIUM – Partner WASTE & WATER, FRANCE – Partner ROMANIAN WATER ASSOCIATION, ROMANIA – Partner ASIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, THAILAND – Partner NORIA, NETHERLANDS – Partner
Website page:	https://inspire-europe.org/

Microplastics, Filtration, Wastewater treatment plant, Pilot system

Investigation of the Content of Micropolymers and Biota from a Marine Ecosystem

Sevdalina H. Turmanova¹, Yancho H. Hristov¹, Dimitrina S. Kiryakova¹, Alexander N. Dimitrov¹, N. Todorov¹, Emilia D. Ivanova¹, Plamena V. Atanasova¹, Ganka R. Kolchakova¹, Antonia S. Ilieva¹, Elena Y. Mollova¹

¹Burgas State University „Prof. Dr. Assen Zlatarov“, Bulgaria

gkolchakova@gmail.com

Background & Objectives: The Black Sea and its watershed represent a natural laboratory of worldwide significance for fundamental science and sustainable policies. The current project addresses the global problem of micropolymer (MP) pollution, with its scientific focus on their presence and impact in the marine environment of the Burgas Bay. The activities set out in the project are related to determining the content and distribution of MP in sediments and biota in three key locations: Burgas Central Beach, „St. Anastasia“ Island, and Chengene Skele. Applying an interdisciplinary approach combining physical, chemical, and biotechnological methods, as well as spectral analyses, the chemical composition of MP will be identified, and their distribution and potential penetration into marine organisms will be determined. Based on the results, specific methodologies for extracting micropolymers and approaches for assessing pollution in different matrices of the marine environment will be developed

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Project number:	KP-06-H89/4
Project name:	INVESTIGATION OF THE CONTENT OF MICROPOLYMERS IN SEDIMENT AND BIOTA FROM A MARINE ECOSYSTEM
Project acronym:	-
Call:	BULGARIAN NATIONAL SCIENCE FUND
Topic:	COMPETITION FOR FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR BASIC RESEARCH PROJECTS – 2024
Type of action:	RESEARCH
Service:	-
Project starting date:	09.12.2024
Project duration:	36 MONTHS
Participants:	-
Website page:	-

Microplastics, Marine ecosystem, Black Sea, Burgas Bay, Sediment, Biota

InPlasTwin - Increasing expertise in micro- and nanoplastics analysis through twinning action

Janja Vidmar¹, Nhu Phan², Milica Velimirovic², Katrin Loeschner³, Nanna B. Hartmann⁴, André Marcel Bienfait⁵, Dimitrios Savvas⁶, Gordana Racić⁷, Mladen Radišić⁷

¹Department of Environmental Sciences, Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

²Laboratory for inorganic and organic analysis, Flemish Institute for Technological Research, Mol, Belgium

³National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark

⁴Department of Environmental and Resource Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark

⁵Institute of Marine Research, Bergen, Norway

⁶Department of Crop Science, Agricultural University of Athens, Athens, Greece

⁷Foodscale Hub, Novi Sad, Serbia

janja.vidmar@ijs.si

Background & Objectives: The InPlasTwin Horizon Europe project, running from October 2024 to September 2027, is dedicated to advancing the understanding of the environmental and food-related impacts of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), with a particular focus on possible impacts arising from plastic and biodegradable mulching film use in strawberry cultivation. Its overarching goal is to enhance research capacity in the analysis of MNPs in the environment and food through strategic networking, knowledge exchange, and collaborative research activities between the Jožef Stefan Institute in Slovenia, the Agricultural University of Athens in Greece, and leading European research institutions in the field of MNPs analysis: the Flemish Institute for Technological Research (Belgium), the Technical University of Denmark, and the Institute of Marine Research (Norway).

Methods: The research component of this twinning project focuses on investigating the degradability of mulching films and the potential uptake and effects of the resulting MNPs on strawberries. To achieve this, a series of laboratory- and field-scale experiments has been designed, including: 1) investigating the degradation behaviour of mulching films into MNPs under simulated agricultural conditions; 2) developing protocols for extracting MNPs from agricultural soil and food samples; 3) advancing analytical methodologies for the quantification, identification, and characterization of MNPs using state-of-the-art spectroscopic and mass spectrometric techniques; 4) assessing the release of plastic additives into the environment and their potential migration into edible plant parts, with implications for food safety; and 5) evaluating the environmental fate and uptake of MNPs and associated plastic additives by strawberries in controlled laboratory and field-scale experiments.

Conclusions: The outcomes of the project are expected to foster networking and knowledge exchange among the partners, strengthen their scientific capabilities and research profile in MNPs studies, and raise awareness among relevant stakeholders about the challenges of plastic pollution in agriculture and food.

Acknowledgements: Funded by the European Union project InPlasTwin, grant agreement No. 101160289.

Microplastics, Nanoplastics, Mulching films, Strawberry, Agricultural soil

Microplastics for Breakfast: Strengthening research collaboration and science to business to policy dialogue in the Western Balkan

Andreja Palatinus^{1,2}

¹Business Consulting, Andreja Palatinus, s.p., Ljubljana, Slovenia

²National Institute of Chemistry, Ljubljana, Slovenia

andreja.palatinus@ki.si

Background & Objectives: The first assessment of microplastics in the Slovenian Sea in 2010 marked an early step toward understanding plastic pollution in the region. Since then, research on microplastics in the Western Balkans has grown rapidly, especially after 2017. This expansion has also led to fragmentation: researchers often remain unaware of each other's work, infrastructure is scattered, and duplication of effort is common. Collaboration in EU projects is limited, while inconsistent media coverage weakens scientific credibility. The Microplastics for Breakfast (MPfB) initiative was launched in 2023 to connect researchers, strengthen links with business and policy stakeholders, and promote science-based communication on micro- and nanoplastics.

Methods: MPfB combines complementary activities centred on networking events inspired by the business breakfast concept and aligned with the quintuple helix approach. Technical workshops build expertise, while webinars with leading scientists share best practices and motivate early-career researchers. A regional newsletter informs subscribers about new research and policy developments. The MPfB aims to create an environment where researchers are valued and supported. We want to build a database of regional experts, institutions, and companies working on micro- and nanoplastics, to strengthen collaboration and enable practical solutions.

Results: So far, eleven MPfB events have been held in Slovenia, Croatia, and Serbia. Three major meetings in Ljubljana (2023), Zagreb (2024), and Belgrade (2025) brought together over 200 researchers, while workshops and webinars featured experts such as João Frias, François Galgani, and Giuseppe Suaria. In total, MPfB engaged 373 in-person participants, 303 online attendees, and 455 YouTube views. A database of more than 200 regional researchers has been established, mapping expertise and equipment, and fostering new collaborations across science, business, and policy.

Conclusions: Microplastics for Breakfast (MPfB) is developing into a regional hub for expertise and collaboration, serving as a reference point for all interested in micro- and nanoplastics, supporting policy implementation, and strengthening the collective scientific voice toward a cleaner, plastic-free environment [1–3].

Acknowledgements: Thank you, Merel d.o.o. (Slovenia), Shimadzu d.o.o. (Croatia), SUPERLAB d.o.o. (Serbia), PerkinElmer, Prirodno-matematički fakultet Novi Sad (Serbia), Educons University (Serbia), and COST Actions PRIORITY and GREENLand, both funded by the European Union.

[1] Dewika D. et al. (2024). Integrating the quintuple helix approach into atmospheric microplastics management policies for planetary health preservation. *Science of the Total Environment*. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.173902,

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[3] Gajšt T., Palatinus A. et al. (2016). Microplastics in Slovenian coastal waters and sediments. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 113(1–2), 392–399. doi:10.1016/j.marpolbul.2016.10.028

NOMAD: Nano-/Microplastic Mobility and Contaminant Co-Transport in Groundwater – A Multiscale Study with Finnish Perspective

Muhammad Muniruzzaman¹, Evgenii Kortunov¹, Tuomo Soininen², Tenzin Tsering², Jarkko Akkanen², Arto Koistinen²

¹Geological Survey of Finland (GTK), ²University of Eastern Finland (UEF)

arto.koistinen@uef.fi

Background & Objectives: Nano- and microplastics (NMPs) have emerged as a global problem because of their widespread distribution in the environment and potential for detrimental effects on human health and ecology. Despite a decade of extensive research, most studies so far focused on surface waters, with very little attention to groundwater systems. Therefore, a systematic understanding of the environmental fate of NMPs and associated contaminants in groundwater is currently lacking.

Methods: NOMAD will create novel scientific understanding and tools to assess the fate of Nano- and microplastics (NMPs) and NMP driven contaminant co-transport in groundwater systems, by integrating innovative multi-scale investigations and process-based modeling. We will perform laboratory experiments in batch, 1D column, and 2D flow-through setups to study NMPs-contaminant interactions and to quantify the sorption and transport parameters. Successively, we will perform analogous experiments in pilot meso-scale aquifer setup and, finally, in groundwater aquifers, to 1) study NMPs transport and NMPs induced co-transport phenomena and 2) test the applicability of lab-derived parameters at field conditions. To quantitatively interpret the experiments, a new reactive transport modeling tool will be developed by simultaneously resolving key physical, geochemical, and electrostatic processes and their multilevel coupling during NMPs transport and contaminant co-transport in groundwater. Moreover, we will develop an adequate workflow to analyze small-sized NMPs (<20µm) in water and solid samples. Finally, we will establish a baseline for N-MP concentrations in Finnish aquifers.

Conclusions: To date, NMPs' fate and transport and the associated co-transport mechanisms have only been studied in laboratory batch and column experiments. Thus, our multi-scale approach, involving 2D, pilot and field experiments, goes radically beyond the state-of-the art leading to novel discoveries on multidimensional and field-scale effects of NMP's transport mechanisms. Also, NOMAD provides a modeling tool, which will benefit the research community, regulatory agencies, and stakeholders globally.

Acknowledgements: The project is funded by Research Council of Finland for 4 years.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Project name:	Nano-/Microplastic Mobility and Contaminant Co-Transport in Groundwater – A Multiscale Study with Finnish Perspective
Project acronym:	NOMAD
Call:	Research Council of Finland
Topic:	-
Type of action:	Research project
Service:	-
Project starting date:	1 September 2024
Project duration:	48 months
Participants:	GEOLOGICAL SURVEY OF FINLAND – Coordinator UNIVERSITY OF EASTERN FINLAND, FINLAND – Partner
Website page:	https://uefconnect.uef.fi/NOMAD

Microplastics, Facilitated transport, Laboratory experiment, Field study, Reactive transport modeling, Groundwater

Awareness and knowledge of farmers, winegrowers, and students on microplastics in agricultural soil

Claudia Preininger¹, Viktoria Stagl¹

¹Austrian Institute of Technology, Center for Health & Bioresources, Bioresources Unit, Konrad-Lorenz-Straße 24, 3430 Tulln, Austria

Claudia.preininger@ait.ac.at

Background & Objectives: Information, education, and awareness are essential to reduce plastic use and identify sustainable solutions. This requires the involvement of all stakeholders—from industry and farmers to the public and education sector—and understanding their perceptions and behaviors. In 2023, we surveyed students at Austrian universities (including universities of applied sciences and higher agricultural schools) and farmers/winegrowers to assess knowledge and attitudes toward microplastics and bioplastics.

Methods: The student survey was conducted online via the easyfeedback platform and distributed through the Austrian National Union of Students (ÖH), agricultural colleges, and university partners. An 18-question online survey for farmers and winegrowers, distributed through the Agricultural Chamber of Lower Austria, targeted producers of arable crops, vegetables, fruit, and wine.

Results: Among students (N=417), 98% had heard of microplastics, mainly in the context of water and marine pollution. While 88% reported hearing about microplastics in water “very often” and 12% “sometimes,” awareness in agriculture was lower: 22% and 36%, with 16% never hearing of them. Main information sources were internet and television. Regarding solutions, 65% had heard of bioplastics, and 49% believed they were less harmful than conventional plastics. Among farmers, 67% used plastic equipment such as foils and nets for protective purposes. Farmers were generally aware of degradability or recyclability of obvious plastics but mostly unaware that fertilizers, treated seeds, or pesticides may contain microplastics. Awareness of certifications for degradable products was low: 21% recognized the TÜV Austria label and 3.4% the DIN label.

Conclusions: Awareness and concern about microplastic pollution are high, though discussion focuses on waterborne microplastics. Knowledge is mainly media-driven, with limited attention to soil contamination. Promoting sustainable plastic use in agriculture requires clear policy guidelines, farmer incentives, and more information on biodegradable products' technical performance in field conditions.

Acknowledgements: This research was supported by the Gesellschaft für Forschungsförderung Niederösterreich m.b.H. within NETmicroplastic (FTI21-P-008).

Awareness of microplastics, Students' survey, Farmers' survey, Bioplastics

Communicating Microplastics Science through Education

Katrin Školnik Škrabe¹, Lea Komerički Kotnik¹, Anja Bubik¹

¹Faculty of Environmental Protection, Trg mladosti 7, 3320 Velenje, Slovenia

lea.komericki.kotnik@fvo.si

Background & Objectives: Microplastics are omnipresent and pose significant environmental and health risks. Despite growing scientific understanding and public discourse, awareness among the general population, especially youth, remains limited. At the Faculty of Environmental Protection, we have been addressing this gap by promoting science communication and environmental education across all formal education levels. Our goal is to empower youth to understand microplastics' sources, fate, and inspire behavioral changes.

Methods: As a joint outcome of four Erasmus+ projects (MicPlaPROB, EDU4PlastiCircular, GreenGate, and GreenGate₂), we developed the educational program Micro(μ)School, which includes interdisciplinary workshops for primary, secondary, and tertiary education. These workshops integrate digital tools, interactive learning, and real-life examples (e.g., microplastics in textiles and cosmetics) to actively engage youth and educators. The pedagogical approach was guided by EU strategic documents, including the European Green Deal and the Council Recommendation on Learning for the Green Transition.

Results: Over a three-year period, we engaged more than 1000 youth through 21 educational events. In this paper, we present three thematic workshops from the Micro(μ)School program, each adapted for all educational levels. The workshops focus on microplastics in textiles, hidden plastics in cosmetics, and environmental consequences of plastic pollution. Participants gained knowledge, developed green and digital skills, and proposed innovative solutions. Activities included online courses, video creation, field excursions, interactive apps, and hands-on workshops, fostering local engagement and raising awareness of microplastics' environmental impact.

Conclusions: Our program demonstrates how science communication can be integrated into education to address environmental challenges. By targeting youth, one of the first generations to understand the microplastics issue and one of the last with the power to act, we contribute to a more informed and responsible society. The program also supports EU goals for sustainability, digital transformation, and green skills development, highlighting education as a key driver of change.

Acknowledgements: The work presented in this paper was co-funded by the EU Erasmus+ projects EDU4PlastiCircular: “Education for Plastics in a Circular and Climate Neutral Economy – Preventing Waste from Ending Up in the Environment” (Erasmus+ 2023-1-RO01-KA220-HED-000166242); MicPlaPROB: “Microplastics: tomorrow's macro problem”(Erasmus+ 2021-1-SI01-KA210-VET-000034536); GreenGate (Erasmus+ 2021-1-CZ01-KA2020-ADU-000026171); and GreenGate2 (Erasmus+ 2023-2-CZ01-KA220-YOU-000174554). The content of this paper and any related communication reflect the views of the authors alone, and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use made of the information provided herein.

Microplastics, Science Communication, Environmental Education, Youth Engagement, Green Skills

Microplastics in suspended sediments of the Danube River – preliminary results of the SUNDANSE project research

Yevhen Nasiedkin^{1,2}, Ruslan Havryliuk^{1,3}, Mihaela Timofti⁴, Madalina Calmuc⁵, Vladyslav Balinsky¹

¹National Ecological Centre of Ukraine

²State Scientific Institution “Center for Problems of Marine Geology, Geoecology and Sedimentary Ore Formation of NAS of Ukraine”

³Institute of Geological Sciences of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine

⁴Dunarea de Jos University of Galati, Faculty of Sciences and Environment & REXDAN Research Infrastructure

⁵Dunarea de Jos University of Galati, REXDAN Research Infrastructure

Mihaela.Timofti@ugal.ro

Background & Objectives: There are a significant number of publications on the transport of MPs in the Danube by water flows, their distribution in bottom sediments or biological objects [1], [2]. Most studies focus on transport by water currents, with pollutants being collected from the water surface using plankton samplers such as manta trawls or other means of filtering water flow through mesh filters with a cell size of 200-300 µm.

Methods: Through SUNDANSE project, co-financed by the European Union, an experiment on long-term sampling of suspended solids using sedimentation traps were made. The testing site and location of the equipment is the Danube water area (45.391641, 29.602092) adjacent to the town of Vylkove in the Ochakiv estuary branch, where the division of the main water flow into two branches creates favorable conditions for studying sedimentation processes. The water depth at the sampling site is 1 m (with minor seasonal fluctuations). The equipment used (**Figure 1**), belongs to the “passive samplers” type, representing sedimentation traps designed for sampling suspended sediments [3].

Figure 1. General view of traps with pin fasteners in the riverbed and their location in the Danube River.

Results: During the research period, four samples of natural material were processed, each of which was accumulated over a period of one month between January and May 2025. As a rule, the total number of fragments separated from the main mass of the sample of mineral, organic, and anthropogenic origin ranged from 50 to 1,500 specimens and included, in addition to particles of artificial polymers, various organic (fragments of shells or shells of organisms and plants, in particular bark, stems, and branches) and loose mineral aggregates. A significant amount of carbon fragments was also observed in the samples, varying considerably for different sampling points and areas in terms of both quantitative and qualitative (dimension, morphological types, composition) indicators.

Conclusions: The study area is defined by the influence of the Danube water mass, and the mineral, organic, and anthropogenic suspended solids it carries partially reach this shelf zone and participate in sedimentation processes. A number of peculiarities in the distribution of MP fragments in the lower Danube suspension were revealed in comparison with particles studied in surface bottom sediments of shelf areas within the territorial waters of Romania in earlier studies. The comparison is preliminary in nature due to the small number of suspended matter in the samples and requires clarification with the involvement of a larger amount of field material.

Acknowledgements: This research is part of the project ‘Innovative sediment management framework for a SUSTAINABLE DANUBE BLACK SEA SYSTEM (SUNDANSE)’, co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Microplastics, Suspended sediment, Raman spectroscopy

Methodological Challenges of Microplastic Sampling and Analysis in the Framework of the MicroDrink Project

Branislav Petrović¹, Ana Selak², Gábor Bordós³, Sebastian Koeppel⁴, Lindinger Helga⁴, Uta Wemhöner⁴, Jadranka Šangulin⁵, Mirna Svec², Ljiljana Vasić¹, Saša Milanović¹, Veljko Marinović¹, Jelena Močević¹, Jasmina Lukač Reberski², Ivana Boljat², Marek Polášek⁶, Anja Torkar⁷, Mihael Brenčić⁷, Mohammad Alqadi⁸, Gabriele Chiogna⁸

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mining and Geology, Belgrade, Serbia

² Croatian Geological Survey, Zagreb, Croatia

³ Eurofins Analytical Services Hungary Kft., Budapest, Hungary

⁴ Environment Agency Austria, Vienna, Austria

⁵ Institute of Public Health Zadar, Croatia

⁶ T. G. Masaryk Water Research Institute, Brno, The Czech Republic

⁷ Department of Geology, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia

⁸ Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen, Germany

branislav.petrovic@rgf.bg.ac.rs

Background & Objectives: The presence of microplastics (MP) in drinking water resources is a growing concern, highlighting the urgent need for robust and standardized methods to accurately measure concentrations and assess potential environmental and human health impacts of MP. A lack of standardized methods for MP monitoring (water sampling, laboratory analysis) and varying national capacities pose significant obstacles and challenges across the entire EU as well as in the Danube River Basin (DRB). To address this, the MicroDrink project [1] was launched with the primary goal of enhancing DRB capacity for managing MP pollution.

Methods: One of the three specific objectives of the project was the development of a reliable methodology for groundwater and drinking water sampling. Based on the specific Commission Delegated Decision (EU) 2024/1441 [2], the proposed approach involved filtering 1,000 litres of water through two 20 µm stainless-steel filters (first filter: sample, second: blank), maintaining a flow rate below 1 L/s. Research on the presence of MP in drinking water resources is carried out in 9 pilot areas in all 8 participating countries. In Serbia, microplastics in drinking water sources are monitored in two pilot areas: the „Pavliš“ source (intergranular aquifer) and the „Staničenje“ source (river bank filtration).

Results: The initial sampling campaign revealed several challenges. Excessive interference probably caused by rubber particles from the hoses. The filter mesh was partially damaged or deformed due to excessive water pressure (and/or transport and handling), causing changes in the pore sizes and allowing particles larger than 20 µm to pass. Furthermore, local laboratories reported discrepancies in microplastics analysis results for duplicate samples (the same water sample). A high number of microplastic particles were unexpectedly found in the blank control sample, indicating potential impairments of the filter cascade functionality and/or contamination issues.

Conclusions: To address these problems, the project team proposed and implemented several solutions, such as recommending the flushing of rubber sampling hoses before use or replacing them with silicone or metal alternatives, as well as carefully controlling the water flow rate to prevent filter damage and implementing more rigorous cleaning protocols for the filters (using an ultrasonic bath and rinsing equipment with pre-filtered deionized water). The team also suggested using alternative types of filters to improve data reliability and reduce the risk of contamination. These refinements aim to improve the accuracy and consistency of future microplastics monitoring efforts in drinking water sources.

[1] <https://interreg-danube.eu/projects/microdrink>

[2] https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_del/2024/1441/oj/eng

Microplastic, MicroDrink project, Drinking water, Danube River Basin

Development of a protocol for extracting nanoplastics from agricultural soils using metal-doped nanoplastics

Pia Leban^{1,2}, Quynh Nhu Phan Le³, Milica Velimirovic³, Kristof Tirez³, Janja Vidmar^{1,2}

¹Department of Environmental Sciences, Jožef Stefan Institute, Jamova cesta 39, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

²Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School, Jamova cesta 39, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

³Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO), Boeretang 200, 2400 Mol, Belgium

Background

- **Nanoplastics (NPs)** are emerging environmental pollutants in agricultural soils due to the extensive use of plastics in farming.
- Extraction and quantification of NPs by conventional techniques is limited by their **small size, complex composition and interactions with soil particles** (aggregation and/or adsorption).
- **Single Particle ICP-MS (spICP-MS)** offers a promising strategy for method development, enabling **sensitive detection and quantitative assessment of extraction recovery for particle-by-particle analysis of metal-doped plastics**.

Objectives

Develop an extraction protocol for nanoplastics from soil using 198 nm europium-doped polystyrene nanoparticles (PS-Eu NPs).

Materials and Methods

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Recoveries of particle number concentration, particle mass concentration, and mean particle mass determined by spICP-MS were evaluated by comparing the PS-Eu NPs extracted from different soil types to the expected values in the spiked samples. Extraction recoveries were determined for sample aliquots collected at various stages of the extraction protocol. Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation of three replicates.

Soil type	Particle number concentration recovery (%)			Particle mass concentration recovery (%)			Mean particle mass recovery (%)		
	Supernatant before centrifugation	Supernatant after centrifugation	Supernatant after H ₂ O ₂ treatment	Supernatant before centrifugation	Supernatant after centrifugation	Supernatant after H ₂ O ₂ treatment	Supernatant before centrifugation	Supernatant after centrifugation	Supernatant after H ₂ O ₂ treatment
Loamy sand	86 ± 5	86 ± 6	95 ± 9	89 ± 9	84 ± 4	95 ± 8	99 ± 3	99 ± 3	99 ± 3
Clay loam	66 ± 6	65 ± 8	71 ± 10	70 ± 5	70 ± 5	81 ± 8	107 ± 4	106 ± 4	99 ± 3
Silt clay	58 ± 2	58 ± 5	59 ± 3	65 ± 2	61 ± 5	64 ± 2	106 ± 2	106 ± 0	99 ± 3

Figure 1. Size distribution histograms of Eu-doped PS NPs (bin size 10 nm). (A) Reference standard in aqueous solution, PS-Eu NPs in different aliquots extracted from (B) loamy sands, (C) clay loam, and (D) silt clay.

- ☑ The soil type influenced PS-Eu NPs extraction recoveries. Loamy sand exhibited the highest recoveries, followed by clay loam and silt clay.
- ☑ spICP-MS analysis showed that the Eu mass per particle remained constant across samples, suggesting no significant leaching or aggregation of the metal tracer.
- 📊 The particle size distributions are similar between the soil type, sample aliquots, collected at different stages of the extraction protocol, and comparable to the reference PS-Eu NPs standard. These results indicate that the extraction procedure likely did not alter particle integrity.

Future work

- We will apply this protocol to various NPs polymer types and sizes, with subsequent identification and quantification performed using pyrolysis-GC-MS.
- This approach will contribute to the development of a more comprehensive and standardized methodology for assessing NPs contamination in soils.

Detection and Isolation of Microplastics from Chicken Feces

Anja Klančnik¹, Živa Kolenc¹, Krištof Kepić¹, Majda Golob², Manca Kovač Viršek³

¹University of Ljubljana, Biotechnical faculty, Ljubljana, Slovenia

²University of Ljubljana, Veterinary Faculty, Ljubljana, Slovenia

³National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana, Slovenia

*anja.klancnik@bf.uni-lj.si

BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Plastics are synthetic or semi-synthetic materials produced by the polymerization of organic carbon compounds. Microplastics (MP), polymer particles smaller than 5 mm, are widespread in the environment and can enter the food chain through water, soil, and feed, potentially affecting animal and human health (1). **Poultry may be exposed to MP via feed and drinking water, resulting in their excretion in feces.**

MP in the environment have negative impacts due to: (i) their persistence; (ii) their presence in the food chain of animals; (iii) their penetration into tissues through food consumption; (iv) chemical pollution caused by toxic plastic additives, such as endocrine disruptors; and (v) the transfer of other pollutants, as they can bind phthalates, alkylphenols, metals, persistent organic pollutants, or invasive species of microorganisms (2, 3).

The objective of this study was to develop and validate a reliable method for isolating and identifying MP from chicken feces and to determine their occurrence on Slovenian poultry farms.

References: (1) Wagner in Lambert, *Environ Chem* 2017, 1-23; (2) Dris in sod., *Environ Chem* 2015, 12: 592-599; (3) Kolenc in sod., *STOTEN*, 949, 175130, 1-7.

Figure 1. The figure illustrates the key phases of microplastic detection in tissue: sampling, isolation, filtration, and characterization. It also shows a filter with isolated particles selected for FTIR analysis. Marked points indicate measurement locations on the Rapt-IR FTIR microscope, used to determine the polymer composition of individual microplastic particles.

SAMPLES AND METHODS

140 CHICKEN FECES SAMPLES FROM 14 FARMS

Figure 2. Samples and optimized method for the detection and quantification of MP from chicken feces.

We developed a method for isolation of microplastic (MP) from poultry feces. For quality assurance, most plastic tools were excluded and replaced by glassware, cleaned with MilliQ water, work was performed in the laminar flow box, white cotton clothes were worn and nitrile gloves were used.

Poultry caeca were previously frozen at -20 °C and thawed in the fridge overnight for MP isolation. From each sample of caeca, fat tissue was removed using scissors, tweezers, and a scalpel. Each sample was transferred into an Erlenmeyer flask and weighed, followed by digestion in 10% KOH with a ratio of 5:1 (V/w).

The flasks were covered with gauze, parafilm and aluminium foil, leaving a small hole to allow gas exchange, and incubated for 48 hours (37 °C and 80 RPM). After 48 hours, the samples were filtered using a vacuum filter system and 60 µm nylon net filter. The filter cake was washed with 70% ethanol and stored in a glass petri dish at -20 °C awaiting microscopic analysis.

Figure 3. Sample preparation and digestion.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Results: A total of 57 MP particles were isolated from chicken feces. Using stereomicroscope images, we assessed the visual characteristics of the microplastics. Three shapes were identified: fibers, fragments, and films. Fragments were most common (n=29), followed by fibers (n=26) and films (n=2). Particle sizes ranged from 0.107 mm to 5.038 mm. Microplastics were grouped by size into 1000-4999 µm (n=24), 300-999 µm (n=17), and 100-299 µm (n=16). Of the 57 isolated microplastic particles, most were blue (n=30), followed by white (n=16), black (n=3), and others (n=8; pink, green, grey, red, brown). Transparency was nearly evenly distributed, with 28 transparent and 29 non-transparent particles.

Conclusions: The identified polymers included polypropylene as the most frequent, followed by polyethylene and other types. The particles varied in shape, color, and transparency, indicating multiple potential sources of contamination. **This study confirms the presence of MP in chicken feces and provides a validated protocol for their isolation and characterization.** The findings suggest that poultry can serve as bioindicators of environmental MP contamination, emphasizing the need for further monitoring and mitigation strategies in the food production chain.

Figure 4: From 140 fecal samples, 193 particles were isolated, of which 57 were identified as microplastics. The identified microplastics were mainly characterized as polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET). The majority of detected fragments were blue in color.

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Fenton oxidation of municipal wastewater for microplastic analysis

D. Argyropoulou^{1*}, A. Galani¹, C. Noutsopoulos¹, D. Mamais¹, S. Malamis¹

¹ Sanitary Engineering Laboratory, School of Civil Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece

*Corresponding author: d_argyropoulou@mail.ntua.gr

Background

Micro-spectroscopic techniques, such as μ Raman, have recently been standardized for analyzing microplastics in clean water samples [1]. However, sample preparation methods for complex matrices have yet to be standardized and efficient pre-treatment remains crucial for achieving reliable spectral information and shorter analysis times [2], [3]. This study investigates the removal of organic matter from municipal wastewater with Fenton's reagent for subsequent microplastics analysis.

Method

Influent wastewater (WW_{in}) after the pre-treatment stage was sampled and filtered with stainless-steel sieves. To determine the optimum reaction conditions, the removal of organic matter from wastewater was measured under different doses of H_2O_2 and ferrous catalyst.

Reaction Efficiency

$$\text{Mass removal (\%)} = \left(1 - \frac{\text{mass after digestion}}{\text{mass before digestion}}\right) \cdot 100$$

Reaction Conditions

- Hydrogen peroxide / Suspended solids ratio: 0,4–2,4 $g_{H_2O_2}/mg_{SS}$
- $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ dose: 1,6–3,7 $mg_{cat}/g_{H_2O_2}$
- 30-minute reaction time
- Initial 3-min heating at 35°C to accelerate the reaction

Microplastic Analysis

Following Fenton digestion at the optimal reagent doses, density separation with a $ZnCl_2$ solution and an acidification step, samples were analyzed with μ Raman spectroscopy and a Particle Analysis software (InVia Qontor, Renishaw UK).

Figure 3. μ Raman analysis of a WW_{in} subsample (50–100 μ m sieve fraction). LWD objectives: 5x (image), 50x (spectral acquisition). Laser: 785nm, 3mW.

Results

The results showed that:

- 1,2 $g_{H_2O_2}/mg_{SS}$ & 3 $mg_{cat}/g_{H_2O_2}$ ensured 93,6 \pm 1,4% mass removal from the WW_{in} (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. Mass removal from WW_{in} by Fenton oxidation vs. (i) H_2O_2 dose, (ii) catalyst dose.

- The exothermic reaction is usually complete within approximately 20 minutes. Temperature increase depended on the reagent doses (Fig. 2)

Figure 2. T vs. t of Fenton reaction for various doses of (i) H_2O_2 and (ii) ferrous catalyst.

- Lower mass removal was observed with 35% H_2O_2 (Fig. 1.i). A possible reason may be the presence of stabilizers that could affect hydroxyl radical formation, delaying oxidation in the given 30-minute reaction time, and/or interact with the catalyst species
- μ Raman analysis revealed multiple microplastic particles in a WW_{in} subsample (Fig. 3).

Conclusions

- Fenton is confirmed as a fast and dependable method for organic matter removal from municipal wastewater
- A simple way to estimate chemical dosing for Fenton oxidation is suggested, depending on the suspended solids concentration of municipal wastewater.

Acknowledgement

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Isolation and detection of large microplastics from fish intestines

Tomislav Kačarević, Sandra Jakšić, Milica Živkov Baloš, Jelena Petrović and Radomir Ratajac

Scientific Veterinary Institute "Novi Sad", Rumenacki put 20, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia, tomislav.k@niv.ns.ac.rs

INTRODUCTION

Microplastic particles in surface waters pose a significant ecological risk to aquatic ecosystems. These particles accumulate in fish through feeding, leading to tissue damage, metabolic disturbances, and reduced reproductive capacity.

This study aimed to assess the efficiency of isolating large microplastics from fish intestines and to evaluate the effect of KOH digestion on three common polymer types. Additionally, the method was applied to detect microplastics in fish intestines from the Danube-Tisa-Danube Canal using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy.

Sampling points

EXPERIMENTAL

Validation study- blank and spiked trout samples

Examination of fish intestines from the Canal

RESULTS

ATR-FTIR spectrum of PET before and after digestion

One of the ATR-FTIR spectra of a suspect particle from fish intestines

ATR-FTIR spectrum of PE before and after digestion

ATR-FTIR spectrum of PP before and after digestion

- The digestion method effectively decomposed the organic material in trout intestines.
- In spiked trout samples containing 10 pieces (1–5 mm) of polyethylene, polypropylene, and polyethylene terephthalate, a 100% recovery rate was achieved.
- Recorded spectra before and after digestion confirmed the stability of all polymers.
- No large microplastics were detected in fish intestines from the Canal.
- Differences in intestinal content were observed between pike and carp; pike contained undigested fish remains, while carp samples showed inorganic residues such as calcium carbonate from Canal sediment or the remains of glass filter.

CONCLUSION

- The applied digestion and ATR-FTIR identification method proved effective for analyzing large microplastics (1–5 mm) in fish intestines.
- Method improvement through density-based separation is recommended due to the high inorganic content in Canal fish samples.

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MUSSEL TISSUE DIGESTION PROTOCOLS: EFFICIENCY AND EFFECTS ON MICROPLASTICS

S. H. Turmanova, Y. H. Hristov, D. S. Kiryakova, A. N. Dimitrov, E.D. Ivanova, P. V. Atanasova, G. R. Kolchakova, A. S. Ilicva, E. Y. Mollova, N. S. Todorov

Burgas State University „Prof. Dr. Assen Zlatarov“, Y. Yakimov Str. 1, Burgas 8010, Bulgaria

Microplastics (MPs) are emerging pollutants in marine ecosystems, and filter-feeding mussels are widely used as bioindicators. A key step in MP analysis is tissue removal without altering plastics. This study compares three commonly applied digestion protocols – enzymatic, acidic, and alkaline – on lyophilized and frozen mussel samples (*M. galloprovincialis*) from Burgas Bay, Black Sea. Digestion efficiency was assessed and the effects of treatments on four typical representatives of microplastics were evaluated.

Protocols for the digestion of biota mussel *Mytilus galloprovincialis*

Assessment of the Effects of Digestion Protocols on Polymers

Hit Quality Index values for the analyzed polymers

Plastic type	HQI values, %		
	Digestion Method		
	Enzymatic	Acidic	Alkaline
HDPE	99.98	99.29	99.55
PA	99.99	93.68	99.77
PET	99.74	99.69	98.85
PVC	98.83	95.39	99.56

Conclusions

The results obtained show that all three approaches achieve a high degree of organic matter removal of over 96%. From the ATR-FTIR analysis and the calculated HQI values, it was found that the Enzymatic and Alkaline protocols are compatible with all analyzed polymers, as they preserve their chemical integrity and allow reliable subsequent identification of microplastics. The highest chemical resistance was demonstrated by HDPE, while PA was found to be the most sensitive to acidic treatment.

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Nonlinear optical imaging and Nile Red staining approaches for microplastic detection: Influence of additives and structural modifications

Milica Popović¹, Mira Aničić Urošević², Aleksandar Popović², Milica Čurčić¹, Mihailo D. Rabasović¹, Tanja Pajić³, Aleksandar Krmpot¹

¹Institute of Physics Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia

³University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology, Belgrade, Serbia

UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE
FACULTY OF CHEMISTRY

FACULTY OF BIOLOGY
UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE

INTRODUCTION

Microplastics (MPs) are recognized as emerging environmental pollutants, yet standardized detection methods are still lacking due to their variable shapes, chemical compositions, and presence of various additives. Nile Red (NR) staining has been proposed as a rapid fluorescence-based detection technique, but its performance may vary with particle properties. In this study, nonlinear optical imaging combined with NR staining was employed to examine the optical responses of reference polymers and consumer-derived MPs, with the goal of evaluating how particle size, additives, and structural modifications affect polymer fluorescence and the reliability of NR-based detection.

METHODOLOGY

Three reference polymers: high-density polyethylene (HDPE), polystyrene (PS), and polypropylene (PP), were examined using NLSM modalities: two-photon excitation fluorescence (TPEF) and third harmonic generation (THG).

Fluorescence spectra were recorded upon excitation at three different wavelengths: 730, 800, and 1040 nm, before and after NR staining.

The same procedure was applied to MPs (<50 μm) obtained by grinding plastic packaging materials aiming to assess the influence of particle size, additives, and structural modifications to polymers' fluorescence.

- 1 μg mL⁻¹ of NR in methanol
- 15 min at 60 °C
- dark incubation

RESULTS

Reference polymers exhibited negligible autofluorescence at all excitation wavelengths, whereas NR stained polymers induced strong fluorescence responses:

Excitation wavelength: 730 nm
Emission filter: 700 sp

filter 500-550 sp
filter 550-600 sp

Emission spectra of NR stained reference polymers show a clear shift of emission maximum compared to pure NR, indicating distinct dye-polymer interactions. By selecting appropriate emission filter based on the known spectra, specific polymers can be selectively detected in mixed samples.

Strong THG signals observed for both reference plastics (1) and product-derived MPs (2)

CONCLUSION

While NR staining efficiently induced fluorescence in pure polymers, its performance on commercial MPs was limited, indicating the influence of particle size, additives, and structural changes on dye binding. Consistently strong THG signals highlight the potential of this label-free technique for MP detection in environmental samples.

1. Introduction

Microplastics (MPs) are emerging pollutants, ubiquitous in the environment, for which standardized methods of analysis have not yet been established [1]. Micro-FTIR is a non-destructive technique applied in the analysis of MPs extracted from various matrices [2]. The advantage of using this type of method is that it allows for the morphological characterization of MPs (e.g., shape, size). The main objective of this study is to optimize the parameters of microplastics analysis methods using the Spotlight 400 FT-IR Imaging System, PerkinElmer, which is part of the REXDAN Research Infrastructure at "Dunarea de Jos" University of Galati, Romania. Thus, both microplastic particles from certified reference materials for polyethylene and polypropylene polymers and MPs samples taken from the Danube River were analyzed. Various filters, including polycarbonate gold-coated (Au), aluminum oxide (Al) and polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) membranes, were tested on the surface of which MPs were scanned using a microscope.

2. Material and methods

Figure 1. Micro-FTIR Spotlight 400, Perkin Elmer

Figure 2. Certified Reference Material - Polyethylene and polypropylene

Figure 3. Filters used in the analysis

Method parameters: Reflectance mode; Resolution of 32 cm⁻¹; Spatial resolution of 6.25 μm; Speed: 2.2; Spectral range between 4000 - 750 cm⁻¹

3. Results and discussion

Figure 4. Spectral image of PE and PP on Al filter

Figure 5. FT-IR spectra of background - Al

Figure 6. FT-IR spectra of PE - Al

Figure 7. FT-IR spectra of PP - Al

Figure 8. Spectral image of PE and PP on PVDF filter

Figure 9. FT-IR spectra of background - PVDF

Figure 10. FT-IR spectra of PE - PVDF

Figure 11. FT-IR spectra of PP - PVDF

Figure 12. Spectral image of PE and PP on Au filter

Figure 13. FT-IR spectra of background - Au

Figure 14. FT-IR spectra of PE - Au

Figure 15. FT-IR spectra of PP - Au

4. Conclusions

Based on the tests performed, advantages and disadvantages were identified for each filter analysed, with the polycarbonate gold-coated and aluminum oxide filters being the most suitable in terms of accuracy results, and the PVDF filter in terms of cost-effectiveness.

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Quantification of polyethylene in soils using Py-GC/MS: A comprehensive assessment of matrix interference and plastic weathering effects

Quynh Nhu Phan Le¹, Janja Vidmar², Pia Leban², Dimitrios Savvas³, Vasileios Papisotriopoulos³, Milica Velimirovic¹

¹ Laboratory for inorganic and organic analysis, Flemish Institute for Technological Research, Mol, Belgium

² Department of Environmental Sciences, Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

³ Department of Crop Science, Agricultural University of Athens, Athens, Greece

nhu.phan@vito.be

1. BACKGROUND

- Microplastic contamination in soils is increasing, with polyethylene (PE) identified as a major contributor, especially through agricultural application of conventional mulching.
- Extraction and identification of PE using Py-GC/MS are feasible, but quality assurance remains limited, particularly for smaller and weathered particles and the risk of false-positive
- This study investigates the influence of soil matrix composition and polymer weathering on Py-GC/MS performance, aiming to reduce false positives and, using PE as a model polymer, support method development and standardization for other plastics.

2. METHODOLOGY

3. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

4. SUMMARY

1. Weathered PE showed a different oligomer distribution, with a decrease in longer-chain oligomers (e.g., C₂₅) and an increase in shorter ones (C₁₄-C₁₅).
2. Weathered PE was more difficult to extract than pristine PE from mulch film, possibly due to greater susceptibility to chemical digestion and decrease in method sensitivity (calibration slope)
3. Soil extracts contributed variably to oligomer signals, with particularly higher intensities for C₁₁ and C₁₉-C₂₂; these oligomers should therefore be avoided for quantification.

5. FUTURE WORK

- Double-shot analysis mode
- Heart-cut analysis mode
- Identify the analysis mode that minimize false positives in PE quantification

Introduction

Microplastic (MP) contamination in wastewater systems has become a critical environmental concern due to its persistence and potential ecological impacts. Plastic particles in wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) are mostly originating from sources such as personal care products, synthetic textiles and industrial effluents. WWTPs act as both sinks and potential pathways for these particles, retaining a significant portion in sludge while also allowing a fraction to be released into receiving water bodies. Sewage sludge, as a by-product of wastewater treatment, is a complex matrix rich in organic matter and other substances, making the isolation and characterization challenging.

This study aimed to extract and characterize microplastics from sludge collected from WWTPs employing distinct treatment technologies, focusing on particle size, shape, color and number of particles.

Results

- Fragments, fibers and films were the main types of MPs identified in both WWTP regardless of particles density.
- In small-scale WWTP sludge when distilled water was used for density separation sphere-shaped microplastic particles occupied as about 4 times more than in other samples.

Figure 1 Shape distribution of microplastic particles extracted from sewage sludge. Particles shape of: A – low-density ($\leq 1 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) microplastics; B – high-density ($\leq 1.53 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) microplastics

Figure 2 Color distribution of microplastic particles extracted from sewage sludge. Particles colors of: A – low-density ($\leq 1 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) microplastics; B – high-density ($\leq 1.53 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) microplastics

In small-scale and large-scale WWTP sewage sludge transparent microplastics in low density solution (1 g cm^{-3}) takes approximately 50 % and 52 % respectively, in higher density solution (1.53 g cm^{-3}) the percentage is lower – approximately 28 % and 39 %.

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Methodology

Figure 3 The length of microplastic particles isolated from different scale WWTP sewage sludge. A – particle size of low-density ($\leq 1 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) microplastics; B – particle size of high-density ($\leq 1.53 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$) microplastics

- In the small-scale WWTP particles with a size ranging from 30 μm to 1 mm occupy about 80 % of all identified particles.
- The same trend is observed in the sludge of a large-scale WWTP, however the distribution is more uniform.

So what?

- Most abundant color – transparent followed by white and yellow
- The shape – fragment followed by fibers
- Sewage sludge from small-scale WWTP contained approximately 12 % more MP particles ranging in size from 0.03 μm to 1 mm compared to large-scale WWTP.
- These findings raise a new research question about the influence of WWTP size, equipment and treated wastewater volume on microplastic fragmentation.

Variation in microplastic size ratios in swine and poultry feed mixtures

Mislav Đidara¹, Marcela Šperanda¹, Brigita Popović¹, Darko Kerovec¹ and Daria Petrović¹

¹Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences Osijek, University of Josip Juraj Strossmayer in Osijek, Vladimira Preloga 1, Osijek, Croatia (mđidara@fazos.hr)

Background & Objectives

- Microplastics are increasingly recognized as contaminants of concern in animal production systems due to their negative effects on digestive physiology, potential for bioaccumulation and associated health risks.
- While the LUMOS II system enables reliable polymer identification, its precision decreases substantially for particles below 20 μm , limiting accurate detection of the smallest microplastics.

- Chi-square tests confirmed these differences as statistically significant ($\chi^2(1) = 13.72$, $p < 0.001$ for 1-pixel; $\chi^2(1) = 9.28$, $p = 0.0023$ for ≤ 3 pixels).

Ratios of larger (>1 px) to smaller (1 px) particles in different feed type

Group	Category	Category	Totals
Count	Swine feed	> 1 px	1572
		1 px	461
Percent			2033
Count	Poultry feed	> 1 px	440
		1 px	188
Percent			628
Count		All Groups	2012
			649
			2661

Pearson Chi-square: 13,7150, df=1, p=,000213

Ratios of larger (>3 px) to smaller (≤ 3 px) particles in different feed type

Group	Category	Category	Totals
Count	Swine feed	> 3 px	1064
		≤ 3 px	969
Percent			2033
Count	Poultry feed	> 3 px	285
		≤ 3 px	343
Percent			628
Count		All Groups	1349
			1312
			2661

Pearson Chi-square: 9,28327, df=1, p=,002313

Methods

- In this study, we analyzed microplastic content in swine (n=6) and poultry (n=6) commercial feed sold in Croatia, using a LUMOS II FTIR microscope with FPA detector and Purity software.
- Feed samples were digested with 10% KOH at 60 °C for 24 h, followed by repeated Fenton oxidation, with both steps accompanied by filtration and rinsing to isolate microplastics.
- We compared the ratio of small particles (1 pixel $\approx 10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ and up to 3 pixels) to larger particles across feed types using Pearson's Chi-square test of independence, thereby estimating the fraction of microplastics potentially overlooked if small particles were excluded from counts.

Results

- Our results revealed significant differences in size distributions between swine and poultry feed.
- Larger particles accounted for 77.3% of the total in swine feed compared to 70.1% in poultry feed, when 1 pixel particles were included in the „small” category.
- When particles up to 3 pixels were included in the “small” category, larger particle ratios were 52.3% and 45.4%, respectively.

Conclusions

- Microplastics are abundant in both swine and poultry feed, with the smallest size fractions representing a critical share of the total.
- These findings demonstrate that excluding the smallest size fraction would systematically bias results, leading to underestimation of microplastic contamination, particularly in poultry feed.
- The study underscores the importance of methodological refinement for reliable quantification of microplastics and highlights the need to consider particle size distribution when evaluating exposure risks in animal health.

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Microplastics in soil: Are smaller particles lost during the extraction process?

Diana Nantege¹, Sarmite Kernchen¹, Martin G. J. Löder¹, Christian Laforsch¹
¹Animal Ecology I and BayCEER, University of Bayreuth, Bayreuth, Germany

Introduction

To assess exposure levels and potential risks associated with microplastics (MPs) pollution, accurate MP quantification in environmental samples is required. This necessitates the use of reliable and fully validated analytical methods. These typically involve complex, multi-step procedures that pose risk of contamination and especially MP particle loss. While contamination can be reduced by effective strategies, recovery studies are one of the most important quality control measures that involve spiking soils with known quantities of reference MP particles. However, most existing studies focus on relatively large particles (>100 µm), often neglecting the smaller size fractions that are more abundant, environmentally relevant and potentially more hazardous.

Aim: To evaluate the recovery efficiency of MPs across a range of particle sizes, down to 10 µm using typical soil extraction and purification procedures, and identify the steps that contribute most to MP loss.

Material & Methods

Protocol for recovery experiment

Test material:

- ✓ Fluorescent polyethylene (PE) beads
- ✓ Sizes: 10-20; 32-38; 53-63; 90-106 µm diameter
- ✓ LUFA 2.2 standard soil as environmental matrix
- ✓ 10 µm stainless-steel sieves for filtering steps

Two density separation (DS) methods evaluated:

- ✓ Scooping technique and separatory funnels

Fluorescent images taken using a Leica M205 FCA

- ✓ Particles counted at each step of extraction/purification

Results

Total MP Recovery

- The smaller the MP size, the lower the recovery
- More MPs are recovered when scooping is used for density separation

MP Losses at Different Steps

- Large MPs low losses
- Smaller MPs are lost at all steps with both methods
- Higher loss using separatory funnels (DS)

Discussion: Key mechanisms of MP loss

Sediment

1. MPs remained trapped in sediments, even after four cycles of density separation

Stainless-steel Filter

2. Particles became lodged within the stainless-steel filter aperture
3. Splashing and adhesion to equipment during the process

Conclusion

- Microplastics losses increase with decreasing particle size which may partly explain the lower counts of smaller MPs frequently detected in environmental soils samples
- General validity of results: Procedural steps as investigated here are commonly used across different sample matrices, the losses observed during these steps are likely to occur consistently during analysis of similar samples
- Important: Inclusion of smaller MP particle size during recovery rates for assessment of reliability of data

Artificial Intelligence –Satellite Synergy for Multi-Year Detection of Coastal Plastic Hotspots in Santo Domingo

V.C. Shruti¹, Gurusamy Kutralam-Muniasamy², Fermín Pérez-Guevara¹, Ricardo Cuenca Alvarez²

¹Department of Biotechnology and Bioengineering, CINVESTAV-IPN, Av IPN 2508, San Pedro Zacatenco, GAM, 07360, CDMX, México
²CIITEC - IPN. Centro de Investigación e Innovación Tecnológica. Cda. de Cecati s/n, Santa Catarina, Azcapotzalco, 02250, CDMX, México
shruti.venkata@cinvestav.mx

Background & Objectives

- **Coastal hotspots as microplastics sinks:** river discharge and coastal currents concentrate floating plastics into confined nearshore zones, where macroplastics fragment into persistent micro- and nano- plastics.
- **2018 Wake-Up Call:** Massive plastic surge at Santo Domingo's Ozama river mouth revealed urgent monitoring needs
- **Traditional monitoring limits:** expensive, infrequent, lacks full spatial coverage
- **The opportunity:** Satellites + AI enable scalable, frequent and cost effective plastic hotspot detection
- **Study goal:** Analyze Sentinel 2 imagery with machine learning to:
 - Identify and track hotspot locations
 - Detect persistent accumulation patterns
 - Support proactive pollution management

Methods

Results

Classified Maps

Overall Confusion Matrix (2020-2025)

Actual Class \ Predicted Class	Background	Water	Plastics	Wood	Seaweed	Pumice	Sea Snot	Sea Foam	Land
Land	248	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sea Foam	4	4	3	3	6	108	0	0	0
Sea Snot	5	0	0	0	104	4	0	0	0
Plastics	0	0	91	4	0	0	0	0	0
Seaweed	0	0	145	0	0	0	0	0	0
Wood	1	1	51	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pumice	3	189	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Water	106	3	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Background	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Coastal Plastic Hotspots

- **High classification accuracy:** Achieved 95% overall accuracy for multi-year monitoring (2020–2025).
- **Strong detection for plastics:** Producer's accuracy = 95%, User's accuracy > 95%.
- **Persistent major hotspot:** Ozama River mouth repeatedly detected as a key accumulation area.
- **Spatial variability:** Secondary hotspots shifted location and intensity across different years.
- **Source linkage:** Hotspots closely associated with riverine inputs and coastal human activity.
- **Urban & industrial influence:** Concentrations highest near densely populated and industrial shorelines.

Conclusions

- Remote sensing + AI works** – Machine learning with Sentinel-2 data accurately detected multi-year plastic hotspots along the Santo Domingo coast.
- Persistent hotspot identified** – The Ozama River mouth remained a consistent plastic accumulation zone from 2020–2025.
- Microplastic risk zones** – Hotspots align with areas where macroplastics likely fragment into microplastics due to wave action and river discharge.
- Management priority areas** – Findings provide spatial targets for cleanup and source-reduction strategies.
- Scalable approach** – Method can be applied to other microplastic-impacted coasts globally for continuous monitoring.

Acknowledgments

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Assessment of Microplastics Particles Composition in Raw and Treated Wastewater and River Water

Małgorzata Komorowska-Kaufman¹, Katarzyna Jaszczyszyn^{2,1}, Edyta Kiedrzyńska^{2,3}

¹ Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Energy, Poznan, Poland,

² European Regional Centre for Ecohydrology of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Lodz, Poland

³ University of Lodz, Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, UNESCO Chair on Ecohydrology and Applied Ecology, Poland

malgorzata.komorowska-kaufman@put.poznan.pl

Background & Objectives: The presence of microplastics (MPs) in the environment in recent decades has become a significant issue, especially because their toxic impact on living organisms has been documented. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are considered as one of the main point sources of this pollution, thus increasing MPs removal during wastewater treatment is crucial. This research aimed to determine the quantity and quality of MPs found in typical urban wastewater at various treatment stages and in the receiver (river).

Methods: Wastewater samples were collected at the inlet, after mechanical treatment, and after biological treatment at the urban WWTP (PE 45,000) situated in central Poland (Fig.1). River water samples were collected in the river stream, approximately 21 km downstream from the treated wastewater discharge, in the centre of a large city. Organic and mineral matter was eliminated with chemical and physical extraction, and μ -FTIR spectroscopy was used for MPs analysis (Fig.2).

Fig.1. Sampling locations.

Fig.3. MPs in analysed samples of raw wastewater (RWW), mechanically treated wastewater (MTWW), biologically treated wastewater (TW) and river water (RIVER): filter surface overviews of the filtrate >250 μ m (a) and 32-250 μ m (b); and composition of polymer types (c) and particle sizes in μ m (d).

Conclusions: Properly operated WWTPs can effectively eliminate substantial amounts of microplastics. The mechanism of this removal is varied, partially it is based on MPs degradation and fragmentation, which may increase the number of particles not detected by the selected analytical approach, specifically those under 20 μ m. Although WWTPs are known and controllable source of microplastics, it is also important to identify and reduce uncontrolled sources of this contamination.

Acknowledgments

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Fig.2. Analytical procedure a) two-step sieving; b) sample extraction H_2O_2 , temperature+time; c) filtering through silicon membrane filters 1μ m; d) micro-FTIR analysis (Nicolet IN10, Thermo Fisher).

Results (Fig.3):

- RWW contained the higher amount of microplastics particles (MPs) of varying shapes, chemical composition, and colors.
- The quantity of MPs diminished in the treated wastewater and the particle morphology also changed, with gray fibers predominating.
- MPs particle removal efficiency within the tested particle size range (>20 μ m) was very high (98-99%). Most of MPs were removed at biological treatment step.
- PE, PVC and PU particles dominated in all samples. Their total share was from 78.7% to 90.1%, however, the amount of PU was significantly higher in the river water sample.
- A greater proportion of MPs above 100 μ m was observed in the untreated wastewater. In the effluent and river water, smaller particles predominated.

Avoidance behavior of *Lumbricus terrestris* (Oligochaeta: Lumbricidae) induced by polyethylene microplastics

Ana Lazić¹, Milica Baloš², Aleksandra Petrović¹, Ivana Ivanović¹, Vojislava Bursić¹, Dejan Prvulović¹, Aleksandra Tubić³

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Environmental and Plant Protection, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

²Agrounik d.o.o., Zemun, Republic of Serbia

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia

aleksandra.petrovic@poli.edu.rs

Introduction

Microplastics have become emerging contaminants in agricultural soils, where they may affect soil biota and essential ecosystem processes. As a key bioindicator species, *Lumbricus terrestris* is suitable for evaluating how such pollutants influence soil habitats.

This study examines the avoidance behavior of *L. terrestris* in response to polyethylene microplastic particles using a standardized four-compartment soil avoidance test.

Materials and Methods

The experiment followed the SRPS EN ISO 17512-1 guideline using soil (1 kg per replicate) amended with polyethylene microplastics derived from shredded mulch films at three concentrations (0.25%, 0.5%, and 0.75% w/w).

L. terrestris worms were introduced into four-compartment test containers and maintained for 48 hours under controlled laboratory conditions without feeding or irrigation. After exposure, worms were counted in each compartment according to predefined criteria for intact and injured individuals. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and Fisher's LSD test to evaluate differences in avoidance behavior among treatments.

Table 1. Average number of worms and avoidance percentage

Concentration (%)	Number of <i>L. terrestris</i>		Number of worms at the end of the experiment	A (%)
	Soil with MP	Soil without MP		
0,25	3,6	6,2	9,8	26,67
0,5	2,9	6,1	9,0	36,22
0,75	1,3	6,3	7,6	53,17%

Results

The strongest avoidance response (53.17%) and highest mortality (10%) were recorded at 0.75% microplastic concentration. ANOVA confirmed a significant statistical difference between treated and untreated chambers ($p=0.000000$ for $p<0.01$) although no significant differences were detected among the tested concentrations (0.25%, 0.5%, and 0.75%; $p=0.931227$ for $p < 0.05$).

Graphic 1. Statistical difference between chambers depending on microplastic content

Conclusion

These findings suggest that microplastics in soil can elicit strong avoidance behavior and elevate mortality in *L. terrestris*, potentially impairing soil functionality. Furthermore, the obtained results emphasize the ecological relevance of standardized tests as an early warning indicator of soil contamination. The observed effects underline the potential threat microplastics pose to soil biodiversity and ecosystem stability, reinforcing the need for further research into their long-term environmental consequences as well as for human health.

Acknowledgments

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Biodegradable plastic mulch performance and degradation in real field conditions, case Slovenia

Kristina Ugrinovič¹, Karin Hriberšek², and Mojca Bavcon Kralj²

¹Agricultural Institute of Slovenia, Hacquetova ulica 17, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

²University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Health Sciences, Zdravstvena pot 5, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia
contact: kristina.ugrinovic@kis.si

Objective

To assess the degradation/accumulation dynamics of biodegradable (BD) plastic mulch films (MF) in soil at continuous use under the real field conditions and their impact on crops and soil in a long term.

Background

BD plastic MF are designed: -> to be tilled into the soil where microorganisms are expected to use the mulch polymers [1];
-> to avoid waste generation and cut the time and cost of handling the conventional MF.
Only few studies report of complete biodegradation of BD plastic MF in real field conditions.
The tilling of BD MF into the soil, to facilitate biodegradation, is an open door to potential environmental impacts [2].

Materials and methods

Long term field trial in vegetable rotation. 4 commercially available BD MF (2 thermoplastic starch (TPS), 2 polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT)+ polylactic acid (PLA), standard low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and uncovered control. 2 regions of Slovenia on 2 soil types. Since 2022.

Monitoring of
-> MF performance,
-> crops performance,
-> influence of MF on soil properties.

Soil sampling for monitoring of (BD) microplastics formation and further extraction.

Results

The BD MF are less effective at weed suppressing than LDPE film. Weed problems are particularly evident in slow-growing crops and plants that do not cover the soil well.

The early development of plants is, in most cases, the fastest on the LDPE, slightly slower or the same on BD films and the slowest on bare soil. There are no major differences between different BD films.
For zucchini, initial development affects the early yield, which is the lowest on bare soil and the highest on LDPE film. The total yield either does not differ between the treatments or is lower on uncovered soil than on soil covered with LDPE or BD films.

Several macro plastic fragments of BD MF are still present at the time of soil cultivation in the spring after the use of BD MF.

First attempt to determine the plastic MF fragments in soil samples proved challenging, anyhow the highest mass of plastic fragments was determined in the group of films composed of TPS, followed by PBAT/PLA, and finally, LDPE.

Conclusion

Studying of the formation of (BD) plastic fragments and their degradation in real field conditions on a long term is crucial for evaluating their impact on the environment as well as on agricultural production. Several challenges still need to be addressed.

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Degradation Dynamics of Conventional and Biodegradable Mulch Films in Agricultural Soils

Skaistė Dreskiniųė, Karolina Barčauskaitė, Monika Vilkienė
skaiste.dreskiniene@yahoo.com

Lithuanian Research Centre for Agriculture and Forestry, Akademija, Lithuania

Introduction

Plastic mulch films are widely used in agriculture, but their persistence in soils leads to concerns over environmental pollution. Conventional polymer, such as **polypropylene (PP)** and **polyethylene (PE)**, degrade very slowly, whereas **biodegradable films** are promoted as more sustainable alternatives. However, their actual degradation under field conditions remains insufficiently understood. This study aimed to evaluate the degradation dynamics of PP, PE and biodegradable films over one year under soil and different burial depths influence.

Methods

A field experiment was conducted in Akademija, Kėdainiai district Cambisol soil in . Samples of PP, PE and biodegradable mulch films were buried at two depths (10 cm and 20 cm) and retrieved after 6 and 12 months. Attenuated Total Reflectance–Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) was applied to assess chemical changes in polymer structure.

Results

sample	r	nRMSE, %
PP		
12m_10cm	0.701	22.0
12m_20cm	0.76	17.8
6m_10cm	0.698	20.3
6m_20cm	0.83	19.1
Bio		
12m_10cm	0.82	15.4
12m_20cm	0.92	11.9
6m_10cm	0.85	13.2
6m_20cm	0.94	10.2
PE		
12m_10cm	0.92	5.5
12m_20cm	0.82	9.5
6m_10cm	0.71	14.8
6m_20cm	0.85	8.3

Conclusion

The findings confirm that conventional polymers persist with different degradation over one year, while biodegradable films degrade more extensively under field conditions. More analyses are planned to be conducted. These results highlight the importance of long-term field testing to assess the environmental sustainability of agricultural plastic films and their role in soil microplastic pollution.

Early Plasticrust Formation and Rock-Plastic Interaction Risks in a Caribbean Coastal Zone (Santo Domingo)

Gurusamy Kutralam-Muniasamy¹, V.C. Shruti², Fermin Pérez-Guevara², Ricardo Cuenca Alvarez¹

¹Centro de Investigación e Innovación Tecnológica. IPN Cda. de Cecati s/n, Santa Catarina, Azcapotzalco, CDMX, México
²Department of Biotechnology and Bioengineering, CINVESTAV-IPN, Av IPN 2508, San Pedro Zacatenco, GAM, CDMX, México; mgurusamy@cinvestav.mx

BACKGROUND & OBJECTIVES

Plastic-Rock Interactions: Plastics are bonding with rocks, forming hybrid pollution like plasticrusts—blurring nature–synthetic boundaries.

Unquantified Risk: No standard tools exist to measure or compare plastic–rock interactions; most data remain observational.

The Research Gap: No indices exist to assess the form, extent, or risk of plastic–rock formations.

Local Blind Spot: This study provides the first evidence of plastic–rock interactions on Santo Domingo’s polluted coast, addressing a key geographic gap.

The Opportunity: Field-Based Classification

This study uses field surveys and analysis to: **Classify** types of plastic–rock interactions; **Measure** adherence, coverage, and weathering; **Assess** potential ecological and coastal risks

METHODS

RESULTS

KEY OBSERVATIONS

- PII shows inverse relationships with physical metrics, indicating plastic integration vary independently from size.
- Peeling Risk Index is strongly driven by MPRD ($r = 0.71$) and edge complexity ($r = 0.66$).
- Macroplastics form stable clusters, while fibres exhibit wider dispersal.
- High-risk zones are localized.

CONCLUSIONS

- Introduces a standardized index framework for monitoring
- Advances understanding of how coastal geology influences plastic persistence

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DISCUSSION

- Edge complexity indicates fragmentation and weathering
- Opaque plastics (high MPRD) resist integration with surroundings
- Stable macroplastic clusters suggest accumulation zones
- Localized risks require targeted mitigation strategies
- Spectral properties enable detection of "hidden" plastics
- Fibers pose different risks due to high mobility

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Ecological Footprint of Livestock Farming: Microplastic Contamination in Agricultural Soil and Water

Suzana Knežević¹, Milena Milojević¹, and Aleksandra Milošević²

¹Academy of Applied Studies Šabac, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Faculty of Law, Serbia
s.knezevic@akademijasabac.edu.rs

Background & Objectives

Microplastic pollution has emerged as a significant environmental concern, increasingly recognized in agricultural soils and waters. Livestock farming has been identified as a potential source of microplastics, primarily through the application of manure containing synthetic residues. Additionally, certain veterinary pharmaceuticals used on farms have been found to contain microplastic particles, contributing to environmental load. This review explores the extent to which livestock-related activities contribute to microplastic contamination and their impact on the ecological footprint of agroecosystems (Figure 1).

Methods

A systematic review of peer-reviewed literature published between 2015 and 2025 was conducted. The selection criteria focused on studies reporting microplastic presence in animal manure, agricultural soils, and drainage water. Emphasis was placed on identifying pathways of microplastic movement and accumulation resulting from livestock farming practices.

Figure 1 Microplastic Contamination Pathways in Agricultural Soil and Water from Livestock Farming

Results

Studies indicate that continuous application of pig manure leads to significantly elevated levels of microplastics in soils—rising from baseline concentrations of ~16 particles/kg to over 40 particles/kg in treated fields. In specific agricultural zones, concentrations in raw manure have reached up to 88,000 particles/kg. Evidence suggests horizontal transport from treated soils to adjacent fields, and vertical migration into drainage systems, confirming their mobility beyond initial application zones.

Conclusion

Livestock farming contributes notably to the introduction and spread of microplastics in agroecosystems, exacerbating environmental degradation through soil and water contamination. The presence of microplastics in veterinary drugs represents an additional, often overlooked pathway. Effective management of manure, pharmaceuticals, and plastic waste in agriculture is essential to mitigate ecological impact and promote sustainability.

Harnessing Mushroom Waste for Green Synthesis of ZnO Nanoparticles: A Sustainable Route Toward Soil Microplastic Remediation

Alok Ranjan Kerketta¹, Martin Šebesta¹

¹Comenius University Bratislava, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Institute of Laboratory Research on Geomaterials, Mlynská dolina, Ilkovičova 6, 842 15 Bratislava, Slovak republic

Introduction

- Global microplastic and heavy metal contamination threaten environmental and food security¹.
- Green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles from fungal extract provide sustainable photocatalytic remediation alternative to conventional chemical synthesis^{2,3}.
- This research optimizes synthesis conditions and evaluates effectiveness compared to industrial materials.

Pleurotus ostreatus

- Pleurotus ostreatus* (oyster mushroom) is widely cultivated globally and easily available in Slovakia due to its growth on abundant agricultural waste substrates.
- The Spent mycelium substrate (SMS) is a cheap, sustainable waste biomass rich in biomolecules, offering an eco-friendly resource for large-scale nanoparticle synthesis.
- Its biological and chemical composition includes potent reducing and capping agents such as polysaccharides (β -glucans), proteins, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and enzymes⁴.
- These biomolecules facilitate effective reduction of metal ions and stabilization of ZnO nanoparticles, making *Pleurotus* a cost-effective, scalable source for green nanomaterial production with minimal environmental impact⁵.

Synthesis mechanism

Methodology

1. Process of Fungal Extract Preparation

2. Green Synthesis of Nanoparticles (ZnO) process

Results

Discussion

- Higher pH enables synchronized nucleation producing uniform particles with enhanced stability through enhanced bioactive capping.
- Plant compounds reduce metal ions and create organic coating lowering band gap for visible light activation
- Post-treatment improves commercial materials, bridging lab optimization to industrial scalability.
- Green synthesis offers superior stability and sustainability for practical microplastics remediation

Future directions

- Advanced analysis (TEM/SEM) validating nanoparticle structure and surface properties.
- Apply nanoparticles on plants to prevent micro/nanoplastic, and toxic element (As/Cd) uptake and translocation.
- Photocatalytic breakdown of PE/PP/PET plastics into non-toxic products under visible light; characterize degradation pathways; compare nanoparticle types; demonstrate sustainable plastic waste remediation.

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Identification of microplastic particles in water supply system of Rogoźno (Greater Poland Voivodeship, Poland)

Agnieszka Szuster-Janiaczyk¹, Beata Madrecka-Witkowska¹, Aleksandra Dajema¹, Karolina Olszewska², Tomasz Runka²

¹Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Energy, Poznan, Poland
²Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Materials Science and Technical Physics, Poznan, Poland
beata.madrecka@put.poznan.pl

INTRODUCTION AND AIMS OF THE RESEARCH

- Synthetic polymers are widely used in the production of pipes for water supply systems (WSS). These substances can be released to drinking water as a result of degradation, leaching, aging etc.
- The aim of this research was to investigate the presence of microplastic in WSS in the urban-rural commune of Rogoźno located in Greater Poland Voivodeship.

METHODS

- Drinking water for the Rogoźno commune (approx. 18000 inhabitants). is produced by 3 water treatment plants located in Rogoźno, Gościejewo and Słomowo, and provided to consumers via the integrated water supply network (WSN).
- All WTPs use groundwater intakes. Water demand is primarily covered by the in Rogoźno intake, which utilizes 6 wells constructed in 1972-2022.
- The water treatment technology at this WTP includes cascade aeration, coagulation, two-stage pressure filtration for iron and manganese removal, and disinfection with sodium hypochlorite.
- WSN is approx. 213 km long and consists primarily of PVC pipes.
- Water samples for microplastic analysis were collected four times at WTP and WSN. For each water sample, a volume of 5 liters was filtered through 0.45 μ m nylon filters. MPs were identified using a Renishaw InVia Raman microscope. Data analysis included peak position, intensity, integral intensity, and FWHM determined using Wire 5.6 software. Identification of particles/fibers was performed at 25 random spots per filter (10 spots at 100 \times and 15 at 150 \times).

RESULTS

Total number and percentage of different types of particles and fibers

Number of different types of particles and fibers identified for each sampling point on the 4 sampling dates

CONCLUSIONS

- The number of detected MPs particles and fibers was very low (<3 per sample).
- Most of the analysed particles were mineral or unidentified.
- The very low amount of MPs content may result from low release from WSS or difficulties in sample preparation.
- Some samples (e.g. 1A) were very difficult to analyze due to high concentration of total suspended solids.
- To conduct valuable scientific research, there is a significant need to develop a detailed analysis methodology, especially regarding sample preparation prior to microscopic analysis.

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MICROM Conference MICROPlastics in Organic-rich Matrices 26 – 27 of November 2025 Novi Sad, Serbia

Impact of plastic mulching and road proximity on microplastic pollution in agricultural soils: Insights into weathering characteristics, elemental association, and ecological risk

IISER KOLKATA

Jayant Karwadiya^a, Alok Ranjan Kerketta^a, Saurabh Kumar Pathak^b, Sudhakar Srivastava^a, Gopala Krishna Darbha^a
^a- Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Kolkata, India 741246
^b- Institute of Environment and Sustainable Development, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, India 221005

Introduction

Plasticulture- Use of plastics in agriculture

Global Production of Agricultural Plastics

Methodology

Study Area- Bihar

Results

Macroplastics & microplastics abundance in agricultural soils

Morphological and polymer characterisation of Soil MPs

Multidimensional risk assessment of agricultural soils

SEM images of soil-extracted MPs

Weathering properties of soil-extracted plastics

Elemental enrichment on MPs and in bulk soils

Conclusions

- High MP levels in mulched fields near roads (803 ± 371 particles kg⁻¹ soil)
- PE and PP made up over 95 % of identified MPs in agricultural soils.
- MPs showed a higher carbonyl index (CI) than larger MaPs, indicating weathering.
- Higher Zn adsorbed onto soil-extracted MPs than bulk soil.
- MultiMP score classifies the agricultural fields at high risk.

Contact

Jayant Karwadiya, IISER Kolkata, India
 Email: jayantkarwadiya@gmail.com
 LinkedIn: jk21rs06@iiserkol.ac.in

PMRF Ministry of Education

Microplastics assessments in Moroccan Mediterranean Bivalve mollusks (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Callista chione*)

Mostapha Benomar¹, Yosra Ajbar², Soumaya Terrestri³, Chafiq Lahcen⁴
¹ Regional centre of National Institute of Fisheries Research, Tangier, Morocco
² Faculty of Science and Technology, Abdelmalek Essaâdi University, Tangier, Morocco
³ Faculty of Sciences, Abdelmalek Essaâdi University, Tetouan, Morocco
⁴ Regional centre of National Institute of Fisheries Research, Nador, Morocco

Introduction

The Moroccan Mediterranean Sea holds great economic potential in the areas of tourism, fishing, and maritime transport, however it is affected by plastic pollution, notably microplastics (MPs). In 2025, bivalve mollusks were collected from Moroccan Mediterranean coast at seven sites to assess MP contamination: Kabila (site 1), M'diq (site 2), Oued Laou (site 3), Cala Iris (site 4), Torres (site 5), Ras El Ma (site 6), and Saïdia (site 7). Varnish shells (*Callista chione*) were collected in the western Mediterranean and mussels (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) in the east. MPs were analyzed according to their size, color, shape, and abundance.

Analytical Protocol

Forms & Colors of Mps

Figure 1 : Analytical protocol for MPs detection in (*Callista chione*) and (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*) samples

Figure 2 : Different forms and colors of microplastics detected in the studied samples: (a) red fiber (40x), (b) brown foam (40x), (c) red line, (d) black line (100x), (e) blue fiber (40x), (f) black pellet (100x), (g) transparent film (100x), (h) transparent fiber (40x), (i) red fragment (100x)

Abundance and Sizes of MPs

Figure 3 : Abundance of microplastics in each sampling site

Figure 4 : Proportion of MPs in different size at each sampling site

Conclusion & Outlook

- Microplastics were successfully identified in *Callista chione* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis*
- The abundance of microplastics per individual varies across the studied sites, from highest to lowest: Rass El Ma (17.83 items/individual), Torres (14.2 items/individual), Oued Laou (13.3 items/individual), Kabila (9.43 items/individual), M'diq (4.92 items/individual), and Saïdia (4.08 items/individual)
- Fibers and fragments were the dominant forms, with sizes ranging from 1–250 μm
- Transparent particles were most common, followed by blue, brown, red, black, and green
- Future work: polymer identification (FTIR/Raman) and assessment of ecological impacts

Microplastics Contamination in Aquatic Ecosystems: Challenges in Extraction and Ecological Risk Assessment

Marijana Nikolić¹, Aleksandra Tubić², Marija Jakovljević¹, Branko Kordić², Branislav Jović², and Vladica Simić¹

¹University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Science, Department of Biology and Ecology, Kragujevac, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Science, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract:

Microplastics (MPs) contamination is a growing environmental concern, originating from diverse sources such as municipal solid waste landfills, plastic packaging, road runoff, and agricultural activities. Once in the environment, plastic degrades into micro- and nanoplastics, which interact with organic matter and pollutants, complicating their extraction and analysis. Understanding these interactions is crucial for assessing the ecological risks of MPs and their role as pollutant vectors. Riverine MPs pollution has been extensively studied for over a decade, with research focused on quantification and characterization. As particle size decreases, MPs become more bioavailable, increasing the risk of uptake by lower trophic levels. MPs act as carriers for pollutants from the aqueous phase and release chemical additives upon ingestion, raising concerns about their potential toxicity.

A major challenge in MPs research is the extraction of particles from complex organic matrices. The choice of methods must balance efficiency with minimal damage to MPs structure. Visual sorting remains a key step before chemical digestion. Sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) has proven effective in processing benthopelagic fish samples, specifically the common bleak (*Alburnus alburnus*), preserving the integrity of MPs particles while successfully digesting organic matter.

Despite the ubiquity of MPs in aquatic environments—detected across species and throughout the water column—methodological inconsistencies hinder large-scale comparative analyses. To improve reliability, a standardized methodology adapted to different biological materials is necessary for accurate risk assessment and environmental monitoring. This research aims to enhance our understanding of MPs-pollutant interactions and develop robust analytical approaches to evaluate their ecological impact better.

Picture 1. Filaments found in the stomach content of fish (a) visually identifying; b) after chemical digestion with NaClO

Materials and methods

Gruža Lake (Picture 2) is an artificial reservoir located in Central Serbia, primarily used for water supply (Čomić & Ostojić, 2005). Fish from this lake, particularly common bleak, are frequently consumed in the region (Simić et al., 2016).

Potential sources of microplastics (MPs) pollution include numerous cottages, houses, and restaurants surrounding the lake, as well as recreational fishing activities that contribute to environmental contamination through lost fishing lines, lures, and plastic waste.

To isolate potential microplastics particles from biological material, visual sorting was initially conducted to separate larger organic debris. Subsequently, sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) was applied to digest the remaining organic matter in samples of common bleak (*Alburnus alburnus*), ensuring efficient removal of biological material while preserving the structural integrity of microplastics.

Results and discussion

During 2024, specimens of common bleak (*Alburnus alburnus*, Picture 2) were sampled from three sites within Gruža Lake (Picture 2) to evaluate microplastics (MPs) contamination, as this species - being a key component of both the lake's ecosystem and the human diet - is highly susceptible to MPs ingestion and thus serves as a relevant bioindicator of aquatic pollution.

MPs isolation was performed using NaClO (sodium hypochlorite) digestion, a non-destructive method that preserves particle integrity. Picture 1 confirms that extracted MPs retain their original morphology, ensuring reliable analysis.

These findings underscore the need for continuous MPs monitoring in freshwater fish, particularly those consumed by humans. Improved waste management around Gruža Lake is essential to reducing pollution, while further research should assess long-term ecological and health risks.

Picture 2. Gruža Lake; common bleak *Alburnus alburnus*

Acknowledgments

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Packaging as a Source of Microplastics in the Food Supply Chain: Evidence from Packaged Chicken Meat

Tina ŠAULA^{1*}, Živa ZIDAR¹, Sonja SMOLE MOŽINA¹, Manca KOVAČ VIRŠEK², Anja KLANČNIK¹

¹Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
²National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana, Slovenia

*tina.saula@bf.uni-lj.si

INTRODUCTION

Microplastics (MPs) are increasingly recognised as emerging food safety hazard due to their ubiquitous presence in the environment and their ability to adsorb or transport chemical and biological contaminants. Within food production systems, MPs can originate from various sources, including packaging, potentially accumulating on the food surface. MPs in food represent a possible route of consumer exposure.

THE AIM OF THE STUDY

This study aims to assess the occurrence of MPs on the surface of packaged chicken meat from various producers and packaging types.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

RESULTS

- ❖ 1 to 6 particles/50 g meat surface,
- ❖ as fibres or films,
- ❖ ranging in size from 0.2 to 2.2 mm,
- ❖ mostly translucent or green, which corresponds to the colour and polymer composition of the packaging material,
- ❖ other types of polymers have also been detected, indicating other routes of contamination likely to occur during meat processing.

CONCLUSIONS

- ✓ MPs from packaging and also from other sources are present on the surface of chicken meat and thus pose a direct (physical, chemical) and indirect (microbiological) risk for food contamination.
- ✓ The findings confirm that packaged chicken meat can act as a vector for human exposure to MPs, originating from packaging and other environmental sources.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Exposure to indoor pollutants – volatile organic compounds, phthalates, bisphenol A - in small-cell vs. non-small-cell advanced lung cancer patients

Jana Pavlović¹, Danica Szadanić-Velikić^{2,3}, Mirjana Ševo^{2,4}, Jovan Kulić¹, Maja Milanović², Nataša Milošević² and Nataša Milić²

¹University of East Sarajevo, Faculty of Medicine Foča, Foča, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

³Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Clinic for Pulmonary Oncology, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

⁴IMC Banja Luka-Center of Radiotherapy, Part of Affidea Group, Banja Luka, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina

jana.stojanovic@ues.rs.ba

Background & Objectives

As lung cancer became the fifth leading cause of cancer-related death among non-smokers, scientific focus shifted to other risk factors, including environmental pollution [1]. This study assessed potential exposure to indoor pollutants: volatile organic compounds (VOCs), phthalates, and bisphenol A (BPA), in newly diagnosed advanced lung cancer patients and compared these exposures between small-cell (SCLC) and non-small-cell (NSCLC) lung cancer types.

Methods

In this study, 205 newly diagnosed patients with IIIB/IV stage of either SCLC or NSCLC (111 men vs. 94 women) from Vojvodina, Serbia, were surveyed for selected environmental factors through questionnaire.

Sources of VOC and Phthalates

Results

Among respondents, 44.9% reported using air fresheners in homes, cars, and offices, 42.9% used deodorants $\geq 3x$ /week, while 19.5% applied perfumes daily. Scented laundry detergents, fabric softeners, and household cleaning products were commonly used by 96.1%, 94.6%, and 95.6% of participants, respectively. No significant differences were found between SCLC and NSCLC patients regarding the use of the scented products as possible sources of VOC and phthalates. Only 7.3% used organic, fragrance-free alternatives. Men with NSCLC were more frequently exposed to scented cleaning products than women ($p=0.049$), whereas women with NSCLC favored organic, fragrance-free products more often ($p=0.007$). Deodorant use was higher among women across both cancer types ($p \leq 0.006$). Consumption of instant soups and canned foods as probable source of BPA was similar between groups, although men with SCLC used canned foods more than women ($p=0.010$). Most respondents reported never using plastic containers for heating food which was observed as BPA and phthalates source of exposure.

BPA sources

Conclusions

The use of fragranced products was predominantly associated with gender rather than with the cancer type. Our findings also indicate that men more frequently consume canned foods, which are potential sources of endocrine disruptors and warrant further investigation as probable risk factors for lung cancer.

Acknowledgments

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Microbial community structure in landfill soils: Case study in Serbia

Gordana Racić¹, Igor Vukelić², Nataša Stojić³, Ljiljana Čurčić³, Galina Čurčić³, Jozefien Demeulenaere⁴, Caroline de Tender⁴

¹ Research and Development Institute Tamiš d.o.o., Novoseljski put 33, 26000 Pančevo, Serbia

² Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Maksima Gorkog 30, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

³ Faculty of Environmental Protection, Educons University, 21208 Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

⁴ Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

Background and objectives

Microorganisms are vital for soil health and demonstrate an adaptive capacity to environmental change, with their role in plastic biodegradation increasingly recognized. Complex and dynamic interplay, and the critical role soil microorganisms play in ecosystem health, it raises issue to precisely investigate the composition, diversity, and functional potential of microbial communities in terrestrial habitats. Understanding these alterations is crucial not only for assessing the ecological impact of microplastic pollution but also for identifying microorganisms with bioremediation potential. This is why the precise identification, taxonomic classification, and ecological role elucidation of soil microbial community members recent advancements based on DNA sequencing have become important tool, enabling detailed analysis and understanding of microbial communities. Main purpose of this case study was to analyse bacterial and fungal communities in soils where high numbers of microplastics are expected.

Methods

Soil samples were collected from three land use types: active landfill, remediated landfill, and agricultural soil (Figure 1). From each field, we took 3 replicates and isolated all DNA from soil samples of the top soil layer (0-10 cm). Microbial community profiling was performed using Illumina amplicon sequencing, making use of a Novaseq (2x300 bp, paired-end), targeting the V3-V4 fragment of the 16S rRNA gene (bacteria), and ITS2 rDNA region (fungi).

Figure 1: Sampling locations (active landfill, remediated landfill, and agricultural soil)

Results

Sequencing analysis showed shifts in microbial community structure across the tested soil types (Figure 2). In the agricultural soil (control), the bacterial community was dominated by *Pseudomonadota* (50%) and *Actinomycetota* (20–25%). The active landfill exhibited a significant reduction in both species, with a strong increase in *Bacteroidota* (Figure 3). This change in community structure was proven by a PERMANOVA analysis (0,001) showing a statistical difference in microbial community in between the two land types. In the remediated landfill the relative abundance of *Pseudomonadota* was higher than in the active landfill but still lower than in the control. This indicates that the long-term effects of landfill continue to prevent a full return of microbial communities to the structure observed in the agricultural soil, served as control. However, we do acknowledge that the effects could also be soil dependent and should be evaluated further with information regarding nutrient status, organic matter content, microplastic content and soil texture.

Figure 2: Alpha diversity (Shannon-Wiener index) of bacterial communities originating from active landfills (red), agricultural land (green) and remediated landfills (blue). Although no statistical difference can be observed in average diversity, the variability in between soil samples severely reduced when soils are remediated

Figure 3: Stacked bar chart representing the bacterial community composition of three soil types. Overall, a shift in bacterial community can be noted from active landfill towards remediated landfills and agricultural soils, with a higher relative abundance of *Pseudomonadota* when soils contain less plastic.

Conclusions:

These findings highlight the lasting impact of land use and remediation efforts on soil microbial communities, aligning with existing results on environmental stress and community composition.

Acknowledgement

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Managing Microplastics for Sustainable Agriculture: Legal and Policy Perspectives from the EU and Serbia

Biljana Panin¹, Ljiljana Milošević¹, Nataša Stojić¹, Mira Pucarević¹, Dunja Prokić¹, Galina Ćurčić¹, Mislav Didara², Marcela Šperanda²

¹Educons University, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia

²Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek Faculty of Agrobiotechnical Sciences Osijek

contact person: biljana.panin@educons.edu.rs

Management of microplastics in agriculture is not an isolated environmental issue but a key area for achieving multiple goals of the 2030 Agenda – from resource protection and the attainment of sustainable agriculture to ensuring food safety and preserving ecosystems.

This paper examines existing legislation, regulatory frameworks, and policy measures addressing plastic management, with a particular focus on microplastic, within the framework of sustainable agriculture, focusing on the European Union (EU) and the Republic of Serbia.

Microplastics are governed through several major policy pillars in EU:

- EU Green Deal
- Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)
- Zero Pollution Action Plan
- EU Plastics Strategy

Key EU Regulations Relevant to Microplastics

Regulation / Directive	Waste	Water	Air	Soil	Food	Relevance to Microplastics
REACH Regulation (EC 1907/2006) + 2023 Restriction	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Restricts intentionally added microplastics; controls releases across all environmental media.
Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)	–	✓	–	✓ (indirect)	✓ (via irrigation)	Requires monitoring of pollutants including emerging ones such as microplastics.
Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (Recast)	✓	✓	–	–	✓	Introduces advanced treatment to reduce microplastics in effluents.
Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	Reduces plastic waste and prevents generation of secondary microplastics.
Drinking Water Directive (2020/2184)	–	✓	–	–	✓	Requires monitoring of microplastics in drinking water and setting future limit values.
Food Safety & Food Contact Materials Regulations (178/2002; 1935/2004)	–	–	–	–	✓	Microplastics treated as contaminants; controls migration from packaging into food.

SERBIAN LEGISLATION REGARDING MICROPLASTICS

Serbia has made progress in aligning its legislation regarding microplastics with EU laws, but there are still some areas where Serbia needs to improve its compliance with EU laws regarding microplastics

- The Law on Waste Management
- The Law on Packaging and Packaging Waste
- The Regulation on the list of waste prevention measures

CONCLUSIONS:

Achieving sustainable agriculture in both the EU and Serbia requires the development of a coherent and comprehensive regulatory framework that explicitly governs microplastic generation, use, and mitigation.

Addressing microplastics in agriculture is not only a regulatory challenge but also an opportunity: by aligning policies with scientific evidence,

Harmonized legal and policy approaches will protect natural resources, support climate change adaptation, and promote a transition toward sustainable agri-food systems for the future.

Acknowledgments

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AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE OF FARMERS, WINEGROWERS, AND STUDENTS ON MICROPLASTICS IN AGRICULTURAL SOIL

MISSION OF NETmicroplastic

Deepen our knowledge and foster science-based, multi-dimensional assessment of microplastics in soil

To address the many gaps in our understanding of the sources and pathways of microplastics in agricultural environments, the NETmicroplastic partnership, initiated by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT), connects actors and stakeholders from relevant sectors through workshops, webinars and science communication events. A strong knowledge base has been built through tailored surveys of farmers and winegrowers, students, compost facility owners and waste management companies.

The data was supplemented by information gathered at agricultural fairs from plastic tool manufacturers and distributors, and from interviews with recycling facilities, to produce a comprehensive regional concept paper.

STUDENTS' VIEW

The student survey was conducted 2023 online via the easyfeedback platform and distributed through the Austrian National Union of Students (ÖH), agricultural colleges, and university partners. This email survey among students (n=417) in Lower Austria reveals that students from all fields are well-informed about microplastics. While 98% of students have heard of microplastics, most associate them with water and marine pollution (88%) rather than agriculture (22%), with 16% unaware of their presence in soil. Students' knowledge is highest for microplastics in water bodies and lowest for those in agriculture.

The internet (82%) and television (68%) are the primary sources of information, while scientific journals (37%) and courses (36%) are less influential.

The main sources of microplastics in soil, according to respondents, are littering, fertilizer use, and tire wear. A majority (53%) believe microplastics are very harmful. While 65% have heard of bioplastics, 49% think they are less harmful than conventional plastics, though the term "bio" leads to oversimplified positive associations. The survey suggests the need for clearer communication about the different types of plastic, especially bioplastics, and their environmental impact.

FARMERS' AND WINEGROWERS' VIEW

In cooperation with the Chamber of Agriculture of Lower Austria, an online survey was conducted on plastic materials and equipment used in agriculture. The majority (85-100%) of respondents (n=97) are aware that film, nets, irrigation pipes, clips and growing sheets contain or are made of plastic, while knowledge of plastic in fertilisers (14%), treated/coated seeds (9%) and plant protection products (36%) is limited.

The majority of respondents (87%) would be willing to try alternative products, especially twine for tying vines and straw bales, irrigation products, fertilisers and plant production products, if they were in the same price range and of comparable quality in terms of handling and durability to conventional products.

Awareness of certification labels for biodegradable plastic products was low, with only 21% of respondents recognising the TÜV Austria label and only 3.4% having ever heard of the DIN label.

% Farmers using plastic products

Conclusions

Awareness and concern about microplastic pollution are high, though discussion focuses on waterborne microplastics. Knowledge is mainly media-driven, with limited attention to soil contamination. Promoting sustainable plastic use in agriculture requires clear policy guidelines, farmer incentives, and more information on biodegradable products' technical performance in field conditions.

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Microplastics: Invisible but Everywhere

Microplastics are present in air, water and soil, posing risks to ecosystems and human health. Despite increasing scientific knowledge, awareness, especially among youth, is limited.

At the Faculty of Environmental Protection, we aim to bridge this gap through science communication and environmental education at all school levels. Our goal is to help young people understand the sources and impacts of microplastics and to encourage sustainable behaviors that reduce plastic pollution.

Workshop Themes

Microplastics in Textiles

Participants investigate microfibers released from synthetic garments, explore their environmental impact, and try to recognize natural and synthetic fabrics through a blind test, promoting reflection on personal choices and sustainable alternatives.

Microplastics in Cosmetics

Participants identify microplastics in everyday cosmetics, examine their environmental and health effects, and create their own products from natural ingredients, encouraging responsible consumption and creativity.

Microplastics in the Environment

Participants explore how microplastics move through air, water, and soil, study their effects on living organisms, and perform hands-on tasks like river sampling and microscope analysis to build environmental awareness.

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Micro(μ)School

Program developed as part of four Erasmus+ projects (MicPlaPROB, EDU4PlastiCircular, GreenGate, GreenGate2) offering interdisciplinary workshops for primary, secondary, and tertiary students.

The workshops use digital tools, interactive activities, and real-life examples (e.g., microplastics in textiles and cosmetics) to actively engage youth and educators. The program aligns with EU guidelines, including the European Green Deal and the Council Recommendation on Learning for the Green Transition.

Results

Over a three-year period, we organized 21 educational events reaching more than 1,000 young people of different educational levels within the Micro(μ)School program.

The largest share of participants were elementary school students (44%), who were especially active in the textiles workshop. Secondary school students (40%) were most engaged in environment-focused activities, while higher education students (16%) participated more evenly across all three themes (Figure 1). Through online courses, video production, field excursions, interactive apps, and hands-on workshops, participants gained knowledge, developed green and digital competences, and became actively involved in proposing innovative local solutions. The activities fostered environmental awareness and community engagement, highlighting the real-world impact of microplastics pollution.

Figure 1. Participation in Micro(μ)School workshops by educational level and thematic focus.

Conclusion

Today's youth are among the first to understand the microplastics problem—and among the last with the power to act.

The Micro(μ)School program demonstrates how education can combine science, innovation, and green skills to engage young people in meaningful learning and drive the transition to a more sustainable future.

InPlasTwin – Increasing expertise in micro- and nanoplastics analysis through twinning action

Janja Vidmar¹, Quynh Nhu Phan Le^{2*}, Milica Velimirovic², Katrin Loeschner³, Nanna B. Hartmann⁴, André Marcel Bienfait⁵, Dimitrios Savvas⁶, Gordana Racić⁷, Mladen Radišić⁷

¹ Department of Environmental Sciences, Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia
² Laboratory for inorganic and organic analysis, Flemish Institute for Technological Research, Mol, Belgium
³ National Food Institute, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
⁴ Department of Environmental and Resource Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Kgs. Lyngby, Denmark
⁵ Institute of Marine Research, Bergen, Norway
⁶ Department of Crop Science, Agricultural University of Athens, Athens, Greece
⁷ Foodscale Hub, Novi Sad, Serbia

*nhu.phan@vito.be

Background

Plastics have become an integral part of modern agricultural practices, offering several benefits that increase crop yields. Mulching films, made from conventional polymers or biodegradable alternatives, are one of the most common applications. However, their extensive use and improper disposal have resulted in a significant accumulation of plastic materials in soils. Over time, these mulching films degrade into micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), which can persist in the environment or be ingested by biota, posing potential risks to plant health and human safety. This contamination is of particular concern because both synthetic plastics and bioplastics contain chemical additives that can leach into the environment and enter the food chain. Given the limited research on the release of MNPs after mulching film degradation and their subsequent effects on edible plants, the InPlasTwin project was proposed.

The concept of the InPlasTwin methodology

Partners of InPlasTwin Project

InPlasTwin unites six partners from widening (Slovenia, Greece, Serbia) and non-widening countries (Belgium, Denmark, Norway) with expertise in natural sciences, biogeochemistry, analytical chemistry, agriculture, and innovation management.

InPlasTwin: A Roadmap for Scientific Capacity Building

Investigating the degradability of mulching films and the impact of the released MNPs on the environment and food.

InPlasTwin – Increasing expertise in micro- and nanoplastics analysis through twinning action
 Programme: HORIZON-AL1 – Widening participation and spreading excellence. Type of action: HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
 Duration: 1 October 2024 – 30 September 2027. Coordinator: Institut Jožef Stefan. Total budget: 1,400,000.00 €

Strawberry fields located in Varda, Iliia Prefecture in Western Peloponnese, Greece (photo taken by Prof. Dr. Dimitrios Savvas)

Microplastics in suspended sediments of the Danube River – preliminary results of the SUNDANSE project research

Yevhen Nasiedkin^{1,2}, Ruslan Havryliuk^{1,3}, Mihaela Timofti⁴, Madalina Calmuc⁵, Vladyslav Balinsky¹

¹National Ecological Centre of Ukraine,
²Center for Problems of Marine Geology, Geoecology and Sedimentary Ore Formation of NAS of Ukraine,
³Institute of Geological Sciences of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine,
⁴Dunarea de Jos University of Galati, Faculty of Sciences and Environment & REXDAN Research Infrastructure,
⁵Dunarea de Jos University of Galati, REXDAN Research Infrastructure

Background & Objectives

There are a significant number of publications on the transport of MPs in the Danube by water flows, their distribution in bottom sediments or biological objects. Most studies focus on transport by water currents, with pollutants being collected from the water surface using plankton samplers such as manta trawls or other means of filtering water flow through mesh filters with a cell size of 200-300 µm.

Methods

An experiment on long-term sampling of suspended solids using sedimentation traps was made. The testing site and location of the equipment is the Danube water area adjacent to the town of Vylkove (Ukraine). The water depth at the sampling site is 1 m. The patented equipment belongs to the "passive samplers" type, representing sedimentation traps designed for sampling suspended sediments.

Fig. 1 Sampling location (red circle), patented tools, and the technique used for sampling the analyzed suspended sediment

Results

During the research period, four samples of natural material were processed, each of which was accumulated over a period of one month between January and May 2025. As a rule, the total number of fragments separated from the main mass of the sample of mineral, organic, and anthropogenic origin ranged from 50 to 1,500 specimens and included, in addition to particles of artificial polymers, various organic (fragments of shells or shells of organisms and plants, in particular bark, stems, and branches) and loose mineral aggregates.

Fig. 2 Various components identified in the analyzed samples

A significant amount of carbon fragments was also observed in the samples, varying considerably for different sampling points and areas in terms of both quantitative and qualitative (dimension, morphological types, composition) indicators.

Fig. 3 Previously identified MP particles that could not be confirmed by Raman spectrometry because of their size

In addition to polyethylene, polypropylene, and polystyrene, which are typical for aquatic environments, one particle of polyethylene terephthalate was also confirmed.

Fig. 4 Microplastic particles from sediment samples and their Raman spectral analysis

Fig. 5 Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)

Conclusions

The study area is defined by the influence of the Danube water mass, and the mineral, organic, and anthropogenic suspended solids it carries partially reach this shelf zone and participate in sedimentation processes. A number of peculiarities in the distribution of MP fragments in the lower Danube suspension were revealed in comparison with particles studied in surface bottom sediments of shelf areas within the territorial waters of Romania in earlier studies. The comparison is preliminary in nature due to the small number of suspended matter in the samples and requires clarification with the involvement of a larger amount of field material.

Methodological Challenges of Microplastic Sampling and Analysis in the Framework of the MicroDrink Project

Branislav Petrović^{1,*}, Ana Selak², Gábor Bordós³, Sebastian Koeppl⁴, Lindinger Helga⁴, Uta Wemhöner⁴, Jadranka Šangulin⁵, Mirna Švec², Ljiljana Vasić¹, Saša Milanović¹, Veljko Marinović¹, Jelena Močević¹, Jasmina Lukač Reberski², Ivana Boljat², Marek Poláček⁶, Anja Torkar⁷, Mihael Brenčić⁸, Mohammed Alqadi⁸, Gabriele Chiogna⁸
brasilav.petrovic@rgf.bg.ac.rs

¹University of Belgrade, Faculty of Mining and Geology, Belgrade, Serbia; ²Croatian Geological Survey, Zagreb, Croatia; ³Eurofins Analytical Services Hungary Kft., Budapest, Hungary; ⁴Environment Agency Austria, Vienna, Austria; ⁵Institute of Public Health Zadar, Croatia; ⁶T. G. Masaryk Water Research Institute, Brno, The Czech Republic; ⁷Department of Geology, University of Ljubljana, Slovenia; ⁸Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Erlangen, Germany

The presence of **microplastics in drinking water resources** is a growing concern, highlighting the urgent need for robust and standardized methods to accurately measure concentrations and assess potential environmental and human health impacts of MP.

A lack of standardized methods for **MP monitoring (water sampling and laboratory analysis)** and varying national capacities pose significant obstacles and challenges across the **entire EU** as well as in the **Danube River Basin (DRB)**. To address this, the MicroDrink project was launched with the primary goal of enhancing DRB capacity for managing MP pollution.

Based on the specific **Commission Delegated Decision (EU) 2024/1441**, the proposed approach involved **filtering 1,000 litres of water through two 20 µm stainless-steel filters** (first filter: sample, second: blank), maintaining a flow rate below 1 l/s.

Research on the presence of MP in drinking water resources is carried out in **9 pilot areas** in all **8 participating countries**. In Serbia, microplastics in drinking water sources are monitored in **two pilot areas**.

The initial sampling campaign revealed several challenges:

- ✓ Excessive interference probably caused by rubber particles from the hoses
- ✓ The filter mesh was partially damaged or deformed due to excessive water pressure (and/or transport and handling)
- ✓ Local laboratories reported discrepancies in microplastics analysis results for duplicate samples (the same water sample)
- ✓ A high number of microplastic particles were unexpectedly found in the blank control sample, indicating potential impairments of the filter cascade functionality and/or contamination issues.

The project team proposed and implemented several solutions to improve the accuracy and consistency of microplastics monitoring:

- ✓ Recommending the flushing of rubber sampling hoses before use or replacing them with silicone or metal alternatives
- ✓ Carefully controlling the water flow rate to prevent filter damage and implementing more rigorous cleaning protocols for the filters (using an ultrasonic bath and rinsing equipment with pre-filtered deionized water)
- ✓ Using alternative types of filters to improve data reliability and reduce the risk of contamination.

The „Staničenje“ source (river bank filtration)

The „Pavliš“ source (intergranular aquifer)

- LinkedIn
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- YouTube

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www.sundanseproject.eu
info@sundanseproject.eu

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Frontier Lab's analytical pyrolyzer (EGA/PY-3030D) and accessories can be easily installed on almost all commercially available GC/MS systems.

In the recent years, Frontier Lab set the R&D focus on the development of accessories and software/libraries for Micro- and Nanoplastics analysis by Py-GC/MS:

- The new F-Search MPs software allows users to identify and quantify unknown microplastics in the environment, and it consists of a sophisticated search program and mass spectral libraries of pyrolyzates. The software is used with the data obtained by Py-GC/MS and the analytical process is very easy and straightforward. Also, a Microplastic Calibration Standard Kit was developed what includes mixtures of up to 12 polymers in different inorganic diluents for easy weighing and calibration.
- The Multi-Functional Sampler MFS-2015E makes splitless Pyrolysis without compromises possible, enabling 100x improved sensitivity (with LOQs in ng range). The MFS shortens analysis time by backflushing. The new Cryogenic Mill IQ MILL-2070 is easy to use and simple to operate. It pulverizes samples or micro plastic standards at highest uniformity, homogeneity, and reproducibility.

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The Collaborative Research Center (CRC) 1357 “Microplastics”, funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG), was established in 2019 at the University of Bayreuth.

The CRC investigates the increasing contamination of the environment by plastics worldwide and develops innovative solutions to counteract the resulting ecological, health and economic risks.

The close linking of interdisciplinary basic research with problem-related application research will enable well-founded risk assessments and further strengthen the transfer of knowledge to the public.

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